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Abstract

Astronomical imaging with ground-based telescopes suffers from quickly varying optical distortions, which cause blurring and loss of contrast. These optical distortions are induced by turbulences in the earth's atmosphere. Since the contrast and sharpness of images are essential for astronomical observations, a method that compensates for these aberrations is required. This technique is called Adaptive Optics (AO). It utilizes a combination of wavefront sensors, that measure the deformations of wavefronts emitted by guide stars, and deformable mirrors to correct for them. Classical AO systems, using only one guide star, achieve high image quality only near to this guide star. Since there are not enough bright guide stars available close to scientific objects of interest, AO systems that achieve a good correction over a large field have been developed. These systems involve a tomographic estimation of the 3D atmospheric wavefront disturbance. Mathematically, the reconstruction of turbulent layers in the atmosphere is severely ill-posed, hence, limits the achievable solution accuracy. Moreover, the reconstruction has to be performed in real-time at a few hundred to thousand Hertz frame rates. This leads to a computational challenge, especially for the AO systems of future Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs) with a primary mirror up to 40 m.

The aim of this work is to develop and implement an efficient real-time reconstruction algorithm on the high-performance hardware of the industrial partner Microgate. In particular, we present a novel, conjugate gradient (CG) based method called augmented Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm (augmented FEWHA) for atmospheric tomography. Our method is based on the classical FEWHA, which uses a dual-domain discretization strategy to obtain sparse operators. The matrix-free representation of these operators leads to a significant reduction in the computational load and memory. Moreover, the method is highly parallelizable. A crucial indicator for the run-time of iterative solvers is the number of iterations. We extend the classical FEWHA with an augmented Krylov subspace method in order to reduce the number of CG iterations. Moreover, we provide an efficient, parallel implementation of both algorithms on a multi-core CPU and a GPU. We analyze the performance of augmented FEWHA in terms of quality and run-time via numerical simulations for ELT-sized test configurations. As a quality benchmark we use the classical FEWHA, which is known to yield excellent results. In terms of run-time augmented FEWHA requires less CG iterations compared to the classical version, which results in a significant performance boost.

Zusammenfassung

Die astronomische Bilderfassung mit erdgebundenen Teleskopen leidet stark unter sich schnell veränderten optischen Effekten, welche Unschärfe und Kontrastverlust zur Folge haben. Diese Störungen werden durch Turbulenzen in der Erdatmosphäre hervorgerufen. Um die Bildqualität zu verbessern, werden sogenannte Adaptive Optik (AO) Systeme eingesetzt. Diese Systeme benutzen Wellenfrontsensoren, welche die Aberrationen der Lichtwellen von Leitsternen erkennen, sowie verformbare Spiegel, welche die atmosphärischen Störungen kompensieren. Klassische AO Systeme benutzen lediglich einen Leitstern und erreichen deshalb eine hohe Bildqualität nur für Objekte in der Nähe dieses Sterns. Da nicht genug helle Leitsterne für beliebige astronomische Objekte verfügbar sind, wurden AO Systeme entwickelt die eine gute Bildqualität über ein breites Sichtfeld liefern. Solche Systeme erfordern die tomografische Berechnung der dreidimensionalen atmosphärischen Wellenfrontstörungen. Aus mathematischer Sicht ist dieses Problem schlecht gestellt, d.h. die Lösungsgenauigkeit ist stark eingeschränkt. Zudem muss die Rekonstruktion in Echtzeit, bei einer Bildrate von einigen hundert bis zu tausend Hertz, passieren. Dies führt zu erheblichen Herausforderungen im Bereich der Rechenleistung, im Speziellen für die AO Systeme der zukünftigen Riesenteleskopen (ELTs), welche einen Primärspiegel von bis zu 40 m besitzen.

Das Ziel dieser Arbeit ist es, einen effizienten Echtzeitrekonstruktor zu entwickeln und in die Hardware des Industriepartners Microgate zu integrieren. Wir präsentieren den augmented Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm (augmented FEWHA), welcher auf dem klassischen FEWHA beruht und somit auf der Methode der konjugierten Gradienten. FEWHA benutzt eine duale Domän-Diskretisierungsstrategie, um eine effiziente matrixfreie Darstellung aller zugrundeliegenden Operatoren zu erhalten. Diese Darstellung reduziert den Rechenaufwand und die Speicherauslastung erheblich. Außerdem ist der Algorithmus sehr gut parallelisierbar. Ein entscheidender Faktor für die Laufzeit iterativer Löser ist die Anzahl der Iterationen. In dieser Arbeit erweitern wir FEWHA mit einer augmentierten Krylov-Unterraum-Methode und reduzieren so die Anzahl der Iterationen. Außerdem präsentieren wir eine parallele Implementierung beider Algorithmen auf einer multi-core CPU und einer GPU. Wir analysieren die Leistung des Algorithmus hinsichtlich Qualität und Laufzeit für ELT Testkonfigurationen. Letzendlich ist es uns möglich bei gleichbleibender Qualität die Anzahl der Iterationen für augmented FEWHA zu verringern und so die Laufzeit deutlich zu reduzieren.

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Bernadett Stadler
Linz, October 2021

*It is the
darkest nights
that produce
the brightest stars.*

JOHN GREEN

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Challenges in ground-based astronomy

More than 500 years ago Galileo invented the first telescope and started with extending the "eye" from 8 to 37 mm, allowing for an imaging of small objects so far undetectable for the naked eye. This factor of almost 5 started a revolution. Since then, ground-based astronomy is aspiring for larger telescope apertures. This ambition has been motivated through a better image quality, a larger field of view and a higher sensitivity, all playing a decisive role for astronomical observations. Nowadays, 8 to 10 m telescopes, like, the Keck Telescope, the Very Large Telescope (VLT), Subaru and Gemini, are celebrating scientific successes. Figure 1.1 shows a sketch of the evolution of telescopes over time.

Figure 1.1. The evolution of telescopes - from Galileo to the ELT.

These outstanding achievements raised the motivation of international teams to put their effort into the design of the next generation of Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs), which are planned to see first light by 2025–2030. With a diameter up to 40 m, these telescopes will revolutionize optical instrumentation and modern astronomy. The most prominent amongst them is the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), which will get a diameter of approximately 39 m. The ELT is currently built at Cerro Armazones at more than 3000 m altitude in the Atacama Desert in Chile by the European Southern Observatory (ESO). ESO is an astronomy organization, that builds and operates earthbound telescopes. Its main mission is to provide state of the art research facilities to astronomers and astrophysicists. In 2008 Austria joined ESO and since then Austrian astronomers are able to use ESO facilities.

Basically, there are two reasons why astronomers aim for telescopes with larger apertures. The first one is the acquisition of collecting more energy, which scales at the surface of the telescopes primary mirror. Going from an 8 to a 40 m telescope multiplies the effective area by a factor 25, which considerably increases the telescope sensitivity. The second reason is the increase in theoretical angular resolution. In general, the ability of a telescope to recognize details, i.e., the resolving power, is directly proportional to the aperture diameter. However, this is only true for telescopes working at their diffraction limit, i.e., all optical distortions, induced either by atmospheric turbulences or the telescope itself, have to be corrected by sophisticated methods. So called Adaptive Optics (AO) techniques have been developed in the last decades with the intention to cope with this problem. At the intersection of electronics, astronomy, optics, control theory, computer science and mathematics, AO is a technique to compensate for the quickly varying optical distortions in the earth's atmosphere in real-time. For current and future telescopes the utilization of AO is essential in order to obtain sharp images. The main components of AO systems are: wavefront sensors, guide stars, deformable mirrors and high performance computers. The wavefront sensors (WFSs) measure the wavefront aberrations of natural or laser guide stars. This measurement data is utilized by high performance computing architectures, which calculates the actuator commands to control the deformable mirrors (DMs). The DMs subsequently perform the wavefront correction. Due to the rapidly changing atmosphere, the computation has to be done in real-time, i.e., within a few milliseconds.

In classical AO systems, one natural guide star is used as a reference light source together with a single WFS and a single DM to perform the compensation. Such a system is commonly referred to as Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics (SCAO). However, a good correction is only achieved for directions in the vicinity of the guide star. Because the turbulence is time and space dependent, the image quality decreases very fast with the distance to this guide star. Since there are often not enough bright natural guide stars available close to scientific objects of interest, there is the need for more advanced systems. In future AO systems, such as Laser Tomography Adaptive Optics (LTAO), Multi Object Adaptive Optics (MOAO) and Multi Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO), mul-

multiple WFSs and DMs are employed. The data obtained from several WFSs are utilized to tomographically estimate the 3D atmospheric wavefront disturbances. Moreover, the usage of multiple DMs together with the 3D atmospheric reconstruction enables to correct for multiple directions and a wider field of view.

Developing AO control systems for future ELTs is an ambitious and critical task, since a considerably higher amount of data has to be processed in real-time. In order to achieve superb results, the combination of an efficient reconstruction algorithm implemented on a high performance computing architecture is inevitable. In this thesis we make a contribution to the further development of the state of the art technology.

1.2 Project origin

The work for this thesis was carried out in the framework of an European Industrial Doctorate (EID) program "Reduced Order Modelling and Optimization of Coupled Systems (ROMSOC)". This project brings together 15 international academic institutions, 11 industry partners and 11 early stage researchers working on individual projects. In particular, our project is dealing with real-time computing methods for astronomical AO systems and was carried out jointly at the Industrial Mathematics Institute of the Johannes Kepler University in Linz and the company Microgate located in Bolzano, Italy. The Engineering department of Microgate is mainly focused on large projects for astronomy and more specifically on AO systems for large telescopes. Over the past 20 years they have developed, together with other Italian partners, the large, contactless deformable mirror technology. The aim of our ROMSOC project was to develop atmospheric layer model reduction methods and to collaborate in the development and adaption of reconstruction algorithms. Finally, these algorithms have to be optimized and implemented in the real-time computing and DM hardware of Microgate.

1.3 State of the art

Mathematically, the atmospheric tomography problem as a limited angle tomography problem is severely ill-posed, i.e., there is an unstable relation between measurements and the solution; see [1, 2]. As a consequence, sophisticated regularization techniques are required. A common way to regularize this problem is the Bayesian framework, as it allows to incorporate statistical information about turbulence and noise. The random variables are typically assumed to be Gaussian, therefore the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate is an optimal point estimate for the solution. Detailed information about the systems can be found in [3–7].

So far, the standard solver for atmospheric tomography is the Matrix Vector Multiplication (MVM), i.e., the direct application of a (regularized) generalized inverse of the system operator. The computational costs of the MVM scale at $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$, where n is the dimension of the AO system. For computing the inverse the computational demand is even higher and scales at $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. The dimension n of the atmospheric tomography problem depends on the number of subapertures of the WFSs and on the number of degrees of freedom of the DMs, which are in general higher for bigger telescopes. Moreover, the solution has to be computed in real-time leading to a highly non-trivial task for ELT-sized problems. Even with a very high level of parallelization, the MVM and other direct solution methods are extremely demanding. Thus, research in the last years moved into the direction of iterative methods. Besides being fast, iterative methods benefit from on the fly system updates, whenever parameters in the atmosphere or at the telescope change. In recent years, several solvers were developed dealing with the atmospheric tomography problem, either directly or iteratively; see [8–22]. A very promising iterative method is the Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm (FEWHA) [23–25]. This algorithm utilizes a dual domain discretization approach in which the operators are transformed into a finite element or wavelet domain, leading to sparse representations of the underlying matrices. This concept allows an efficient matrix-free representation of all operators, leading to a significant reduction in floating point operations and memory resources. The dual domain discretization of the MAP estimate is then solved using a preconditioned conjugate gradient (PCG) method. FEWHA is not perfectly parallelizable and for ELT-sized test configurations the real-time requirements are hard to fulfill with an off the shelf hardware system; see [26].

1.4 Overview

In this thesis we focus on the optimization of FEWHA for certain real-time hardware architectures. This includes, on the one hand, the implementation of the algorithm on the hardware used for large AO systems together with a detailed performance study. On the other hand, we propose a new version of FEWHA that reduces the number of PCG iterations and in this regard the run-time in order to be able to fulfill the real-time requirements of ELTs.

A crucial indicator for the computational efficiency of iterative methods is the number of PCG iterations. Within this thesis we propose a novel method, called augmented FEWHA, which speeds up the convergence of the PCG method by reusing information from previous time steps. In particular the Krylov subspace generated when solving the previous system is reused in subsequent systems. The augmented CG method for solving consecutive linear systems was proposed in [27]. The concept is based on the idea of Saad in [28] on augmented Krylov subspace methods for solving linear systems with multiple right-hand sides. We want to emphasize that we are using an augmented Krylov subspace

method but no recycling. What is commonly known in the literature as Krylov subspace recycling, in addition to augmentation, changes the Krylov space [29]. In our method, the Krylov subspace is not changed. By recycling we understand reusing the search directions from previous time steps. In [30] a deflated version of the augmented CG is proposed, which further improves the convergence behavior. However, the overhead induced by their projection is large, and thus not feasible for the run-time requirements of ELTs. In [31] improved seed methods for linear equations with multiple right-hand sides have been studied. We considered this method for our application as well, but it performed worse than the augmented CG. The reason is that the augmented CG applies an additional projection in every CG iteration, which improves the approximation further.

Real-time implementations for ELT AO systems are also studied in [32–37]. Suitable architectures have been evaluated within the Greenflash project; see [38, 39]. Based on these investigations we mainly focus on Central Processing Units (CPUs) and Graphics Processing Units (GPUs) within this work. For Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) we state some ideas, however, the full implementation is part of the ongoing research. We utilize common parallel programming models that have been widely studied, e.g., in [40–42], to optimize the performance of our method for specific hardware architectures. We demonstrate the performance of our implementations on the challenging test configuration of MAORY, which is an adaptive optics module for the ELT operating in MCAO. The MAORY real-time computer is discussed in [34].

This thesis is split into two parts. In Chapters 2 – 5 we discuss the state of the art and currently available results. In Chapters 6 – 11 we present our research, which is based on or work in [26, 43, 44]. In the following, we briefly describe the content of the chapters:

- Chapter 2 is devoted to an introduction to astronomical AO. In particular, we present the mathematical models used to describe the image formation on telescopes and the atmospheric turbulence. Moreover, we give a brief overview on the components of an AO system and specify the AO configurations which are handled throughout this thesis.
- In Chapter 3 we give an overview on real-time hardware architectures used for the control of large AO systems. Furthermore, we describe common methods, such as pipelining and parallelization, that are used to efficiently implement control algorithms on these hardware architectures.
- In Chapter 4 we present some standard tools necessary to define the mathematical problem formulation behind AO. This involves the fields of deterministic and stochastic inverse problems as well as wavelet methods. Further, we present mathematical concepts that are used within this work to reduce the computational load of solving the atmospheric tomography problem for ELTs.
- Chapter 5 is devoted to the mathematical problem formulation behind AO for

ELTs, referred to as atmospheric tomography. In addition, we give an overview on state of the art solvers including their benefits and weaknesses.

- In Chapter 6 we present our novel augmented FEWHA, which utilizes an augmented Krylov subspace method to reduce the number of iterations for the PCG method.
- In Chapter 7 we state the test configuration used to evaluate the performance of our method in terms of quality and speed. This test setting is related to the ELT instrument MAORY. Moreover, we list test configurations for other AO systems in order to be able to study the quality of the algorithm in greater detail.
- In Chapter 8 we give a detailed quality analysis of augmented FEWHA for the test configuration defined in the previous chapter. Moreover, we analyze the performance for varying configurations to be able to see how the algorithm reacts on different parameters settings.
- Chapter 9 is devoted to a theoretical performance study of augmented FEWHA regarding floating point operations, memory usage and parallelization possibilities. In addition, we show results for FEWHA and the MVM to be able to compare these three solvers. Based on this study we decide on a possible real-time hardware architecture for the ELT.
- In Chapter 10 we list the run-time results for the classical FEWHA and its augmented version for different test configurations on the real-time system chosen in the previous chapter. Moreover, we study the bottlenecks in terms of computational speed.
- In Chapter 11 we state our conclusion and future work.

Chapter 2

Astronomical adaptive optics

The potential image quality of the new generation of ground based ELTs suffers heavily from atmospheric turbulences. These turbulences are triggered by the sun and wind, which lead to an irregular mixing of hot and cold air. Turbulent air motion leads to fluctuations of the refractive index, and thus the light initially travelling through the atmosphere as planar waves gets distorted. The aim of an AO system is to mechanically correct these distortions in real-time through deformable mirrors (DMs). To determine the optimal shape of the DM, wavefronts, that either stem from bright astronomical objects or artificially produced laser beams, are measured by wavefront sensors (WFSs). Based on these measured wavefronts a reconstruction algorithm computes the so called actuator commands, which are used to deform the mirror. In fact, the distorted wavefronts are first reflected onto the DM. This DM is shaped such that the wavefronts get corrected and the scientific instrument observes a high quality image; see Figure 2.1. In this chapter we provide an overview on the basics of image formation for telescopes, the concept of atmospheric turbulence and the main components of an AO system. Moreover, we describe the ELT currently built by ESO in more detail, since it acts as real world example for the simulations carried out in the framework of this thesis.

2.1 Extremely Large Telescopes

Since the first telescopes were built in the early 1600s our view into the universe got deeper and deeper. Currently there are several earthbound, extremely large telescopes under construction. Note, that the term extremely large here corresponds to the diameter of the telescope's primary mirror. Within this thesis we focus on ground based telescopes. The drawback of such telescopes compared to space telescopes is that the light passes through the atmosphere of the earth before arriving at the pupil, hence, it is affected

Figure 2.1. Basic functionality of an AO system.

by atmospheric turbulences. Space telescopes on the other hand are expensive and the transport and maintenance is very demanding. To cope with the distortions in the atmosphere earthbound telescopes utilize a technique called Adaptive Optics (AO) which enables a superb image quality of the newly developed ELTs. Deformable mirrors that correct the distorted wavefronts in real-time, make it possible to see farther and fainter objects than ever before. Such telescopes will considerably advance astrophysical knowledge by allowing the study of, e.g., the formation of first galaxies, super massive black holes, dark matter and dark energy.

The most prominent amongst the ELTs is the *Extremely Large Telescope* (ELT), which is currently built by the *European Southern Observatory* (ESO) and will become the world's largest earthbound telescope. The ESO is an astronomy organization with 17 member states, including Austria. The headquarter is located in Garching, near Munich in Germany. The ESO builds and operates earthbound telescopes like the Very Large Telescope (VLT), that is located in Paranal in Chile. Not far from there, the ELT is built on the Cerro Armazones at more than 3000 m altitude. The primary mirror of the ELT will have a diameter of approximately 38.5 m and a 11 m central obstruction. It is composed into 798 hexagonal mirror segments and about 5300 actuators that adapt the mirror shape in real-time. It will collect more than 15 times the light of any existing state of the art telescope. Figure 2.2 shows a graphical illustration on how large the 'biggest eye on the sky' in fact compares to other existing large telescopes and the pyramids in Egypt. Besides the large deformable primary mirror (M4), the ELT has four smaller mirrors.

Figure 2.2. The ELT in comparison with other existing, large telescopes and the pyramids in Egypt; [45].

The ELT will have four first-light instruments; see Figure 2.3: the *High Angular Resolution Monolithic Optical and Near-infrared Integral field spectograph* (HARMONI), the *Mid-infrared ELT Imager and Spectograph* (METIS), and the *Multi-AO Imaging Camera for Deep Observations* (MICADO) with the Adaptive Optics module *Multi conjugate Adaptive Optics RelaY* (MAORY). Having various instruments, the ELT makes observations in a wide range of wavelengths possible, from optical to mid-infrared. The numerical simulations within this thesis are carried out for a configuration similar to MAORY, which compensates for atmospheric turbulences over a 1 arc minute field of view in the near-infrared regime. The correction is achieved using up to three deformable mirrors that are driven by a system based on several natural and laser guide stars. For a detailed description of the ELT and its instruments we refer to [45]. For the test specification used throughout this thesis we refer to Chapter 7. Figure 2.4 reveals the excellent image quality of the ELT based on the example of the nebula NGC 3603, which is about 20000 light years away from the earth.

Figure 2.3. The ELT's first-light instruments; [45].

Figure 2.4. Illustration of different image quality of the nebula NGC 3603 provided by the NASA/ESA Hubble Space Telescope, ESO’s Very Large Telescope and the Extremely Large Telescope. The NGC 3606 is a star-forming region in the Carina spiral arm of the Milky Way, which is about 20000 light years away from earth; [45].

2.2 Image formation on telescopes

The principles described in this section follow mainly the work in [46]. The telescope aperture, which commonly has a circular shape, can be described by a characteristic function \mathcal{X}_Ω , i.e., it is one within the pupil and zero outside. We assume an object to be a cloud of point sources of light. The real image, including optical errors, is defined by the energy distribution over the image plane and is expressed by the so called *point spread function* (PSF). The $PSF : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is connected the *optical transfer function* (OTF) via the Fourier transform

$$PSF(\mathbf{x}) = |\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{X}_\Omega \exp(i\phi))(\mathbf{x})|^2,$$

where

$$OTF(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{X}_\Omega \exp(i\phi(\mathbf{x})).$$

The image observed on the telescope I_R is related to the astronomical object of interest I_G by a convolution with the PSF of the telescope; see Figure 2.5; i.e.,

$$I_R(x, y) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} PSF(x - \xi, y - \eta) \cdot I_G(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta.$$

This is a convolution operation, which we denote by

$$I_R = PSF * I_G.$$

The incoming wave ϕ in radians is related to the wavefront aberration φ in optical path distance by

$$\phi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \varphi, \quad (2.1)$$

for a certain wavelength λ . Note that within this thesis we omit the constant in Equation (2.1) and use ϕ for the incoming wave as well as for the wavefront aberration, because we are only interested in the shape of the incoming wavefront aberrations.

If we neglect atmospheric perturbations and assume $\phi = 0$, we obtain the so called diffraction limited PSF; see [47]. Assuming a circular telescope pupil with diameter D we get

$$PSF(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\pi D^2}{4\lambda^2} \left(\frac{2J_1(\pi D |\mathbf{x}| / \lambda)}{\pi D |\mathbf{x}| / \lambda} \right)^2.$$

Here $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^2$, λ is the wavelength and J_1 denotes the Bessel function of the first kind. This Bessel function can be represented by a series expansion around zero via

$$J_1(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n! \Gamma(n+2)} \left(\frac{x}{2} \right)^{(2n+1)},$$

where $\Gamma(n) = (n-1)!$ denotes the Gamma function for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Figure 2.5. The PSF of the telescope relates the observed image I_R with the astronomical object of interest I_G ; [48].

The PSF depends on the diameter D of the telescope. The larger the diameter of the telescope the better its PSF approximates a delta distribution. Figure 2.6 illustrates a typical shape of a PSF. For ground based telescopes the PSF is affected by atmospheric turbulences. This results in oscillations that propagate outwards as well as a lower maximum intensity. The goal in AO is to get as close as possible to the diffraction limited PSF, because this results in a sharp image. Various PSF reconstruction algorithms for ELTs exist; see [49–51].

2.3 Atmospheric turbulence

Atmospheric turbulences are caused by the irregular mixing of cold and hot air, triggered by the sun and wind. These irregularities make the refractive index of the air inhomogeneous, resulting in a distorted wavefront arriving at the telescope pupil. The effects of turbulence are non predictable, thus, they are typically modeled by a random

Figure 2.6. Typical diffraction limited PSF; [48].

process. The refraction of the atmosphere in the random setting is given by the mean refraction combined with some additive noise. *Kolmogorov* developed the fundamental model for describing turbulence in the atmosphere.

2.3.1 Kolmogorov turbulence model

According to Kolmogorov [52] the behavior of the atmosphere is modeled via an isotropic, stationary random process. The representation of this random process is based on a structure function, which describes the expected difference of values at two points, and the covariance function, which measures the spatial covariance. As we are dealing with a stationary process, both functions only depend on the separation Δx of two points and not on a specific point x .

The structure function of a stationary process f is given by

$$D_f(\Delta x) := \mathbb{E}((f(x + \Delta x) - f(x))^2),$$

and the covariance is defined via

$$C_f(\Delta x) := \mathbb{E}((f(x) - \mathbb{E}(f))(f(x + \Delta x) - \mathbb{E}(f))).$$

The *power spectral density* (PSD) characterizes the behavior of the covariance function in the Fourier domain and is defined by

$$\Phi_f(\Delta x) := \mathbb{E}((f(x) - \mathbb{E}(f))(f(x + \Delta x) - \mathbb{E}(f))).$$

Kolmogorov's theory is limited by the two quantities l_0 and L_0 called inner and outer scale. The inner scale represents the size of the smallest eddy in the turbulence, whereas

the outer scale corresponds to the largest size. Within this range, Kolmogorov stated that the structure function of the refractive index of the atmosphere at a certain height h is given by

$$D_f(\Delta x) := c_n^2(h)|\Delta x|^{2/3} \quad \text{for } l_0 < |\Delta x| < L_0,$$

where $c_n^2(h)$ denotes the refractive index structure function. This quantity measures the turbulence strength at a certain altitude h . It is usually measured empirically and depends on weather conditions. The PSD of the refractive index n is then given by

$$\Phi_n(\kappa) := 0.033C_n^2(h)|\kappa|^{-11/3} \quad \text{for } 2\pi L_0^{-1} < |\kappa| < 2\pi l_0^{-1},$$

where $\kappa = (\kappa_1, \kappa_2, \kappa_3)$ is the spatial frequency and $|\kappa|$ denotes the Euclidean norm. For a very small $|\kappa| \rightarrow 0$, i.e., for turbulent eddies larger than the outer scale, Kolmogorov's model shows problems due to a singularity. To overcome this unwanted effect, the *von Karman model* was introduced.

2.3.2 Von Karman turbulence model

The von Karman model [53] modifies the Kolmogorov model in order to overcome the problem with the singularity at $\kappa = 0$. This leads to the following, slightly modified definition of the power spectral density

$$\Phi_f(\kappa) = \frac{0.033C_n^2(h)}{(|\kappa| + \kappa_0^2)^{11/6}} \exp\left(-\frac{|\kappa|^2}{\kappa_m^2}\right),$$

with $\kappa_0 = 2\pi L_0^{-1}$ and $\kappa_m = 5.92l_0^{-1}$. For $|\kappa| \rightarrow 0$ the PSD in the von Karman turbulence model has a finite value.

2.3.3 Turbulence layers

Most of the atmospheric turbulences are concentrated in separate layers, which travel at a certain velocity parallel to the surface of the earth; see [54]. These turbulent patterns change slower than the wind speed, thus, for a short time frame constant so called c_n^2 profiles can be assumed; see [55]. During the day, the turbulences are typically stronger near the earth's surface, whereas during the night perturbations are stronger at higher altitudes; see [56]. The atmosphere can be modeled by L statistically independent turbulent layers, which are infinitely thin; see [57]. The optical strength of the atmospheric turbulence at a certain layer $l = 1, \dots, L$ at height h_l is given by $c_n^2(h_l)$. In fact, a small number of layers is sufficient, as shown, e.g., in [48, 58, 59]. Within our numerical simulations we consider between 3 and 9 layers, derived by ESO from measurements at their site in the Atacama desert in Chile. These seeing conditions are

derived from c_n^2 profiles, wind speeds and layer altitudes. They are described by the isoplanatic angle θ_0 and the Fried parameter r_0 . For the detailed parameters we refer to Chapter 7.

The *Fried parameter* r_0 assesses the seeing conditions with respect to a certain wavelength λ . Typically, the parameter is defined in the visible, i.e., at 500 nanometers by

$$r_0 = 0.185 \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{\int_0^\infty c_n^2(h) dh} \right)^{3/5};$$

see [60]. The atmospheric seeing β is the ratio between the wavelength and the Fried parameter:

$$\beta = \frac{\lambda}{r_0}.$$

The Fried parameter lies within 10 and 20 centimetres for the visible region of the spectrum. Larger values correspond to good seeing conditions, and thus to weak turbulence, whereas smaller values refer to bad seeing and strong perturbations.

Within AO we use measurements from guide stars as reference sources to correct the distorted wavefronts of other nearby objects of interest. In general, these measurements are only valid for objects in the same direction as the guide star. If the angle between the reference source and the object of interest increases, the error in the wavefront becomes uncorrelated. We denote by θ_0 the angle at which two speckle images start to look different; see [56]. Angular anisoplanatism is the effect when the angle between two objects is bigger than θ_0 . For an observation at a guide star direction θ , the variance of phase is given by

$$\mathbb{E}(\sigma_\phi^2) = \left(\frac{\theta}{\theta_0} \right).$$

Assuming a single layer atmosphere at altitude h , the isoplanatic angle is given by the relation between the Fried parameter and the layer height by

$$\theta_0 = 0.31 \frac{r_0}{h}.$$

For more details we refer to [55, 56, 61].

2.4 AO components

AO [60, 62, 63] is a technique to compensate the rapidly changing optical distortions in the atmosphere, that heavily degrade the image quality of earthbound telescopes. The correction process is commonly split into two parts. First, the deformations of

wavefronts emitted by natural or laser guide stars in the vicinity of the object of interest are measured via WFSs. This information is then used by a reconstruction algorithm to calculate the actuator commands that deform the mirror. Finally, the light from guide stars as well as the observed object is reflected onto the deformable mirror and the distortions get removed. Figure 2.7 illustrates the basic design of an AO system running in closed loop. The incoming wavefront which got distorted when passing through the turbulent atmosphere, reaches the DM and gets corrected. A so called beam splitter (BS) splits the light into two parts. One part is propagated to the scientific camera and the other to the WFS. These already corrected sensor measurements are used to compute the actual mirror commands for the next incoming wavefront.

Figure 2.7. Basic design of an AO system.

The main components of an AO system are guide stars, wavefront sensors and deformable mirrors. In the following subsections we describe these components in greater detail.

2.4.1 Guide stars

Guide stars (GS) are bright objects, which serve as point light sources. We differentiate between *natural guide stars* (NGS), i.e., real astronomical objects, and *laser guide stars* (LGS) that are artificially generated by a laser beam.

Natural Guide Star

An NGS is a bright star that serves as a reference point for the WFS to detect atmospheric distortions. The star is modeled as a point source at an infinite height. Assuming a layered atmospheric model, the wavefront aberrations in the direction θ of an NGS are given by

$$\varphi_\theta(x) = (P_\theta^{NGS}\phi)(x) := \sum_{\ell=1}^L \phi_\ell(x + \theta h_\ell), \quad (2.2)$$

where ϕ_ℓ is the turbulent layer at altitude h_ℓ for $\ell = 1, \dots, L$. We call P_θ^{NGS} the geometric propagation operator in the direction of the NGS.

We assume that the photon noise from the NGS, that affects the WFS measurements, is modeled by a Gaussian random variable with zero mean and covariance matrix C_η . The noise is identically distributed in each *subaperture* and the x - and y -measurements are uncorrelated. Hence, the covariance matrix can be defined by

$$C_\eta = \sigma^2 I, \quad (2.3)$$

where σ^2 is the noise variance of a single measurement. It is given by

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{n_{photons}}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $n_{photons}$ is the number of photons per subaperture.

Laser Guide Star

For an LGS the model is more complex. An LGS is generated by a powerful laser beam. In this thesis we consider so called sodium LGSs. Besides this kind of LGSs so called rayleigh LGSs are frequently used; see [62] for details. For sodium LGS the laser beam scatters in the sodium layer, at which the light is then backscattered and sensed by the WFS. These procedure induces some important effects that have to be taken into account when modelling an LGS: the *cone effect*, *spot elongation* and *tip-tilt indetermination*.

In contrast to the infinite height assumed for an NGS, an LGS is considered to be at a finite height H . Due to the finite altitude, the light detected by the telescope passes through a cone-like volume of the atmosphere; see Figure 2.8. This behavior is referred to as the cone effect.

As for NGS we assume a layered model of the atmosphere. The incoming wavefront aberrations in the direction θ of an LGS are given by

$$\varphi_\theta(x) = (P_\theta^{LGS}\phi)(x) := \sum_{\ell=1}^L \phi_\ell\left(\left(1 - \frac{h_\ell}{H}\right)x + \theta h_\ell\right), \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.8. Cone effect for LGS; [48]. Due to the finite height of the LGS, the light passes through a cone volume.

where P_{θ}^{LGS} is called the geometric propagation operator in the direction of the LGS.

As the *sodium layer* has a certain layer of thickness, the scattering of the laser beam happens in a vertical stripe instead of in a single point. Thus, the sodium layer thickness must be considered when modeling the photon noise. The charge-coupled device (CCD) detector of the WFS observes this stripe as an elongated spot. The effect is commonly known as spot elongation and is illustrated in Figure 2.9.

Figure 2.9. Spot elongation for LGS; [48].

The vertical density profile of the laser beam scatter is modeled by a Gaussian random variable with mean H and the *full width at half maximum* (FWHM) of the sodium

density profile in meters, which is defined by

$$FWHM = 2\sqrt{2\ln(2)}\sigma.$$

Further, we define the laser launch positions as (x_1^{LL}, x_2^{LL}) and the midpoint of a subaperture Ω_{ij} by (\bar{x}_i, \bar{x}_j) with

$$\bar{x}_i = \frac{x_i + x_{i+1}}{2},$$

for $0 \leq i < n_s$ where the x_i are given by Equation (2.8).

The elongation vector in a subaperture Ω_{ij} is given by

$$\beta_{ij} = (\beta_{ij,1}, \beta_{ij,2}) = \frac{FWHM}{H^2} \left((\bar{x}_i, \bar{x}_j) - (x_1^{LL}, x_2^{LL}) \right).$$

The spot elongated noise covariance matrix in a subaperture is given by

$$C_{ij} = \sigma^2 \left(I + \frac{\alpha_\eta^2}{f^2} \begin{pmatrix} \beta_{ij,1}^2 & \beta_{ij,1}\beta_{ij,2} \\ \beta_{ij,1}\beta_{ij,2} & \beta_{ij,2}^2 \end{pmatrix} \right),$$

where I denotes the identity matrix, σ is defined as in (2.4), f is the FWHM of the non-elongated spot. To cope with noise sources that are not included into the model above, e.g., read out noise, we introduce the fine-tuning parameter α_η . If $\alpha_\eta = 0$ the model coincide with the NGS model, whereas for $\alpha_\eta = 1$ we have the full LGS model.

Summarized, the noise model for a WFS associated to an LGS is given by a Gaussian random variable with zero mean and covariance matrix

$$C_\eta = \text{diag}(C_{ij}), \quad (2.6)$$

with $0 \leq i, j < n_s$ for an active subaperture Ω_{ij} .

In every AO system at least one NGS has to be used in order to overcome the problem of tip-tilt indetermination. The laser beam passes through the atmosphere twice, once when traveling up to the sodium layer and once when being scattered from this sodium layer. Hence, the real position of the LGS is unknown as tip or tilt modes cannot be determined. This leads to an uncertainty in the position of the spots of the Shack Hartman sensor and, subsequently, to untrustworthy low-order aberrations of the LGS. Figure 2.10 illustrates this behavior.

Although the low-order information is unreliable, the relative motion of the spots within the subapertures is kept, and thus also the high-order aberrations. Note that from a measurements point of view, the tip-tilt uncertainty is nothing else than incorrect average slopes over the pupil of the telescope. To achieve a good correction of the incoming wavefronts it is essential to determine the tip-tilt aberrations. Thus, the LGS

Figure 2.10. Tip-tilt indetermination for an LGS; [48].

are coupled with at least one NGS that senses the low-order tip-tilt modes. In this case, a so called low-order *tip-tilt sensor* (TTS) is used that has typically a much smaller size of, e.g., 2×2 or 1×1 subapertures. These two sensors can either be assigned to two different mirrors, one for high-order modes and one for tip-tilt correction, or the two problems can be combined. Throughout this thesis we use the second approach, i.e., the NGS and the LGS problem are coupled.

2.4.2 Deformable mirrors

A *deformable mirror* (DM) typically consists of a thin surface which reflects the light, and a set of actuators that deform the mirror. Here, we assume a simple model of a bilinear DM, i.e., the shape is described using a piecewise continuous bilinear function, which we denote by a .

We define the domain on which the DM operates by

$$\Omega := [-D/2, D/2]^2, \quad (2.7)$$

where D is the telescope diameter. Further, we denote by n_a^2 the number of *actuators* or nodal points of the piecewise bilinear function. We assume that these points are arranged in a rectangular grid with a spacing of $d := D/(n_a - 1)$. Since the telescope has a circular shape, not all of these actuators are active, i.e., they have no effect on the correction of the wavefront.

The actuator positions are given by (x_i, x_j) for $0 \leq i, j \leq n_a$, where

$$x_i := -D/2 + i \cdot d.$$

The actuator grid is then given by the set of points

$$(x_i, x_j) : 0 \leq i, j < n_a.$$

Moreover, we define the square sub-domains of Ω by

$$\Omega_{ij} := [x_i, x_{i+1}] \times [x_j, x_{j+1}].$$

To each subdomain a bilinear function defined on $[0, 1]^2$ is associated by

$$b_{ij}(x, y) = a_{ij}(1 - x - y + xy) + a_{i,j+1}(x - xy) + a_{i+1,j}(y - xy) + a_{i+1,j+1}xy,$$

where the values a_{ij} are called actuator commands.

Figure 2.11 shows different types of DMs. The simplest mirror, which is considered as a low risk concept, is called segmented DM. This mirror has only up to three degrees of freedom (two axes for tilt and piston), but a wide dynamic range and a good frequency response. Due to the gaps between the segments diffraction effects arise. Moreover, such a DM has a higher fitting error compared to other types. The face-sheet DM is stable over time and changes in temperature due to its continuous faceplate. The drawback of this DM type is the limited stroke. This stroke limitation is induced by the stress in the faceplate, which arises due to actuator motion. The deformable mirror of the ELT called M4 consists of a segmented and thin shell. The mirror is driven at 500 Hertz by about 5300 actuators. For the numerical simulations carried out in the framework of this thesis we assume the Fried geometry with equidistant actuator spacing for the DMs, as described in [64].

In general, one distinguishes between the shape of the DM and the mirror commands, which deform the DM. Throughout this thesis we use both wordings to denote the mirror commands a .

2.4.3 Wavefront sensors

A *wavefront sensor* (WFS) measures indirectly the distortions of the wavefronts using the light from an NGS or an LGS. Various WFSs are used within AO. In the following, we describe the *Shack-Hartmann* (SH) WFS and the *pyramid* WFS in more detail. For the numerical simulations carried in this thesis we restrict ourselves to the SH WFS model.

Figure 2.11. Different types of DMs; [65].

Shack-Hartmann WFS

A Shack-Hartmann (SH) WFS; see [63, 66, 67]; consists of a quadratic array of small lenslets and a CCD photon detector lying behind this array. The vertical and horizontal shifts of the focal points determine the average slope of the wavefront over the area of the lens, known as subaperture. Similar as for the actuators we introduce the subaperture grid. Let

$$\Omega := [-D/2, D/2]^2,$$

be the domain on which the wavefront is defined. Here D denotes again the diameter of the telescope. Further, we denote by n_s^2 the number of subapertures. As for the DM, not all subapertures need to be active. Because the telescope pupil has a circular shape, not all subapertures are illuminated. The subaperture grid consists of a set of equidistantly spaced points and is given by

$$(x_i, x_j) : 0 \leq i, j \leq n_s, \text{ where } x_i := -D/2 + i \cdot d. \quad (2.8)$$

A subaperture is then defined as an open square sub-domain of Ω by

$$\Omega_{ij} := (x_i, x_{i+1}) \times (x_j, x_{j+1}).$$

Within a subaperture Ω_{ij} the SH measurements are modelled as the average slopes of the wavefront aberration φ and given by

$$s_{ij}^x = \frac{1}{d^2} \int_{\Omega_{ij}} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}(x, y) d(x, y), \quad (2.9)$$

$$s_{ij}^y = \frac{1}{d^2} \int_{\Omega_{ij}} \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y}(x, y) d(x, y), \quad (2.10)$$

Figure 2.12. SH WFS with 7×7 subapertures. An active subaperture Ω_{ij} is indicated by continuous borders, whereas a non-active subaperture is surrounded by dashed lines; [23].

where $s := (s^x, s^y)$ are the average slopes in x and y -direction, respectively, and d^2 is the area of the subaperture Ω_{ij} . We assume that the incoming wavefront aberration φ is approximated by a continuous piecewise bilinear function φ_{ij} at points $(x_i, x_j) : 0 \leq i, j \leq n_s$. Then Equation (2.9) reduces to

$$s_{ij}^x = \frac{(\varphi_{i,j+1} - \varphi_{i,j}) + (\varphi_{i+1,j+1} - \varphi_{i+1,j})}{2}, \quad (2.11)$$

$$s_{ij}^y = \frac{(\varphi_{i+1,j} - \varphi_{i,j}) + (\varphi_{i+1,j+1} - \varphi_{i,j+1})}{2}; \quad (2.12)$$

see [68]. In this work we denote the SH measurement vector by $s = (s^x, s^y)$. The vectors s^x and s^y are a concatenation of values s_{ij}^x and s_{ij}^y for (i, j) a set of indices that belongs to an active subaperture Ω_{ij} . The subapertures where no measurements are available are excluded from s . To the above defined relation between measurements s and wavefront aberrations φ we associate a SH WFS operator, which we denote by $\Gamma = (\Gamma_x, \Gamma_y)$. Here, Γ_x and Γ_y determine the slopes in x - and y -direction, respectively,

$$s = \begin{pmatrix} s^x \\ s^y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma_x \varphi \\ \Gamma_y \varphi \end{pmatrix} = \Gamma \varphi. \quad (2.13)$$

The CCD detector senses photons over a certain time frame. Typically, the SH WFS suffers from read-out noise and photon noise. The read-out noise is due to errors in reading photons by the CCD detector planes. This kind of noise is measured in electrons per pixel. The photon noise is related to the number of photons that are sensed by the CCD in a subaperture during a certain time frame. If we are dealing with a very faint light beacon, too few photons are detected by the sensor. This leads to an inaccurate position of the focal point in the subaperture. The photon noise is modelled by a poisson process. For a large number of photons, the noise can be approximated by a Gaussian random variable.

Pyramid WFS

The main component of the pyramid WFS is a four-sided glass pyramidal prism in the focal plane of the telescope; see, e.g., [69]. This prism splits the incoming light into four beams. The relay lens, located behind the prism, re-images the beams leading to four different images I_1, I_2, I_3 and I_4 on the CCD camera; see Figure 2.13. Similar to SH WFSs, pyramid WFS measurements are given on a grid of subapertures; see Equation 2.7. The sensor measurements in x- and y-direction are given by

$$S_x(x, y) = \frac{(I_1(x, y) + I_2(x, y)) - (I_3(x, y) + I_4(x, y))}{I_0}, \quad (2.14)$$

$$S_y(x, y) = \frac{(I_1(x, y) + I_4(x, y)) - (I_2(x, y) + I_3(x, y))}{I_0}, \quad (2.15)$$

where I_0 denotes the average intensity; see [70].

Figure 2.13. Pyramid WFS; [69].

It might happen that the incoming beam is not exactly focused on the spot of the pyramidal prism. Hence, light does not fall on every side of the pyramid. To overcome this behavior, the spot of the pyramid can be modulated. The modulation of the incoming beam allows a linearisation of the sensor and to increase its dynamic range; see [70–72]. Several possibilities exist to dynamically modulate the beam; see, e.g., [69, 73]. The advantage of the pyramid WFS over the SH WFS is the increased sensitivity which enables the usage of fainter stars and higher sky coverage; see [74]. For recent research on the pyramid WFS, especially on new mathematical models and accurate wavefront reconstruction, we refer to [75–79].

The four-sided pyramidal prism of the sensor can be approximated via 2 orthogonally placed two-sided roof prisms. Each of the roofs creates two different images on the

detector. The sensor measurements S_x and S_y are obtained by subtracting the two intensity patterns. Due to the physical decoupling of the prisms, the measurements contain information only in x - or y -direction, respectively.

2.5 AO systems

Depending on the specific aim of the system, i.e., observing one or several objects of interest or correcting for a wide field of view, the number of NGS and LGS involved in the correction change. This is what is referred to as different operating modes. Figure 2.14 shows the 4 operating modes considered throughout thesis. In the following subsections we describe these AO systems in more detail.

Figure 2.14. The different AO operating modes; [48]. The red or green stars indicate natural or laser guide stars. The blue parts refer to the corrected areas and the violet spirals are the objects of interest.

2.5.1 Single Conjugate AO

If the object of interest, e.g., a star or a galaxy, is located near a bright NGS, the classical AO system *Single Conjugate AO* (SCAO) is used. In a SCAO system the wavefront is reconstructed using one WFS that measures the deformations, and one DM, where the shape is chosen according to the reconstruction algorithm; see Figure 2.15(a). The drawback of a SCAO system is, that the further away the object of interest is from the NGS, the worse the correction of the wavefront becomes. In the general case, an NGS near the object of interest is not available.

2.5.2 Laser Tomography AO

If no NGS is available in the vicinity of the object of interest, the usage of a SCAO system is not possible. The idea is to use a laser beam to generate one or more LGSs

to obtain a good correction. The LGSs are combined with at least one NGS to correct for the low-order modes; see Section 2.4.1; which are not available using LGS only. In general, a combination of several LGS and NGS is possible.

Figure 2.15. Figure(a) illustrates a SCAO system using one NGS to correct for one direction of interest is shown. Figure(b) shows an LTAO system with two guide stars that corrects for the direction of one object of interest is illustrated; [48].

Within the framework of a *Laser Tomography AO* (LTAO) a number of G_{LGS} and G_{NGS} are used in combination with a single mirror to reconstruct the wavefront. Figure 2.15(b) illustrates an LTAO system. The correction is performed through two steps. The first step is called atmospheric tomography, where the turbulent layers are reconstructed from sensor measurements. In the second step, the shape of the DM is chosen according to the projection of the wavefront through the reconstructed layers in the direction of interest. For an SCAO system, the reconstructed layer is located at the altitude of the DM, hence, the grid points of the reconstructed layer are aligned with the mirror nodal values and nothing has to be done. For an LTAO system, the mirror is optimized towards a certain direction of interest θ_1 . Thus, the DM has to be fitted to the reconstructed layers. This fitting step is defined by a projection through the reconstructed layers towards θ_1

$$a_1 = [P_{\theta_1,1}^{NGS} \dots P_{\theta_1,L}^{NGS}] \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \vdots \\ \phi_L \end{pmatrix},$$

where $P_{\theta_1,\ell}^{NGS}$ is a bilinear interpolation onto layer $\ell = 1, \dots, L$ towards the direction θ_1 .

2.5.3 Multi Object AO

In contrast to LTAO, *Multi Object AO* (MOAO) corrects for multiple directions of interest simultaneously by using several mirrors; see Figure 2.16(a). Each mirror corrects for a specific direction. As in the LTAO case, a combination of NGS and LGS is used for reconstructing the layers. Since we are optimizing towards M directions of interest $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_M$, instead of only one, this leads to a slightly different mirror fitting step

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_M \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P_{\theta_1,1}^{NGS} & \dots & P_{\theta_1,L}^{NGS} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ P_{\theta_M,1}^{NGS} & \dots & P_{\theta_M,L}^{NGS} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \vdots \\ \phi_L \end{pmatrix}.$$

2.5.4 Multi Conjugate AO

Like an MOAO system, a *Multi Conjugate AO* (MCAO) system corrects for multiple directions, however, with the aim to achieve a uniformly good correction over the whole FoV and not into specific directions. For a graphical illustration see Figure 2.16(b). For that purpose, several DMs are used conjugated to different heights in the atmosphere. As for LTAO and MOAO systems, the atmospheric tomography problem is solved in a first step. In the second step, the shapes of the M mirrors are fitted to the reconstructed layers in order to optimize the quality in a large FoV. The standard approach for mirror fitting; see e.g. [63]; is to minimize the following functional

$$\int_{FoV} \int_{\Omega_M} \left\| (P_{\phi}^{NGS} \phi)(x) - (\bar{P}_{\phi}^{NGS} a)(x) \right\|^2 dx d\phi,$$

where $\phi = (\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L)$ is the vector of layers and $a = (a_1, \dots, a_M)$ is the vector of mirror shapes. For details we refer to [80]. By Ω_M we denote the telescope pupil and FoV is a set of directions in the FoV. The operators P_{ϕ}^{NGS} and \bar{P}_{ϕ}^{NGS} are projections through layers and DMs, respectively.

For more details on the fitting step for different AO systems we refer to [81].

2.6 AO delay and control

There is a certain delay between the time when the measurements are obtained from the WFSs and the time when the wavefronts get corrected by the DMs. Because the atmosphere changes rapidly, the AO system updates the DM shapes based on the current measurements, collected by the WFSs, and the previous DM shapes; see [82]. We denote

Figure 2.16. Figure(a) illustrates an MOAO system correcting for two objects of interests using two DMs is shown. Figure (b) shows an MCAO system, that achieves a good correction in a wide FoV, using two DMs conjugated to two different altitudes; [48].

the previous, the current and the next time step of the loop by the superscript indices $(i-1)$, (i) and $(i+1)$. The superscript indices $(i-1, i)$ and $(i, i+1)$ denote the measurements between the respective time steps. In this thesis we consider a *two-step delay*; see, e.g., [23]. The new mirror shapes $a^{(i+1)}$ are determined from the reconstruction that uses the measurements $s^{(i-1, i)}$ and from the previous mirror shapes $a^{(i)}$. Because of the delay, the measurements $s^{(i, i+1)}$ are not available at time step $(i+1)$ for the reconstruction. See Figure 2.17 for a graphical representation.

Figure 2.17. Two-step delay of an AO system. WFS measurements are obtained between $(i-1, i)$ and the correction is applied in the interval $(i, i+1)$. DM shapes are adapted in $(i-1, i)$ and $(i+1)$. The measurements $s^{(i, i+1)}$ are not available at step $(i+1)$ (indicated in gray).

We denote the average wavefront aberrations in the interval $(i-1, i)$ by $\varphi^{(i-1, i)}$ and the slope measurements obtained in this interval by $s^{(i-1, i)}$. In the time frame $(i, i+1)$ the numerical reconstruction algorithms determine the mirror shapes based on $s^{(i-1, i)}$ and in time step $(i+1)$ the DM is updated. There are two ways on how to align the DM and the corresponding WFS in the optical path of an AO system. If the AO system is configured such that the WFS is installed before the DM, the measurements are obtained directly from the wavefronts by

$$s^{(i-1, i)} = \Gamma \varphi^{(i-1, i)} + \eta,$$

where Γ is the SH operator and η is the measurement noise. This control scheme is called *open loop*. In Figure 2.7 a *closed loop* control is shown, i.e., the DM is installed

before the WFS in the optical path, thus, the wavefronts are already corrected before obtained from the WFS. The measurements $s^{(i-1,i)}$ correspond to the residuals of the corrected wavefronts minus the DM correction

$$s^{(i-1,i)} = \Gamma(\varphi^{(i-1,i)} - a^{(i-1)}) + \eta. \quad (2.16)$$

2.7 AO measures

In the following sections we briefly describe some important AO quantities often referred to within this thesis. Moreover, we define a quantity for measuring the quality of the reconstruction algorithms presented in this thesis, which is frequently used in the community of AO.

2.7.1 Important quantities

Wavelength

For the simulations contained in this thesis we consider observations in the near infrared, i.e., in the K-band, which denotes a *wavelength* λ between $2.0 \mu m$ and $2.4 \mu m$. The astronomical band for sensing and evaluating can be different. Note that a different wavelength λ can change the performance of an AO system significantly.

Field of View

The *field of view* (FoV) is commonly indicated by the diameter of a circle (in arcmin or arcsec). One distinguishes between the corrected FoV, which is determined by the GS asterism, and the scientific FoV. Throughout this thesis we refer by FoV to the corrected FoV.

Photon flux

To measure the intensity of light that reaches the telescope pupil the number of photons $n_{photons}$ for one subaperture of a WFS per frame is used. We differentiate between high and low *photon flux*. In general, up to 500 photons is called low photon flux, whereas magnitudes of 10000 are referred to as high photon flux. However, the threshold depends heavily on the signal-to-noise-ratio.

Sensor noise

The most dominant error sources within AO are the *photon noise* and the *read-out noise*. The photon noise, which is described by the signal-to-noise-ratio, denotes the noise in the sensor output. It depends on the sensor size, the number of pixels, the photon flux and the number of subapertures. The read-out noise is triggered by unpredictable phenomena and latency within the read-out process of the CCD detector. We combine all error sources into one probabilistic quantity η . Hence, the model for obtaining the measurements from the WFS becomes

$$s = W\varphi + \eta.$$

Within the framework of this thesis we consider W to be the SH operator Γ . The usage of regularization methods helps in keeping the error propagation low.

Frame rate

The time in which the CCD detector is sensing the photons is called *frame rate* and given in Hertz. In our simulations the frame rate lies at about 500 Hertz, i.e., 2 ms. The tomographic reconstruction has to be performed in approximately half the time.

2.7.2 Quality evaluation: Strehl ratio

The *Strehl ratio* is a frequently used quality evaluation criterion within AO. The *short exposure* (SE) Strehl is defined as the ratio between the maximum of the real energy distribution of incoming light in the image plane $I(x, y)$ over the hypothetical distribution $I_D(x, y)$, which stems from the assumption of diffraction-limited imaging,

$$S := \frac{\max_{(x,y)} I(x, y)}{\max_{(x,y)} I_D(x, y)} \in [0, 1].$$

The higher the Strehl ratio the better the quality of the AO system. The maximum of 1 is reached only in the diffraction-limited case. A tip-tilt mode, which leads to a horizontal shift of $I(x, y)$, does not influence S . In order to detect a tip-tilt mode, the *long exposure* (LE) Strehl ratio is used. The LE Strehl represents the quality of the image from the start of the loop until a certain time step. The short and long exposure Strehl ratios are commonly indicated in %. For more details about the Strehl ratio we refer to [62].

Chapter 3

Real-time systems

Within a real-time computing system the correctness of a certain calculation depends not only on the value of the result, but also at which time frame it is available. A real-time system must respond in a predictable amount of time. Moreover, such systems need sufficient computational power to meet the timing and processing requirements of the specific real-time application, such as the control of an AO system. The main parts of this chapter are based on the book in [83].

A real-time system can be classified into *hard real-time* (HRT) and *soft real-time* (SRT) systems. HRT systems have a strict predefined deadline where the results must be available to guarantee that everything works properly. For SRT systems there is a specified level of urgency and the system executes the task with highest priority. Within the framework of AO, HRT is related to the computation of the DM commands from sensor measurements, which is typically at 500–1000 Hz. SRT is related to the pre-computation of matrices whenever certain parameters at the telescope or in the atmosphere change. For our test configuration the SRT is at 6 minutes. In general, the time frame of HRT is much smaller than that of SRT.

3.1 Hardware architecture of AO systems

In general, three basic hardware technologies are used for the real-time control of large telescopes: *Central Processing Units* (CPUs), *Graphics Processing Units* (GPUs), and *Field Programmable Gate Arrays* (FPGAs). In the following, we provide an overview on all of them. In Chapter 9 we decide which hardware is suitable for which algorithm. Our decision relies on a theoretical performance analysis of the wavefront reconstruction algorithms for ELT-sized test configurations. We follow here the work in [40] for CPUs,

[41] for GPUs and [84] for the FPGA technology.

3.1.1 Central processing units

The most widespread processing units, and thus the most straightforward way to implement a real-time control architecture, are Central Processing Units (CPUs). Internally, a CPU consists of several billion transistors. The number of transistors can serve as a rough estimate for the computational performance. Another performance factor is the clock frequency, which determines the time a processor needs for one cycle, and hence the time to execute a single instruction. Traditionally, a CPU carries out instructions on the data in a sequential way. However, nowadays CPUs consist of several independent processor cores. All cores of a multicore processor can execute tasks simultaneously, which leads to parallel execution. In order to coordinate the control flow of the cores, parallel programming techniques are required. All cores of a processor can access the same global memory and share caches that store frequently used data with a very fast data access compared to global memory. Caches are arranged in different levels, starting from small, fast and expensive L1 cache up to slower but larger L2, L3 cache and global memory. Access of data in L1 cache takes about 2-4 clock cycles, whereas access to global memory can take hundreds of cycles. Generally, CPUs are managed by the *operating system* (OS). These OS often generate unintended side effects in latency, jitter and determinism of the control behavior; see [85].

For programming on CPUs we use the language C++, which was invented by Bjarne Stroustrup in 1979 as an extension to C; see [86]. C++ became very popular for applications where the computational efficiency is essential. It offers a valuable way for hardware oriented programming while still providing high level programming constructs. For compiling C++ code we utilize the GNU Compiler Collection (GCC); see [87].

3.1.2 Graphics processing units

A Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) is optimized for rapid processing of simple tasks. Due to their highly parallel structure, GPUs outperform CPUs by orders of magnitude in algorithms where a huge amount of data has to be processed in parallel. The host CPU directs tasks to the GPU via a stream through a graphics pipeline. A GPU device has a scalable array of multithreaded *Streaming Multiprocessors* (SMs), each having a fixed set of processing cores. Each multiprocessor can execute hundreds of threads concurrently using an architecture called *Single-Instruction, Multiple-Thread* (SIMT). The multiprocessor creates, manages, schedules, and executes parallel threads in groups of 32, called warps. Each warp executes one instruction at a time. All instructions are pipelined, within a single thread instruction level parallelism is performed and thread level paral-

lelism is implemented through concurrent hardware multithreading. To coordinate this control flow parallel programming languages, such as CUDA, are used. For more details on CUDA we refer to Section 3.3.2. In general, a GPU has 3 types of physical memory: register memory, shared memory and global memory. Register memory (256 kB) and shared memory (48 kB) reside on chip and are fast in access, whereas global memory is usually several gigabytes, located off chip and is slow in access. As for CPUs, some unintended side effects in latency, jitter and determinism of the control behavior can be observed for GPUs as well; see [85].

Figure 3.1 shows a schematic illustration of the CPU and GPU architectures. The abbreviation ALU (white) denotes the arithmetic logic unit, which is a digital circuit performing arithmetic and bitwise operations. GPUs have a much higher memory bandwidth compared to CPUs, because more transistors are dedicated to data processing rather than caching (light gray) or flow control (dark gray). This explains why GPUs are extremely efficient for highly parallel computations, such as graphics rendering. They hide memory access latencies with computational throughput. In contrast, for the CPU memory access latencies are avoided through large data caches and flow control.

Figure 3.1. Schematic illustration of CPU and GPU architecture consisting of ALUs (white), flow control (dark gray), caches (light gray) and DRAM. The GPU dedicates more transistors to data processing.

3.1.3 Field programmable gate arrays

A Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) is an array of logic gates that can be configured by the programmer. Common functions, e.g., addition and multiplication, are implemented by interconnected digital subcircuits. These subcircuits, also called Configurable Logic Blocks (CLBs), build the core of the FPGAs programmable logic and provide boolean as well as arithmetic operations and data storage. Moreover, an FPGA contains so called I/O blocks, which consist of components that allow the communica-

tion between CLBs and other blocks on the board. Figure 3.2 illustrates a schematic representation of the design of an FPGA. The two most dominant FPGA manufacturers are Xilinx and Intel (former Altera). An FPGA is designed to be reconfigured by a programmer many times after it was manufactured. This is the reason why they are called field programmable. In contrast to that, ASICs (Application Specific Integrated Circuits) are fixed circuits executing a certain task. The production of such ASICs is very expensive, thus, the idea behind FPGAs is to provide fixed hardware, but a configurable functionality.

Figure 3.2. Schematic design of an FPGA.

In general, FPGA development is considered to be more difficult than programming micro controllers. However, FPGAs are always supported by software that converts your hardware design into programmings bits. The two most common programming languages for FPGA are called Verilog and *Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language* (VHDL). For more details we refer to [84].

3.2 Pipelining

For the control of a large AO system *pipelining* is used to increase the computational throughput. In a pipelined system the processor is working on different tasks at the same time by overlapping instructions, as illustrated for a simple example in Table 3.3.

Instead of six clock cycles used for the non pipelined instructions 1 and 2, only four clock cycles are required when using pipelining.

	cycle 1	cycle 2	cycle 3	cycle 4	cycle 5	cycle 6
Instr. 1	Fetch	Decode	Execute			
Instr. 2				Fetch	Decode	Execute
Pip. Instr. 1	Fetch	Decode	Execute			
Pip. Instr. 2		Fetch	Decode	Execute		

Table 3.3. Cycle without (Instr. 1 and Instr. 2) and with (Pip. Instr. 1 and Pip. Instr. 2) pipelining.

This simple concept is very efficient also for AO systems. The measurement vector s is obtained in HRT from the WFS and used to calculate the mirror commands with a reconstruction algorithm. However, due to the latency from the data acquisition from the sensors, s is not available at once. Hence, for operations that do not require the complete vector the computation can be started before the whole vector is available. This leads to an overlap of the time frame required for the data transfer and the one for calculation, and thus speeds up the overall computational performance. As an example we consider here the computation of pseudo open loop measurements; see also Equation (2.16);

$$s \leftarrow s + \Gamma a^{(i-1)},$$

where Γ denotes the SH matrix and $a^{(i-1)}$ is the DM shape of the previous time step. When closed loop control is applied this computation is done as a first step of a reconstruction algorithm, before the tomographic reconstruction takes place. The measurement vector here is only required for the final sum and computing the sum of two vectors is perfectly pipelineable. Thus, as soon as elements of s are accessible, the first elements of the result vector can be calculated.

3.3 Parallelization

Without parallelization it would not be possible to meet the real-time requirements of a large AO system as, e.g., required for the ELT. Therefore, we provide a rough overview over several parallel programming approaches for CPUs, GPUs and FPGAs. Again, we follow the work in [40, 41, 84].

3.3.1 Thread programming on CPU

A thread model in which all threads have access to shared variables is a common parallel programming model for multi-core platforms with a shared address space. The shared variables are used to exchange data. Below, we describe two popular environments for thread programming: Pthreads and OpenMP.

POSIX threads (Pthreads) is a standard, based on the programming language C, for thread-based programming. All data types, interfaces and macros related to Pthreads are available via a header file. The globally shared address space can be accessed by all threads of a process. In addition, each thread has a separate runtime stack to store local variables. To utilize Pthreads, a programmer has to identify parts of the program that can be executed concurrently and create a suitable number of user threads. These user threads are mapped by the scheduler of the library to system threads and then brought to execution by the scheduler of the operating system. The programmer has little influence on the library scheduler and cannot control the operating system scheduler. On the one hand, this reduces the programming effort, on the other hand an efficient mapping is not possible.

OpenMP is a portable standard for shared memory programming. The OpenMP API provides compiler directives, environmental variables as well as library routines for the programming languages C, C++ and Fortran. To utilize OpenMP the program needs to include the `<omp.h>` header file and it has to be compiled with appropriate compiler options to be translated into multi-threaded code. OpenMP is supported by several compilers like GCC or Clang. An OpenMP program starts with the execution of a single thread, which runs the program sequentially until a parallel construct is reached. At the beginning of this parallel region the initial thread becomes a master thread and creates a team of new threads. The code inside the parallel region is then executed concurrently by all the threads in the team. At the end of the region synchronization takes place and only the master thread continues the execution.

Pthreads are a lower-level programming interface for shared memory programming. Hence, an extremely fine-grained control over threads is possible, such as creating, joining etc., and programmers can gain better control on performance optimizations. OpenMP, on the other hand, has a higher level of abstraction and comes with a portable interface, which makes it very easy to implement compared to Pthreads. Moreover, it still provides satisfactory performance results.

3.3.2 Parallel programming on GPU

Since several years GPUs are employed in non-graphics applications, such as numerical simulations. They are very efficient for programs where the data parallelism is so large that a high number of compute cores gain a considerable speed up. This trend inspired GPU manufacturers to develop programming environments, such as CUDA and OpenCL, which provide a general purpose parallel programming model suitable for GPU architectures. For both programming environments the program is separated into a CPU (or host) part and a GPU (or device) part. In the following, we take a closer look at CUDA. Details about OpenCL can be found in [88]. For the CUDA programming model we follow the work in [41].

The *Compute Unified Device Architecture* (CUDA) is a programming language developed by NVIDIA to control the parallel flow of GPUs. Nowadays, CUDA is widely used for high performance computing in scientific research. CUDA extends the C or C++ programming language in order to support the programming of parallel machines. Moreover, there exist wrappers for other common languages like Python, Java and .NET as well as for MATLAB, Mathematica and R. The CUDA parallel programming model assumes that all CUDA threads execute on a physically separate device, which operates as a coprocessor to the host running the C++ program. In general, the CPU program is responsible for all input/output operations and copies data into the global memory of the GPU. Moreover, the host calls device functions on the GPU to start the parallel processing. Important factors for designing appropriate GPU code are memory organization and the transfer between CPU and GPU. CUDA offers special C++ functions, called kernels, that are executed in parallel by a predefined number of threads. Each thread has a unique index that is accessible within the kernel. The thread index is a three dimensional vector, to provide a natural way of applying operations on vectors, matrices and volumes in parallel often needed within scientific computations. For recent GPUs there is a limit of 1024 threads per block, because all threads are located on the same core and must share the memory resources there. A kernel can be executed by several blocks consisting up to 1024 threads. Blocks are organized in an one-, two- or three-dimensional grid as illustrated in Figure 3.4. The architecture of NVIDIA GPUs is built on an array of Streaming Multiprocessors (SMs). When a kernel is invoked by a CUDA program, the blocks of the grid are distributed to multiprocessors with available execution capacity. All threads of a thread block execute simultaneously on one multiprocessor, and multiple blocks can execute concurrently on one multiprocessor.

The CUDA parallel programming model assumes that host and device have their own separate memory spaces in DRAM, called host memory and device memory, respectively. CUDA threads can access data from different types of memory, as illustrated in Figure 3.5. Threads can share data through shared memory, whereas register memory, also called local memory, is the memory available to a single thread. Global memory is accessible by all threads and the host CPU. Moreover, there are two additional read-

Figure 3.4. A grid of thread blocks.

Figure 3.5. CUDA memory design.

only memory spaces accessible by all threads, namely the constant and texture memory spaces. Unified memory provides a managed memory that is accessible from CPUs and GPUs. This simplifies the task of porting applications from pure C++ to CUDA by eliminating the need of explicit copy statements between host and device written by the programmer.

3.3.3 Single Instruction Multiple Data

The main idea behind *Single Instruction Multiple Data* (SIMD) is to apply the same arithmetic operation to several data elements simultaneously using proper vector instructions. Such computations are supported by many CPUs as well as GPUs. The benefit of these computations is that a single vector instruction handles the compu-

tation of several elements, whereas a scalar instruction treats only one data element. Special vector load instructions are used to load the vector registers with the data from main memory. There are two common ways of dealing with vectorization: the use of vectorizing compilers (referred to as implicit or auto-vectorization) and the use of a programming language (called explicit vectorization). If there is no dependence from one loop iteration to the following, vectorizing compilers can transform them automatically into an equivalent vector statement. Since version 4.0 OpenMP supports SIMD instructions by using the directive *omp simd*. This statement indicates that the respective loop can be transformed into a SIMD loop. Beside the OpenMP directives, there are several other ways to include explicit SIMD vectorization. The Streaming SIMD Extensions (SSE) provide a language based option to cope with vectorization. SSE instructions are working on 128-bit floating point registers. The registers can store eight 16-bit values, four 32-bit values, or two 64-bit values and perform operations on these values concurrently. With the more recently introduced Intel Advanced Vector Extensions (AVX) working on up to 512-bit floating point registers is possible. Intel AVX2 provides special intrinsics for loading and storing vectors as well applying vector operations. The drawback with AVX2 or SSE is that its more complicated to include and it requires to rewrite the code, in contrast to OpenMP, where one additional directive is enough.

3.3.4 Parallel programming on FPGAs

A VHDL based system design includes on the one hand the functionality, described by VHDL code and translated by a synthesis tool into a file that is executable by the FPGA. On the other hand, it is important to verify the functionality by simulations. Figure 3.6 shows the FPGA design flow. The functionality design is composed into various steps. In a first step, the programmer has to describe the task in VHDL. Next, the synthesis tool analyzes this code and implements it utilizing various, connected, basic digital components. Note, that in this stage the exact placement of certain components and the wiring between them is not considered. After synthesis is finished the placement and routing of components is performed. For verifying the functionality a so called testbench file is used. This file contains test cases, written in VHDL, that are used to validate the correctness of the design file. Various inputs are defined and the results are evaluated within simulations. After placement and routing the exact timing of the circuit is fixed. Note, that fixed in this case means that the time for each instruction is known beforehand and not varying like for CPUs or GPUs. The last step is the commissioning of the design.

A VHDL module represents a hardware component of a bigger system that describes a certain functionality. To fully define such a component you need to describe the ports, i.e., the input and output signals, and the functionality. The description that is visible from outside is called entity, whereas the functionality inside is called architecture. To be able to store intermediate results, similar to variables in other programming languages,

Figure 3.6. VHDL design flow.

signals are used. Note, that all signals and port assignments are executed in parallel. So called processes extend the concept of assignments in VHDL. A process is similar to a function for higher programming languages, with one significant difference. A process is not called by the programmer inside the VHDL code, but is constantly active and listens to changes of signals in its signal sensitivity list. Within a process static variables can be declared, i.e., variables that are visible only inside the process and keep the value. Moreover, constructs like *for* or *if* instructions can be used. To structure VHDL code a module can be instantiated from other modules. Figure 3.7 illustrates a simple example of structuring a VHDL code with modules. Module *Add3* initiates two instances of module *Add2* to be able to add three values.

Figure 3.7. VHDL hierarchy with modules.

Chapter 4

Mathematical preliminaries

In this chapter we focus on the mathematical fundamentals utilized throughout this thesis. Besides the principles of inverse problems and methods for solving large linear systems we present more specific techniques that serve as a basis for the algorithms presented in the upcoming chapters. The general introduction to inverse problems and their handling by regularization is mainly based on the work in [89, 90]. The statistical approach for the regularization of inverse problems, i.e., Bayesian inference, follows the content in [91]. The discussion on solvers for large linear systems is to a large extent built on [92]. The part on iterative solvers is also partly from [93]. The extension to multiple right hand sides, available consecutively in every time step, is based on the work in [27, 28].

4.1 Inverse problems

Let \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} be two Hilbert spaces with norms $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{X}}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\mathcal{Y}}$, respectively, and let $T \in L(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y})$ be a bounded linear operator between them. The problem of finding $x \in \mathcal{X}$ for a given $y \in \mathcal{Y}$ that satisfies

$$Tx = y \tag{4.1}$$

is called well-posed, according to Hadamard [94], if all of the following conditions are satisfied

1. $\mathcal{R}(T) = \mathcal{Y}$
2. $\mathcal{N}(T) = \{0\}$
3. $T^{-1} \in L(\mathcal{Y}, \mathcal{X})$.

If the operator T violates any of these conditions, the problem is called *ill-posed*.

Violation of the first condition means that for some $y \in \mathcal{Y}$ there does not exist a solution x . In this situation, it is typical to look for an x such that Tx lies closest to y , which leads to the definition of the least squares solution. An $x \in \mathcal{X}$ is called a least squares solution of (4.1) if

$$\|Tx - y\| = \inf\{\|Tz - y\| : z \in \mathcal{X}\}.$$

Furthermore, it can be shown that it is an least squares solution if and only if the so called normal equation

$$T^*Tx = T^*y \tag{4.2}$$

is fulfilled, where T^* denotes the adjoint operator of T .

If the second condition is violated then there exist infinitely many solutions, i.e., uniqueness is not given. Uniqueness can be enforced by choosing an x with minimal norm. Let L be the set of least squares solutions

$$L := \{x : x \text{ is a least squares solution of } Tx = y\}.$$

The best-approximate solution x^\dagger is defined as the least squares solution $x \in L$ with minimal norm, i.e.,

$$\|x^\dagger\| = \inf\{\|z\| : z \in L\}.$$

The operator which maps y to the best-approximate solution x^\dagger is called Moore-Penrose (generalized) inverse T^\dagger . It is defined by the unique linear extension \tilde{T}^{-1} through

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger) &:= \mathcal{R}(T) \dot{+} \mathcal{R}(T)^\perp, \\ \mathcal{N}(T^\dagger) &= \mathcal{R}(T)^\perp, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\tilde{T} := T|_{\mathcal{N}(T)^\perp} : \mathcal{N}(T)^\perp \rightarrow \mathcal{R}(T).$$

It holds that

$$T^\dagger = (T^*T)^{-1}T^*.$$

There exists no least squares solution if $y \notin \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$.

The third condition deals with stability. For many practical problems, such as X-ray tomography or signal and image processing, the operator T does not have a closed range. Moreover, measurements are usually contaminated by noise, i.e., there is only an error-contaminated approximation $y^\delta \in \mathcal{Y}$ of y available. If T^{-1} is unbounded, the solution of the equation

$$Tx = y^\delta, \quad x \in \mathcal{X}, \quad y^\delta \in \mathcal{Y},$$

even if it exists, may not be a meaningful approximation of the desired solution, i.e., $x^\delta \not\rightarrow x^\dagger$ if $y^\delta \rightarrow y$. Therefore, *regularization methods* have to be used to approximate

the real solution. There are several approaches on how regularization can be performed. In particular, we distinguish in the following between deterministic and stochastic regularization.

4.1.1 Deterministic regularization

In the deterministic setting we assume to have an error-contaminated approximation $y^\delta \in \mathcal{Y}$ of y that satisfies

$$\|y - y^\delta\|_{\mathcal{Y}} \leq \delta,$$

with a known bound $\delta > 0$ called noise level.

A regularization method in the deterministic setting consists of a pair (R_α, α) , where $\{R_\alpha\}$ is a parameter dependent family of continuous regularization operators that approximate T^\dagger . The regularized solution x_α^δ is defined as

$$x_\alpha^\delta := R_\alpha y^\delta,$$

where α is called regularization parameter. For $\delta \rightarrow 0$ the condition $x_\alpha^\delta \rightarrow x^\dagger$ must be fulfilled.

Definition 1 ([89]). Let $T : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ be a bounded linear operator between the Hilbert spaces \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} and $\alpha_0 \in (0, \infty]$. For every $\alpha \in (0, \alpha_0)$, let

$$R_\alpha : \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow \mathcal{X},$$

be a continuous operator. The family $\{R_\alpha\}$ is called a regularization or a regularization operator (for T^\dagger), if for all $y \in \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$, there exists a parameter choice rule $\alpha = \alpha(\delta, y^\delta)$ such that

$$\limsup_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \{\|R_{\alpha(\delta, y^\delta)} y^\delta - T^\dagger y\| : y^\delta \in \mathcal{Y}, \|y^\delta - y\| \leq \delta\} = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

holds. Here,

$$\alpha : \mathbb{R}^+ \times \mathcal{Y} \rightarrow (0, \alpha_0) \quad (4.4)$$

is such that

$$\limsup_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \{\alpha(\delta, y^\delta) : y^\delta \in \mathcal{Y}, \|y^\delta - y\| \leq \delta\} = 0. \quad (4.5)$$

For a specific $y \in \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger) := \mathcal{R}(T) \dot{+} \mathcal{R}(T)^\perp$, a pair (R_α, α) is called a (convergent) regularization method (for solving $Tx = y$) if (4.3) and (4.5) hold.

Hence, a regularization method is composed of a regularization operator and a parameter choice rule for α . The parameter α allows to balance between stability and accuracy of the regularized solution. If α is chosen small, the problem is more accurate but less stable. In contrast, if α is chosen large, the stability is enforced by the minimization of

the regularization term. However, the problem is further away from the original one. Finding the right α , i.e., the balancing between stability and accuracy, is an important task for inverse problems. In the following sections, we describe two different types of parameter choice rules.

A-priori parameter choice rules

We now consider regularization methods based on spectral theory for selfadjoint linear operators. The idea is to utilize the spectral family $\{E_\lambda\}$ of (T^*T) . If (T^*T) is continuously invertible, then $(T^*T)^{-1} = \int \frac{1}{\lambda} dE_\lambda$. Via the so called normal equation (4.2), the best-approximate solution x^\dagger can then be written as

$$x^\dagger = \int \frac{1}{\lambda} dE_\lambda T^* y; \quad (4.6)$$

see [89]. If $\mathcal{R}(T)$ is non-closed and $y \notin \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$, then the integral does not exist, since $\frac{1}{\lambda}$ has a pole in 0. However, we can approximate $\frac{1}{\lambda}$ by a parameter dependent family of functions $g_\alpha(\lambda)$ and obtain

$$x_\alpha := \int g_\alpha(\lambda) dE_\lambda T^* y, \quad (4.7)$$

without a pole in 0. If the operator on the right side of (4.7) is continuous, we get the following formulation for noisy data

$$x_\alpha^\delta := \int g_\alpha(\lambda) dE_\lambda T^* y^\delta. \quad (4.8)$$

If x_α is defined by (4.7), then the residual has the following representation

$$x^\dagger - x_\alpha = \int (1 - \lambda g_\alpha(\lambda)) dE_\lambda x^\dagger.$$

We define, for all (α, λ) for which $g_\alpha(\lambda)$ is defined

$$r_\alpha(\lambda) := 1 - \lambda g_\alpha(\lambda). \quad (4.9)$$

Theorem 2 ([89]). *Let, for all $\alpha > 0$, $g_\alpha : [0, \|T\|^2] \rightarrow \mathcal{R}$ fulfill the following assumptions: g_α is piecewise continuous, and there is a $C > 0$ such that*

$$|\lambda g_\alpha(\lambda)| \leq C,$$

and

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} g_\alpha(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda}$$

for all $\lambda \in (0, \|T\|^2]$. Then, for all $y \in \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} x_\alpha = \lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} g_\alpha(T^*T)T^* y = x^\dagger$$

holds with $x^\dagger = T^\dagger y$.

Theorem 2 describes the convergence of the regularized solution with exact data. The next theorem deals with stability, i.e., the propagation of data noise.

Theorem 3 ([89]). *Let g_α and C be as in Theorem 2, x_α and x_α^δ be defined by (4.7) and (4.8), respectively. For $\alpha > 0$, let*

$$G_\alpha := \sup\{|g_\alpha(\lambda)| : \lambda \in [0, \|T\|^2]\}. \quad (4.10)$$

Then,

$$\|x_\alpha - x_\alpha^\delta\| \leq \delta\sqrt{CG_\alpha}.$$

For the total error we obtain

$$\|x_\alpha^\delta - x^\dagger\| \leq \|x_\alpha - x^\dagger\| + \delta\sqrt{CG_\alpha}. \quad (4.11)$$

From Theorem 2 we know that the first estimate goes to 0 if $y \in \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$. However, since $g_\alpha(\lambda) \rightarrow 1/\lambda$ as $\alpha \rightarrow 0$,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} G_\alpha = \infty.$$

The next theorem gives an estimate for the convergence rate of $\|x_\alpha^\delta - x^\dagger\|$ in terms of $r_\alpha(\lambda)$.

Theorem 4 ([89]). *Let g_α fulfill the assumptions of Theorem 2, r_α be defined by (4.9) and $\mu > 0$. Let for all $\alpha \in (0, \alpha_0)$ and $\lambda \in [0, \|T\|^2]$,*

$$\lambda^\mu |r_\alpha(\lambda)| \leq c_\mu \alpha^\mu \quad (4.12)$$

hold for some $c_\mu > 0$ and assume that G_α as defined in (4.10) fulfils

$$G_\alpha = \mathcal{O}(\alpha^{-1}) \text{ as } \alpha \rightarrow 0.$$

If x^\dagger satisfies the source condition

$$x^\dagger \in \mathcal{R}((T^*T)^\mu), \quad (4.13)$$

then, with the parameter choice rule

$$\alpha \sim \delta^{\frac{2}{2\mu+1}},$$

we obtain

$$\|x_\alpha^\delta - x^\dagger\| = \mathcal{O}(\delta^{\frac{2\mu}{2\mu+1}}).$$

The largest $\mu = \mu_0$ for which Condition (4.12) holds is called qualification of the regularization method. Even if the source condition (4.13) holds for a bigger μ we cannot obtain better rates than with μ_0 . This phenomenon is called saturation.

In general, a $\mu > 0$ such that (4.13) holds is not often known. However, to construct an a-priori parameter choice rule which is at least of optimal order we need to know it. Now, we focus on a-posteriori parameter choice rules and look at the widely-used discrepancy principle.

A-posterior parameter choice rules

Let g_α be defined as in Theorem 2 and let r_α be defined by (4.9). Further, let

$$\tau > \sup\{|r_\alpha(\lambda)| : \alpha > 0, \lambda \in [0, \|T\|^2]\}.$$

Then the regularization parameter defined by the discrepancy principle is given by

$$\alpha(\delta, y^\delta) := \sup\{\alpha > 0 : \|Tx_\alpha^\delta - y^\delta\| \leq \tau\delta\}.$$

Theorem 5 ([89]). *The regularization method (R_α, α) , where α is defined via the discrepancy principle is convergent for all $y \in \mathcal{R}(T)$ and of optimal order in $\mathcal{R}((T^*T)^\mu)$ for $\mu \in (0, \mu_0 - 1/2]$, i.e., $\|x_{\alpha(\delta, y^\delta)} - x^\dagger\| = \mathcal{O}(\delta^{\frac{2\mu}{2\mu+1}})$.*

Tikhonov regularization

One of the most prominent regularization techniques is called *Tikhonov regularization*. Here, the regularization operator is defined by

$$R_\alpha := (T^*T + \alpha I)^{-1}T^*.$$

The regularized solution $x_\alpha^\delta := R_\alpha y^\delta$ is given by the solution of the linear system of equations

$$(T^*T + \alpha I)x = T^*y^\delta.$$

Solving the above equation is equivalent to minimizing the so called Tikhonov functional

$$x_\alpha^\delta := \min_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \left\| Tx - y^\delta \right\|^2 + \alpha \|x\|^2. \quad (4.14)$$

4.1.2 Bayesian inference

In contrast to the deterministic approach, in which the regularization method consists of a family of well-posed problems, the statistical approach regularizes the problem by taking the uncertainty of the solution and the measurements into account. Equation (4.1) is formulated in a stochastic setting, i.e., using random variables. To derive the posterior distribution a priori information about the solution, the measurements and the noise are used.

In the literature, *Bayesian inverse problems* are often formulated as finite dimensional problems. Thus, below we assume to have a discretized version of the inverse problem

in (4.1). Further, we assume the presence of additive noise. Then, Equation (4.1) can be written as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{TX} + \mathbf{E},$$

with the unknown random variable $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the known random variables $\mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{E} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, that correspond to the measurements and noise, respectively. We assume that the random variables are continuous and that the noise is independent from the unknown \mathbf{X} . Furthermore, we assume that the measurement is a realization of \mathbf{Y} , denoted by y^δ . In the Bayesian framework, the solution of the inverse problem is then given as the posterior distribution

$$\Pi_{post} = \Pi_{\mathbf{X}}(x|y^\delta) = \frac{\Pi_{\mathbf{XY}}(x, y^\delta)}{\Pi_{\mathbf{Y}}(y^\delta)}.$$

The posterior distribution can be calculated using Bayes'-formula; see, e.g., [92] for details. Utilizing the posterior distribution we can calculate point estimates. One method to do this is the *maximum a-posteriori* (MAP) estimate. In fact, in [8] they show that the MAP estimate provides an optimal point estimate for the inverse problem arising in AO. It is defined by the following optimization problem

$$x_{\text{MAP}} = \operatorname{argmax}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \Pi_{\mathbf{X}}(x|y^\delta).$$

Using the assumption that \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{E} are mutually independent and that the prior and noise random variables are modeled as Gaussian with mean x_0, e_0 and covariance matrices $C_{\mathbf{X}}, C_{\mathbf{E}}$ the MAP estimate can be reformulated as a minimization problem

$$x_{\text{MAP}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \left(\|x - x_0\|_{C_{\mathbf{X}}^{-1}}^2 + \|y^\delta - Tx - e_0\|_{C_{\mathbf{E}}^{-1}}^2 \right). \quad (4.15)$$

Note that the norms in equation (4.15) induced by the covariance matrices, which are symmetric and positive definite, are defined by

$$\|x\|_C^2 := (Cx, x). \quad (4.16)$$

The solution to this minimization problem is given by the solution of the linear system of equations

$$(T^*C_{\mathbf{E}}^{-1}T + C_{\mathbf{X}}^{-1})x = T^*C_{\mathbf{E}}^{-1}(y^\delta - e_0) + C_{\mathbf{X}}^{-1}x_0.$$

If we are dealing with Gaussian random variables with zero mean and the noise is independent and identically distributed with variance σ_E^2 the MAP estimate in (4.15) reduces to

$$x_{\text{MAP}} = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^n} \left(\sigma_E^2 \|x\|_{C_{\mathbf{X}}^{-1}}^2 + \|y^\delta - Tx\|_{C_{\mathbf{E}}^{-1}}^2 \right). \quad (4.17)$$

In this case the MAP estimate and the Tikhonov functional in (4.14) coincide. The solution space here depends on the prior distribution and the regularization parameter is chosen based on information about noise.

4.2 Wavelets

We will utilize *wavelets* later on for the discretization of the operators arising within the atmospheric tomography problem as proposed in [23]. Throughout this section we will briefly recap the necessary mathematical theory behind them. We start with the general definition of wavelets, continue with the wavelet decomposition and the discrete wavelet transform (DWT). The DWT is one of the fundamental tools for the efficient algorithms in this thesis. Moreover, we extend this concept to wavelets on bounded domains and wavelets in two dimensions, because we need them for our application.

We introduce wavelets, as proposed, e.g., in [95], via the definition of *multiresolution analysis* (MRA) of $L^2(\mathbb{R})$. Such a MRA consists of a nested set of approximation spaces of $L^2(\mathbb{R})$

$$0 \subset \cdots \subset V_{-1} \subset V_0 \subset V_1 \subset \cdots \subset L^2(\mathbb{R}) \quad (4.18)$$

that fulfill the following properties

$$\overline{\bigcup_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} V_j} = L^2(\mathbb{R}) \quad (4.19)$$

$$\bigcap_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} V_j = \{0\} \quad (4.20)$$

$$f \in V_j \Leftrightarrow f(2^{-j}\cdot) \in V_0 \quad (4.21)$$

$$f \in V_0 \Leftrightarrow f(\cdot - k) \in V_0 \quad (4.22)$$

$\forall j, k \in \mathbb{Z}$. Further, there exists a $\varphi \in V_0$ such that

$$\{\varphi(\cdot - k) : k \in \mathbb{Z}\} \quad (4.23)$$

forms an orthonormal basis of V_0 . The first three conditions (4.18)-(4.20) are fulfilled by many spaces, however, the last three (4.21)-(4.23) characterize MRA. The spaces V_j are spanned by the so called scaling functions at scale j given by

$$\varphi_{jk}(x) := 2^{j/2} \varphi(2^j x - k) \text{ for } k \in \mathbb{Z}.$$

If conditions (4.18)-(4.23) are fulfilled it is shown, e.g., in [95], that a wavelet function ψ exists such that the span of

$$\psi_{jk}(x) := 2^{j/2} \psi(2^j x - k)$$

forms a orthonormal basis of $L^2(\mathbb{R})$ for $j, k \in \mathbb{Z}$. The orthogonal complement of V_j in V_{j+1} is given by the space spanned by the wavelet functions ψ_{jk} for fixed j

$$W_j = \text{span}\{\psi_{jk} : k \in \mathbb{Z}\},$$

i.e., $V_{j+1} = V_j \oplus W_j$. Note that the spaces W_j are orthogonal to each other.

The remaining question is how to construct such functions ψ . One way is to utilize low and high pass filters. Since the function $\varphi \in V_0 \subset V_1$, it can be represented by

$$\varphi(x) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle \varphi, \varphi_{1k} \rangle \varphi_{1k}(x). \quad (4.24)$$

Here $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the $L^2(\mathbb{R})$ scalar product. The coefficients $l_k := \langle \varphi, \varphi_{1k} \rangle$ are called low pass coefficients. Note that if φ has finite support, the sequence l_k is finite as well. We will now look in more detail on a particular wavelet family, called Daubechies N wavelets, with finite support

$$\overline{\text{supp } \varphi} := [0, 2N - 1].$$

For increasing N , the support of the wavelet family becomes wider and the decay in the frequency domain faster; see [95]. This wavelets are not available analytically, except for the case $N = 1$, called Haar wavelets. Instead, they are defined by the low pass filter coefficients of dimension $2N$, which are given as

$$l := (l_0, \dots, l_{2N-1}).$$

The relation between the high and low pass filter coefficients is given by

$$h = (h_0, \dots, h_{2N-1}) = (l_{2N-1}, \dots, l_0), \text{ where} \\ h_k := (-1)^k l_{2N-k-1} \quad \text{for } k = 0, \dots, 2N - 1.$$

This low and high pass filter coefficients can be used to numerically approximate the wavelet functions. The wavelet function $\psi \in W_0 \subset V_1$ can be represented, similar to the scaling function in (4.24), by

$$\psi(x) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle \psi, \psi_{1k} \rangle \psi_{1k}(x).$$

It can be shown; see [95]; that $h_k = \langle \psi, \psi_{1k} \rangle$.

The MRA offers the possibility to decompose $L^2(\mathbb{R})$ in several ways by

$$L^2(\mathbb{R}) = \bigoplus_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} W_j = V_{j_0} \oplus \left(\bigoplus_{j \geq j_0} W_j \right). \quad (4.25)$$

These decomposition allows to represent a function $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R})$ by

$$f(x) = \sum_{j,k \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle f, \psi_{jk} \rangle \psi_{jk}.$$

We denote by $d_{jk} := \langle f, \psi_{jk} \rangle$ the detail coefficients of the decomposition. An alternative way is to represent f by

$$f(x) = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle f, \varphi_{j_0 k} \rangle \varphi_{j_0 k} + \sum_{j \geq j_0} \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \langle f, \psi_{jk} \rangle \psi_{jk}.$$

The coefficients $a_{jk} := \langle f, \varphi_{j_0 k} \rangle$ are called approximation coefficients.

4.2.1 Discrete wavelet transform

The concept of approximation and detail coefficients allows us to define an important tool for utilizing wavelets in practical examples, called the *discrete wavelet transform* (DWT).

Without loss of generality let $j_0 = 0$. Further, we define the two wavelet scale indices j_0 and J with $j_0 < J$. The previous derived relation $V_{j+1} = V_j \oplus W_j$ allows the representation

$$V_J = V_0 \oplus W_0 \oplus W_1 \oplus \cdots \oplus W_{J-1},$$

which implies that an approximation of $L^2(\mathbb{R})$ at a finer scale J can be formulated as a coarser scale approximation at scale $j = 0$ with details at scales $j = 0, \dots, J - 1$. The DWT performs a wavelet decomposition by mapping approximation coefficients at the fine level $(a_{Jk})_{k \in \mathbb{Z}}$ to wavelet coefficients $(a_{0k}, d_{jk})_{0 \leq j < J, k \in \mathbb{Z}}$ at a coarse level. The inverse DWT, also referred to as wavelet reconstruction, reconstructs the approximation coefficients at a finer scale from the wavelet coefficients. Both operations can be defined via recursively applying convolution operations at each scale. In particular, the approximation and detail coefficients of f at a certain scale j are given by convolution of the approximation coefficients at $j + 1$ with the high and low pass filter coefficients

$$\begin{aligned} a_{jn} &= \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} l_{k-2n} a_{j+1,k} \quad \text{and} \\ d_{jn} &= \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} h_{k-2n} a_{j+1,k} \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, the approximation coefficients at scale $j + 1$ are given by

$$a_{j+1,n} = \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} l_{n-2k} a_{jk} + \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} h_{n-2k} d_{jk}.$$

For more details on how the convolution equations for the DWT and the inverse DWT are derived, we refer to [95].

4.2.2 Bounded domains

Since we are dealing with bounded domains in our practical examples, we have to extend the concept of wavelets to intervals. The wavelet basis of $L^2(\mathbb{R})$, in general, does not provide an orthonormal basis on an interval. However, there exist different ways on how to enhance the concept in order to form a basis of $L^2([a, b])$. In this thesis we use the so called periodic wavelets, which extend the wavelets periodically around the border of the interval. For the sake of simplicity we fix the interval to $[0, 1]$, which leads to the

following definition of the periodic scaling functions

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_{jk}^{per}(x) &:= \sum_{t \in \mathbb{Z}} \varphi_{jk}(x+t), \\ \psi_{jk}^{per}(x) &:= \sum_{t \in \mathbb{Z}} \psi_{jk}(x+t).\end{aligned}$$

Due to the shifts the function is periodically wrapped around the boundary. From now on we will omit the *per* notation and always refer to the periodic wavelets when dealing with wavelets on intervals. Utilizing the periodic wavelets we have a finite number of 2^j shifts at each scale j . Thus, the approximation space W_j and the details space V_j have finite dimension. As a consequence the number of convolution operations, that determine the direct and inverse wavelet transform, is finite as well. In matrix form the convolution operations W_j of dimension $2^{j+1} \times 2^{j+1}$ at each scale $j = 0, \dots, J-1$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}(W_j)_{i, (2i+p \bmod 2^{j+1})} &= \sum_{\substack{0 \leq q < 2N \\ (q \bmod 2^{j+1})=p}} l_q \\ (W_j)_{2^j+i, (2i+p \bmod 2^{j+1})} &= \sum_{\substack{0 \leq q < 2N \\ (q \bmod 2^{j+1})=p}} h_q,\end{aligned}$$

where the coefficients of the low as well as the high pass filter are of length $2N$ and $0 \leq i < 2^j$ and $0 \leq p < 2N$. The matrix W_j is simply the DWT at a certain scale j . Figure 4.1 illustrates the DWT W_4 for Daubechies 3 wavelets. This wavelet family has six low pass filter coefficients (indicated with blue crosses) that are contained in the first $2^j = 16$ rows of the matrix. The six high pass filter coefficients (marked with red crosses) are listed in the last 16 rows of W_4 . This sparse representation of the DWT will be important later on for an efficient implementation.

We denote the vector of approximation coefficients by $a_j = (a_{j0}, \dots, a_{j,2^j-1})$ and the vector of detail coefficients by $d_j = (d_{j0}, \dots, d_{j,2^j-1})$. The wavelet transform at the scale j is then simply a matrix vector multiplication

$$W_j a_{j+1} = \begin{pmatrix} a_j \\ d_j \end{pmatrix}.$$

The inverse wavelet transform is a matrix vector multiplication with the transposed matrix

$$W_j^T \begin{pmatrix} a_j \\ d_j \end{pmatrix} = a_{j+1}.$$

The DWT maps a_J to $(a_0, d_0, \dots, d_{J-1})$ by sequentially multiplying with the matrices W_{J-1}, \dots, W_0 . On the other hand, the inverse DWT maps $(a_0, d_0, \dots, d_{J-1})$ to a_J via multiplications with the matrices W_0^T, \dots, W_{J-1}^T .

Figure 4.1. Illustration of Daubechies 3 wavelets W_4 matrix. Blue crosses indicate low pass filter coefficients, whereas red crosses mark high pass filter coefficients. Zero elements are represented by black dots. The matrix is of size $2^4 \times 2^4$.

Later in this thesis we will use the DWT to transform the nodal values of a piecewise linear and continuous function to wavelet coefficients. Hence, we conclude this section with a discussion on how to apply the DWT to such functions. We define a set of 2^J points with equidistant spacing $x_k = \delta k$ for $0 \leq k < 2^J$ and $\delta > 0$. Further, we denote by $f : [0, \delta(2^J - 1)] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a piecewise linear function. This function is linear in each interval $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$ for $0 < k < 2^J$. The nodal values of f approximate the approximations coefficients at the finest scale by

$$a_{Jk} \approx \delta^{1/2} f(\delta k), \text{ for } 0 \leq k < 2^J.$$

In fact, it is shown in [95], that the scaling constant $\delta^{1/2}$ imposes the following norm preserving representation

$$\|f\|_{L^2} \approx \|a_J\|_{\ell^2} = \|c\|_{\ell^2},$$

where $c = (a_{00}, d_{00}, d_{10}, \dots, d_{J-1, 2^{J-1}-1})$ denotes the wavelet coefficient vector.

4.2.3 Extension to two dimensions

Since the bounded domains in our practical examples are in two dimension, we need to generalize the concept of wavelets to two dimensions. One way to do this are tensor products, i.e., the MRA of $L^2(\mathbb{R}^2)$ is generated by approximation spaces that are formed

by tensor products of V_j in the x and y variables by

$$\mathbf{V}_j = V_j \otimes V_j.$$

In 2D we are dealing with three different detail spaces, that are called horizontal, vertical and diagonal detail spaces, respectively,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{W}_j^1 &= V_j \otimes W_j, \\ \mathbf{W}_j^2 &= W_j \otimes V_j, \\ \mathbf{W}_j^3 &= W_j \otimes W_j.\end{aligned}$$

Similar to the one dimensional case the space $L^2(\mathbb{R}^2)$ can be represented for any index $j_0 \in \mathbb{Z}$ by

$$L^2(\mathbb{R}^2) = \bigoplus_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} (\mathbf{W}_j^1 \oplus \mathbf{W}_j^2 \oplus \mathbf{W}_j^3) = \mathbf{V}_{j_0} \oplus \left(\bigoplus_{j \geq j_0} (\mathbf{W}_j^1 \oplus \mathbf{W}_j^2 \oplus \mathbf{W}_j^3) \right).$$

The scaling functions in two dimensions, which span V_j , are given by

$$\varphi_{jk}(x, y) = \varphi_{jk_1}(x) \varphi_{jk_2}(y),$$

and the wavelet functions by

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_{jk}^1(x, y) &= \varphi_{jk_1}(x) \psi_{jk_2}(y), \\ \psi_{jk}^2(x, y) &= \psi_{jk_1}(x) \varphi_{jk_2}(y), \\ \psi_{jk}^3(x, y) &= \psi_{jk_1}(x) \psi_{jk_2}(y),\end{aligned}$$

for $k = (k_1, k_2) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ being the two dimensional shift indices.

As for the one dimensional case we utilize periodic wavelets for treating bounded domains. In fact, we use the periodic wavelets in x and y variables for the square domain $[0, 1]^2$. Thus, we have a finite number of shifts $0 \leq k_1, k_2 < 2^j$ and a total number of 2^{2j} wavelet functions. The approximation coefficients a_j as well as the three detail coefficients d_j^t of $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^2)$ at a scale j are then matrices of size $2^j \times 2^j$. These matrices are given by

$$\begin{aligned}(a_j)_{k_1 k_2} &:= a_{jk} := \langle f, \varphi_{jk} \rangle, \\ (d_j^t)_{k_1 k_2} &:= d_{jk}^t := \langle f, \psi_{jk}^t \rangle,\end{aligned}$$

where $t = 1, 2, 3$ and $k = (k_1, k_2)$ with $0 \leq k_1, k_2 < 2^j$.

In two dimensions the wavelet transform as well as its inverse at a certain scale j correspond to two multiplications by the transformation matrix W_j and W_j^T , respectively,

$$\left(W_j(W_j a_{j+1})^T\right)^T = W_j a_{j+1} W_j^T = \begin{pmatrix} a_j & d_j^1 \\ d_j^2 & d_j^3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.26)$$

$$\left(W_j^T(W_j \begin{pmatrix} a_j & d_j^1 \\ d_j^2 & d_j^3 \end{pmatrix})^T\right)^T = W_j^T \begin{pmatrix} a_j & d_j^1 \\ d_j^2 & d_j^3 \end{pmatrix} W_j = a_{j+1} \quad (4.27)$$

The DWT and the inverse DWT correspond to recursively applying (4.26) and (4.27) for $j = J - 1, \dots, 0$ and $j = 0, \dots, J - 1$, respectively.

Later on we will apply the DWT to a continuous piecewise bilinear function to transform its nodal values to wavelet coefficients. For that purpose, we define a grid of 2^{2J} points in \mathbb{R}^2 with equidistant spacing, i.e., $x_{k_i} = \delta k_i$ for $\delta > 0$, $i = 1, 2$ and $0 \leq k_i < 2^J$, by

$$\{(x_{k_1}, x_{k_2}) : 0 \leq k_1, k_2 < 2^J\},$$

and the corresponding bilinear function over the grid points by

$$f : [0, \delta(2^J - 1)]^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}.$$

This function can be approximated by the approximation coefficients at scale $j = J$ via

$$a_{Jk} \approx \delta f(\delta k_1, \delta k_2).$$

As for the one dimensional case the scaling constant δ enforces a norm preserving representation; see [95] for details;

$$\|f\|_{L^2}^2 \approx \|a_J\|_F^2 = \|c\|_{\ell_2}^2,$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm and c the wavelet coefficients

$$c = (a_{00}, d_{00}^1, d_{00}^2, d_{00}^3, d_{10}^1, \dots, d_{J-1, 2^{J-1}-1}^3).$$

Note, that we index the vector of wavelet coefficients according to the following bijective mapping

$$\lambda = \lambda(j, k, t) = 2^{2j}t + 2^j k_2 + k_1,$$

where we call $\lambda = 0, \dots, 2^{2J} - 1$ the global wavelet index.

4.3 Solving large linear systems

In order to numerically compute a solution of an operator equation, discretization is required. This often leads to a system of linear equations

$$Ax = b, \quad (4.28)$$

with A being a square $n \times n$ matrix, x is the desired solution and b the right hand side vector both of size n . Throughout this work we assume n to be of magnitudes up to several hundred thousands. Such large dimensions occur in many real world examples, e.g., within AO.

Throughout this thesis we assume A to be *symmetric and positive definite* (SPD). A matrix is called symmetric if $A = A^T$. A symmetric matrix is positive definite if $(Ax, x) > 0$ for all $x \neq 0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$. By (\cdot, \cdot) we understand the Euclidean scalar product.

4.3.1 Performance criteria for solvers of large linear systems

In order to be able to compare different solvers for large linear systems we need to define performance criteria. In the following, we describe five important criteria in more detail. The first three are used for a first analysis of an algorithm and measure the theoretical performance. The last two depend on the hardware in use and the implementation. In this thesis we use all of them to verify the performance of the presented algorithms.

In the mathematical context, solvers are often compared using the *computational complexity*, which is simply the number of operations required to solve the problem. Usually, this quantity is stated asymptotically in the order of n . For time sensitive problems, like the ones arising within AO, methods with linear complexity, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(n)$ operations for solving the problem, are preferred over methods with quadratic complexity $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. Another important aspect is the *memory usage* of a solver. For large systems the storage can come to its limits. Hence, methods that require less memory are preferred. A more precise measure than the computational complexity is the number of *floating point operations* (FLOPs). We understand by the number of FLOPs any mathematical operation, such as addition or multiplication, or assignment, which involves floating point numbers. We illustrate the benefit of measuring the number of FLOPs instead of using the computational complexity on the example of a sparse matrix vector multiplication. This operation has quadratic computational complexity. We denote a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ *sparse* if a considerable number of entries of the matrix is zero. A matrix that is not sparse is called a *dense* matrix. In general, a dense matrix needs n^2 units of memory and $2n^2 - n$ FLOPs when multiplying with a vector. A sparse matrix, on the other hand, requires only nnz^2 units of memory and $2nnz^2 - nnz$ number of FLOPs, where nnz denotes the non-zero elements per row. Note that depending on the structure of the matrix, it might be necessary to additionally store the position of the non-zero entries. The number of FLOPs $2nnz^2 - nnz$ for sparse matrices is, in general, considerably smaller than $2n^2 - n$.

Without parallelization we would not be able to solve many time sensitive problems. We call a method *parallelizable*, if the whole or at least major parts of the method can be executed in parallel without being dependent on intermediate results. The big advan-

tages of parallelization is the reduction of run-time while the number of FLOPs remains the same. Different hardware systems offer different possibilities for parallelization; see Section 9.2 for details. In some applications numerical advantages can be gained when A is formulated as a linear function $A : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ rather than as full or sparse matrix. This is referred to as *matrix free* methods, which are also used throughout the algorithms in this thesis. For illustrating the benefit of a matrix-free method let us consider the simple example of a matrix $A = vv^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. Saving the matrix requires n^2 units of storage, whereas storing the vector v only uses n units of memory. Performing a matrix vector multiplication Ax with the matrix requires $n(2n - 1)$ number of FLOPs. In contrast, multiplying x with v^T and then v needs only $2(2n - 1)$ FLOPs.

4.3.2 Direct application of the inverse

The most straightforward way to solve Equation (4.28) is to directly apply the inverse of the matrix A by

$$x = A^{-1}b.$$

This is of course only possible if A is invertible. We refer to this method as *matrix vector multiplication* (MVM). The drawback here is that even if A is sparse, in general, its inverse is a dense matrix, and thus is considerably more costly to apply. Moreover, computing the inverse scales at $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. Altogether, this method can become very demanding for large systems. On the other hand, the method is very well parallelizable by using the fact that

$$x_i = A_i^{-1}b,$$

where A_i^{-1} denotes that i -th row of the matrix and x_i the i -th entry.

4.3.3 Matrix factorization

A way to reduce the computational demand for the MVM method is to use a matrix factorization, i.e., to compute a decomposition of A instead of the inverse. A very common factorization method, based on Gaussian elimination, is called *LU-factorization*. Within this technique the matrix A is decomposed into triangular blocks by

$$A = LU,$$

where L is a lower triangular and U an upper triangular matrix. The solution of Equation (4.28) is then given by the solution of the two systems

$$\begin{aligned} Lc &= b, \\ Ux &= c, \end{aligned}$$

via back substitution. The special case of an SPD matrix is referred to as Cholesky decomposition and leads to

$$A = LL^T.$$

Under the assumption that A is dense, the factorization reduces the memory usage to $n^2/2$. However, for computing the solution the complexity is still $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. The computation of the factorization itself scales at $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. Moreover, the back substitution is not well parallelizable. Beneath these two factorization methods there exist plenty of others, e.g., eigenvalue decomposition. Every SPD matrix A has an eigenvalue decomposition

$$A = U\Lambda U^T,$$

where $\Lambda = \text{diag}(\lambda_i)$ is a diagonal matrix containing the eigenvalues and U is an orthogonal matrix of eigenvectors. The inverse is given by

$$A^{-1} = U\Lambda^{-1}U^T.$$

The memory consumption and computational costs for this approach are the same as for *Cholesky decomposition*; see [96].

4.3.4 Iterative methods

The computational demand of direct methods raises the motivation in the development of alternative approaches. So called iterative methods apply the forward operator A repeatedly to obtain the solution. For sparse matrices and those that can be represented in a matrix-free way iterative methods are especially efficient. If the matrix A has a matrix-free representation where, e.g., the memory consumption and computational complexity is of linear order and the number of iterations is fixed, then the iterative approach scales at $\mathcal{O}(n)$. Parallelization of an iterative method is possible if the application of A is parallelizable, however, the iterations itself cannot be parallelized. Therefore, the number of iterations is a crucial indicator for the computational performance. Parallelization of the application of A is guaranteed if the matrix is dense or sparse, whereas for a matrix-free representation parallelization is not always possible. We focus here on the most prominent iterative solver, for A being SPD, called *conjugate gradient* (CG) algorithm.

The CG method is based on the idea that for an SPD matrix A , solving the linear system $Ax = b$ is equivalent to minimize

$$\frac{1}{2}(Ax, x) - (b, x).$$

The minimization of this functional is executed in an iterative way over the subspace that is spanned by the so called search directions p . In theory, the CG method needs at most n iterations until convergence; see [93]. However, for time sensitive problems

this is far too much. In many practical examples the method provides already a good approximation after a couple of iterations. For real-time applications, such as the ones arising within AO, the CG method is often terminated after a fixed number of *maxIter* iterations. Although, a sufficient accuracy cannot be guaranteed with this approach. For the algorithms presented in this thesis we apply the CG algorithm to the residual vector $r_0 = b - Ax_0$ with an initial guess x_0 in order to improve the convergence. The CG method is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 CG Algorithm for $Ax = b$

```

1: Input:     $x_0$  (initial guess)
                $r_0$  (initial residual)
                $maxIter$  (number of PCG iterations)
2: Output:   $x_{k+1}$  (solution after  $maxIter$  iterations)
                $r_{k+1}$  (residual after  $maxIter$  iterations)
3:  $p_0 = r_0$ 
4: for  $k = 0, \dots, maxIter$  do
5:    $q_k = Ap_k$ 
6:    $\alpha = (r_k, r_k) / (p_k, q_k)$ 
7:    $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha p_k$ ,  $r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha q_k$ 
8:    $\beta = (r_{k+1}, r_{k+1}) / (r_k, r_k)$ 
9:    $p_{k+1} = r_{k+1} + \beta p_k$ 
10: end for

```

In the following we list important properties of the CG method, that can be found, e.g., in [27]. We will use these properties later on to extend the CG method in a way that convergence is improved when having multiple right hand sides that are available consecutively in every time step.

The residuals are orthogonal to each other

$$(r_i, r_j) = 0 \text{ for } i, j \geq 0, i \neq j.$$

The search directions p_i are A -orthogonal to each other

$$(Ap_i, p_j) = 0 \text{ for } i, j \geq 1, i \neq j.$$

After m CG iterations we define the matrix of residuals $R_m := (r_0, \dots, r_m)$ and the matrix of conjugate search directions $P_m := (p_0, \dots, p_m)$. The following conditions hold

$$P_m^T A P_m = D_m \text{ and } \text{span}(R_m) = \text{span}(P_m) = \mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0), \quad (4.29)$$

where D_m is a diagonal matrix of size $m \times m$ and $\mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0)$ is the Krylov subspace of size $m + 1$, which is defined as

$$\mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0) := \text{span}\{r_0, Ar_0, \dots, A^{m-1}r_0\}. \quad (4.30)$$

Further, we introduce

$$H_m = I - P_m D_m^{-1} (A P_m)^T, \quad (4.31)$$

the matrix of the A -orthogonal projections onto $\mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0)^\perp$.

The convergence behavior of the CG method is influenced by the eigenvalue decomposition of the matrix A . The error at iteration m ; see [93]; is bounded by

$$\|x_k - x\|_A \leq 2 \|x_0 - x\|_A \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa} + 1} \right)^k, \quad (4.32)$$

where x denotes the exact solution. The *condition number* is given by

$$\kappa = \frac{\lambda_{\max}(A)}{\lambda_{\min}(A)},$$

with λ_{\min} and λ_{\max} being the largest and smallest eigenvalue and κ is the condition number of A . Note, that the norm induced by a SPD matrix is defined by

$$(x, y)_A := (Ax, y), \quad \|x\|_A^2 := (x, x)_A.$$

There are two possibilities on how the CG method can be used in the context of inverse problems. First, it can be applied to a regularized equation, such as (4.14) or (4.15). Since the operators involved are SPD, the CG method is simply used as for well-posed problems. On the other hand, it is possible to directly apply the algorithm to the infinite dimensional normal equation (4.2) in Hilbert spaces where T has a closed range [97]. For those T that do not have closed range, convergence was shown for $y \in \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$, e.g., in [98, 99]. Note, that in general the x_i do not convergence towards a stable solution, if $y \notin \mathcal{D}(T^\dagger)$ [2, 100]. Although, in [100, 101] they show that the CG algorithm can serve as a regularization method, when a proper stopping rule is used. The number of iterations is then the regularizing parameter. In this thesis we apply the CG method to the regularized Equation (4.15).

Preconditioning

The convergence rate of an iterative method is affected by the eigenvalue distribution of the matrix involved. Hence, the convergence behavior can be improved by a transformation into a system with the same solution, but where the matrix has a more convenient distribution of eigenvalues. This transformation technique is called *preconditioning*. A preconditioner can be multiplied from the left, the right or both sides, which is then called split or mixed preconditioner.

If we apply left preconditioning to Equation (4.28) we multiply with a preconditioner M , which should be (easily) invertible, from the left

$$M^{-1}Ax = M^{-1}b.$$

Right preconditioning is related to a variable transformation, i.e., after the solution of the preconditioned equation is found the variable has to be transformed back to obtain the solution for the original equation,

$$\begin{aligned} AM^{-1}y &= b, \\ x &= M^{-1}y. \end{aligned}$$

Because we want to preserve the symmetry of the left hand side matrix, in order to be able to apply the CG method, we prefer a split preconditioner $M^{-1} = M^{-1/2}M^{-1/2}$. Equation (4.28) then becomes

$$M^{-1/2}AM^{-1/2}y = b, \tag{4.33}$$

$$x = M^{-1/2}y. \tag{4.34}$$

If the preconditioner M is SPD, then the matrix $M^{-1/2}AM^{-1/2}$ is it as well. Thus, the CG method can be applied to solve the system.

Finding the right preconditioner for a certain problem is not straightforward. On the one hand, M should approximate A , but on the other hand, the inverse of M should be easier to compute. If we set $M = I$, it is very simple to invert, but we do not gain a reduction in the number of iterations. If we use $P = A$, then an iterative solver converges in one step, but applying the preconditioner is of same the complexity as solving the original problem. Thus, finding the right preconditioner is related to finding a balance between those two requirements.

A split preconditioner can be directly included into the CG algorithm, which then is referred to as Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient algorithm (PCG). The PCG method as shown in Algorithm 2 for solving Equation (4.28) does exactly the same as using Algorithm 1 for Equation (4.33). Thus, we can avoid to compute the factorization $M^{-1} = M^{-1/2}M^{-1/2}$ by using the PCG method.

Equation (4.32) gives us a hint on how good a preconditioner is by suggesting to use a preconditioner that reduces the condition number of the left hand side matrix. Based on this estimate one may conclude that if the condition number of $M^{-1/2}AM^{-1/2}$ is much smaller than that of A the convergence of the algorithm is faster.

4.3.5 Consecutive right-hand sides

In many practical examples we are dealing with several right-hand sides b of Equation (4.28) available consecutively, e.g., in every time step. Since the PCG method is an

Algorithm 2 PCG Algorithm for $Ax = b$

```

1: Input:     $x_0$  (initial guess)
                $r_0$  (initial residual)
                $maxIter$  (number of PCG iterations)
                $M^{-1}$  (preconditioner)
2: Output:  $x_{k+1}$  (solution after  $maxIter$  iterations)
                $r_{k+1}$  (residual after  $maxIter$  iterations)
3:  $p_0 = r_0$ 
4:  $z_0 = M^{-1}r_0$ 
5: for  $k = 0, \dots, maxIter$  do
6:    $q_k = Ap_k$ 
7:    $\alpha = (r_k, z_k)/(p_k, q_k)$ 
8:    $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha p_k, r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha q_k$ 
9:    $z_{k+1} = M^{-1}r_{k+1}$ 
10:   $\beta = (r_{k+1}, z_{k+1})/(r_k, z_k)$ 
11:   $p_{k+1} = z_{k+1} + \beta p_k$ 
12: end for

```

iterative solver we need to reapply it for every new right-hand side b . This is costly in terms of computational speed compared to direct solvers, where the factorization can be reused independently of the right-hand side as long as the left-hand side matrix does not change. If the right-hand sides are only slightly changing, so called *augmented Krylov subspace methods*, see [27], can reduce the number of PCG iterations considerably.

Let us assume we want to solve the two preconditioned linear systems

$$M^{-1/2}AM^{-1/2}x^{(1)} = M^{-1/2}b^{(1)}, \quad (4.35)$$

$$M^{-1/2}AM^{-1/2}x^{(2)} = M^{-1/2}b^{(2)}, \quad (4.36)$$

where A is a symmetric and positive definite matrix and M^{-1} is a preconditioner. Further, we assume that the two right-hand sides $b^{(1)}$ and $b^{(2)}$ are available consecutively. When solving Equation (4.35) for $b^{(1)}$ with m PCG iterations we obtain information that can be reused for solving the subsequent system in (4.36). In fact, we reuse the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0^{(1)})$, where $r_0^{(1)} = b - M^{-1/2}AM^{-1/2}x^{(1)}$ is the initial residual of the previous system.

As a first step the initial guess x_0 is improved by a Galerkin projection technique. This approach was first proposed by Saad in [28] and adapted for the PCG algorithm in [27]. The initial residual $r_0^{(2)}$ is chosen orthogonally to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0^{(1)})$ generated for the previous system. This orthogonality condition is enforced by the condition

$$W_m^T r_0^{(2)} = 0, \quad (4.37)$$

where $W_m := (w_0, \dots, w_m)$ is the matrix of m conjugate search directions. In the following theorem we will show how to choose the initial guess and the initial residual in order to fulfil this orthogonality condition. Since this result is especially important throughout the thesis, we briefly recap the proof, which is taken from [27].

Theorem 6 ([27]). *Let x_0 denote the initial guess and $r_0 = b^{(2)} - Ax_0$ the corresponding initial residual. Further, assume that we have already solved the problem $Ax^{(1)} = b^{(1)}$ with m PCG iterations. To enforce the orthogonality condition (4.37) we must choose*

$$x_0^{(2)} = x_0 + W_m D_m^{-1} W_m^T r_0 \quad (4.38)$$

and the initial residual as

$$r_0^{(2)} = b^{(2)} - Ax_0^{(2)} = H_m^T r_0, \quad (4.39)$$

where $W_m := (w_0, \dots, w_m)$ is the matrix of m conjugate search directions, D_m is defined by Equation (4.29) and H_m by Equation (4.31).

Proof. Since the matrix H_m^T is the A^{-1} -orthogonal projection onto the Krylov subspace generated for the previous system, Condition (4.37) is equivalent to

$$\exists u : r_0^{(2)} = H_m^T u,$$

i.e., $r_0^{(2)} \in \text{Im}(H_m^T)$. Using this information we get

$$\begin{aligned} r_0^{(2)} &:= b^{(2)} - Ax_0^{(2)} = H_m^T u = u - AW_m D_m^{-1} W_m^T u \\ x_0^{(2)} &= A^{-1}(b^{(2)} - u) + W_m D_m^{-1} W_m^T u. \end{aligned}$$

Let now $x_0 = A^{-1}(b^{(2)} - u)$, which implies $u = b^{(2)} - Ax_0 = r_0$. Finally, we obtain

$$x_0^{(2)} = x_0 + W_m D_m^{-1} W_m^T r_0.$$

□

Another way to improve the convergence behavior is to keep the orthogonality of the residual vectors with respect to the Krylov subspace throughout the iterations of the PCG method. As for the first idea, this method was proposed in [28] (called modified Lanczos process) and adapted for the CG method in [27] (referred to as augmented CG). Here, we have two subspaces: the Krylov subspace generated for the previous system $\mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0^{(1)})$ and the subspace $\text{span}(r_0^{(2)}, \dots, r_k^{(2)})$ generated by the current residuals. To enforce the orthogonality in each PCG iteration the residual $r_{k+1}^{(2)}$ in iteration $k+1$ has to be orthogonal to both subspaces and the direction $p_{k+1}^{(2)}$ has to be A -orthogonal to both subspaces. Thus, this approach is a projection method onto the space

$$\mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}) := \mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0^{(1)}) + \text{span}(r_0^{(2)}, \dots, r_k^{(2)}),$$

which is not a Krylov-subspace. The projection is defined by the following three conditions; see [27]:

$$p_0^{(2)} = (I - W_m D_m^{-1} (A W_m)^T) r_0^{(2)} \quad (4.40)$$

$$x_{k+1}^{(2)} - x_k^{(2)} \in \mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}) \quad (4.41)$$

$$(r_{k+1}^{(2)}, z) = 0 \text{ for all } z \in \mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}). \quad (4.42)$$

The last condition is called a Petrov-Galerkin condition and is fulfilled if the current residual $r_{k+1}^{(2)}$ is orthogonal to the residual of the previous iteration $r_k^{(2)}$ and the current direction $p_{k+1}^{(2)}$ is A -conjugate to $p_k^{(2)}$ and $w_m^{(1)}$.

Algorithm 3 shows the augmented PCG method. In Lines 3 to 6 the initial guess and the initial residual are improved by Galerkin projection as presented in Equation (4.38) and (4.39). In Lines 7 to 11 the initial descent direction $p_0^{(2)}$ is updated such that it is A -orthogonal to the span(W_m). Finally, the new search direction $p_k^{(2)}$ is orthogonalized against the last search direction of the previous system w_m in Line 19. Since this is one of the fundamental algorithms in this thesis, we will prove in the following theorem that it implements the conditions previously stated for the augmented PCG method. Again the theorem as well as the proof are taken from [27].

Theorem 7 ([27]). *Algorithm 3 is a realization of the augmented PCG method defined by conditions (4.38), (4.39) and (4.40) - (4.42), i.e.,*

$$z^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0 \text{ and } z^T A p_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0 \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}).$$

Proof. Since $p_0 \in \mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}) = \text{span}(W_m) + \text{span}(R_0)$ we get by induction that $p_k \in \text{span}(W_m) + \text{span}(R_k)$ and Condition (4.41) immediately follows. Note that

$$\mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}) = \text{span}(W_m) + \text{span}(R_k) = \text{span}(W_m) + \text{span}(P_k).$$

We show by induction that $W_m^T r_k^{(2)} = 0$ and $W_m A p_k^{(2)} = 0$. These equalities are then used to prove that $(r_j^{(2)})^T r_{k+1}^{(1)} = 0$ and $(p_j^{(2)})^T A p_{k+1}^{(1)} = 0$ for $j \leq k$, which gives the desired result.

The condition $W_m^T r_k^{(2)} = 0$ and $W_m^T A p_k^{(2)} = 0$ is fulfilled for $k = 0$. By induction we assume that it is true for k and prove it for $k + 1$. The first condition can be rewritten as

$$W_m^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = W_m^T r_k^{(2)} - \alpha_k W_m^T A p_k^{(2)}.$$

Due to the induction hypothesis both terms are zero and we obtain the desired result $W_m^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$. For the second condition we get

$$W_m^T A p_{k+1}^{(2)} = W_m^T A (r_{k+1}^{(2)} - \mu_{k+1} w_m^{(1)}) + \beta_{k+1} W_m^T A p_k^{(2)}.$$

Algorithm 3 Augmented PCG Algorithm for $Ax = b$ [27]

```

1: Input:       $x_0, r_0$  (initial guess and residual)
                  $M^{-1}$  (preconditioner)
                  $W_m = (w_1, w_2, \dots)$  (matrix of previous descent directions)
2: Output:    $x_{k+1}, r_{k+1}$  (new solution and residual)
                  $P = (p_1, p_2, \dots)$  (matrix of current descent directions)
3: for  $j = 0, \dots, m$  do
4:    $\sigma_j = (r, w_j)/(w_j, Aw_j)$ 
5:    $x_0 = x_0 + \sigma_j w_j^{(i)}, r_0 = r_0 - \sigma_j Aw_j$ 
6: end for

7:  $z_0 = M^{-1}r_0$ 
8: for  $j = 0, \dots, m$  do
9:    $z_0 = z_0 - (z, Aw_j)/(w_j, Aw_j)w_j$ 
10: end for

11:  $p_0 = z_0$ 
12: for  $k = 0, 1, \dots$  until convergence do
13:    $\alpha_k = (r_k, z_k)/(p_k, Ap_k)$ 
14:    $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k p_k, r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha_k Ap_k$ 
15:    $z_{k+1} = M^{-1}r_{k+1}$ 
16:    $\mu_{k+1} = (z_{k+1}, Aw_m)/(w_m, w_m)$ 
17:    $z_{k+1} = z_{k+1} - \mu_{k+1}w_m$ 
18:    $\beta_k = (r_{k+1}, z_{k+1})/(r_k, z_k)$ 
19:    $p_{k+1} = z_{k+1} + \beta_k p_k$ 
20: end for

```

The second term is zero because of the induction hypothesis. Now it remains to show that $W_m^T A(r_{k+1}^{(2)} - \mu_{k+1} w_m^{(1)}) = 0$. To prove this equality we consider the term

$$0 = H_m r_{k+1}^{(2)} = r_{k+1}^{(2)} - \mu_{k+1} w_m - \sum_{j=1}^{j=m-1} \frac{(r_{k+1}^{(2)}, Ap_j^{(2)})}{(p_j^{(2)}, Ap_j^{(2)})} p_j^{(2)}.$$

For $j \leq m-1$, $Ap_j^{(2)} \in \text{span}(p_0^{(2)}, \dots, p_{j+1}^{(2)}) \subset \text{span}(W_m)$. Moreover, we know that $W_m^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$, and thus $(r_{k+1}^{(2)}, Ap_j^{(2)}) = 0$ and the last term in the equation above vanishes. We get $r_{k+1}^{(2)} - \mu_{k+1} w_m = 0$, which implies that $W_m^T Ap_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$.

The remaining part is the proof of $(r_j^{(2)})^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$ and $(p_j^{(2)})^T Ap_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$ for $j \leq k$. Again we use induction and the case $k=0$ is trivially fulfilled. Now we assume that the conditions hold for k and get

$$(r_j^{(2)})^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = (r_j^{(2)})^T r_k^{(2)} - \alpha_k (r_j^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)}.$$

For $j < k$ we have $(r_j^{(2)})^T r_k^{(2)} = 0$ by the induction hypothesis. Moreover, we know that $r_j^{(2)} \in \text{span}(W_m) + \text{span}(P_j)$, thus, $(r_j^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} = 0$. By induction and the condition above we conclude that $W_m^T Ap_k^{(2)} = 0$. Altogether, we obtain $(r_j^{(2)})^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$. For the case $j = k$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} (r_k^{(2)})^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} &= (r_k^{(2)})^T r_k^{(2)} + \alpha_k (r_k^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} \\ &= (r_k^{(2)})^T r_k^{(2)} + \alpha_k ((p_k^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} - \beta_k (p_{k-1}^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} \\ &\quad + \mu_k (p_m^{(1)})^T Ap_k^{(2)}) \\ &= (r_k^{(2)})^T r_k^{(2)} + \alpha_k (p_k^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} \\ &= (r_k^{(2)})^T r_k^{(2)} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{(p_k^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)}}{(p_k^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)}} \right) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The missing part is to show $(p_j^{(2)})^T Ap_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$ by induction. Again we distinguish between the case $j < k$ and $j = k$. For $j < k$ we have

$$(p_j^{(2)})^T Ap_{k+1}^{(2)} = (p_j^{(2)})^T Ar_{k+1}^{(2)} + \beta_{k+1} (p_j^{(2)})^* Ap_k^{(2)} - \mu_{k+1} (p_j^{(2)})^T Aw_m.$$

For the first term we have $(p_j^{(2)})^T Ar_{k+1}^{(2)} = (r_{k+1}^{(2)})^T Ap_j^{(2)} = (r_{k+1}^{(2)})^T (r_j^{(2)} - r_{j+1}^{(2)}) / \alpha_j$, which is zero by the result just above. The second term is zero by the induction hypothesis and the last term, because of the condition shown in the first part of this proof. For $j = k$ we have

$$(p_k^{(2)})^T Ap_{k+1}^{(2)} = (r_{k+1}^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} + \beta_{k+1} (p_k^{(2)})^T Ap_k^{(2)} - \mu_{k+1} (p_k^{(2)})^T Aw_m.$$

The term can be rewritten as $(r_{k+1}^{(2)})^T A p_k^{(2)} = -(r_{k+1}^{(2)})^T r_{k+1}^{(2)} / \alpha_{k+1}$ and $(p_k^{(2)})^T A w_m = 0$. Together with the definition of α_{k+1} and β_{k+1} we get $(p_k^{(2)})^T A p_{k+1}^{(2)} = 0$, which completes the proof. \square

We are now interested in computing an asymptotic error bound at a certain iteration k . We utilize the fact that the augmented CG is nothing else than a classical CG applied to the special matrix $H_m^T A H_m$, where H_m is defined by (4.31). Again this result is taken from [27].

Theorem 8 ([27]). *Let κ_1 denote the condition number of $H_m^T A H_m$, where H_m is given by (4.31). The error at iteration k of the augmented CG algorithm is given by*

$$\|x_k - x\|_A \leq 2 \|x_0 - x\|_A \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa_1} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa_1} + 1} \right)^k. \quad (4.43)$$

Proof. We first briefly recap the proof in [27] that for $k \geq 0$ $\text{span}(r_0^{(2)}, \dots, r_k^{(2)}) = \mathcal{K}_k(H_m^T A H_m, r_0^{(2)})$ and

$$\mathcal{K}_{m,k}(A, r_0^{(1)}, r_0^{(2)}) = \mathcal{K}_m(A, r_0^{(1)}) \oplus^{\perp A} \mathcal{K}_k(H_m^T A H_m, r_0^{(2)}).$$

The proof of these two conditions is based on a polynomial formulation of r_k and p_k in the two variables A and H . This enables the characterization of $\text{span}(r_0^{(2)}, \dots, r_k^{(2)})$ as the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_k(AH_m, r_0^{(2)})$. It is easy to show that $H_m^T A H_m = A H_m$ and by induction $(H_m^T A H_m)^j r_0^{(2)} = (A H_m)^j r_0^{(2)}$ so that finally we obtain $\text{span}(r_0^{(2)}, \dots, r_k^{(2)}) = \mathcal{K}_k(H_m^T A H_m, r_0^{(2)})$.

Since this result implies that the augmented CG algorithm is just a classical CG applied to the matrix $H_m^T A H_m$, we can use the error bound of the classical version, which concludes the proof. \square

The result of this theorem implies that the convergence rate of the augmented PCG is the same or better than that of the classical CG method, because κ_1 is no larger than κ_0 , the condition number of A . Moreover, the augmented CG is simply a classical PCG with the symmetric semidefinite preconditioner $H_m H_m^T$; see [27].

Chapter 5

Atmospheric tomography

In this chapter we focus on the mathematical models describing atmospheric tomography within the AO systems LTAO, MOAO and MCAO. For more details on AO systems we refer to Chapter 2. The general problem formulation is mainly based on [60]. Furthermore, we present the standard solver for solving the atmospheric tomography problem, called Matrix Vector Multiplication, and several more novel iterative approaches. In the end, we will focus on the iterative Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm that was first proposed in [24]. We adapt this solver later on in this thesis to fulfill the real-time requirement of ELTs.

5.1 Mathematical problem formulation

In atmospheric tomography the aim is to reconstruct the turbulent layers, i.e., the refractive index of the turbulent atmosphere, using measurements obtained from WFSs; see [60]. For details about the concept of turbulence layers we refer to Section 2.3.3. The atmospheric tomography operator A relates WFS measurements and turbulences at layers by

$$s = (s_g^x, s_g^y)_{g=1}^G = A\phi, \quad (5.1)$$

where G is the number of guide stars, $\phi = (\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L)$ denote the L turbulent layers and s the WFS measurements.

In this thesis we assume the usage of a SH WFS. Then the tomography operator A is composed into a geometric propagation operator P into the direction of the guide star and a SH operator Γ . For a specific guide star g we obtain

$$s_g = \Gamma_g P_g \phi \quad \text{for } g = 1, \dots, G.$$

For details on the SH operator see Section 2.4.3, for the definition of the geometric propagation operator into the direction of NGS we refer to Section 2.4.1 and for LGS to Section 2.4.1.

In atmospheric tomography we are dealing with a limited angle problem. Mathematically, Equation (5.1) is ill-posed; see [1]; i.e., the relation between the solution and the measurements is unstable. For details on inverse problems we refer to Section 4.1. To handle this inverse problem regularization is required. Because the Bayesian framework allows the incorporation of statistical information about turbulence and noise, it is frequently used in the community of AO; see Section 4.1.2. In this statistical approach we assume S and Φ to be random variables corresponding to the SH WFS measurements and turbulence layers, respectively. Moreover, we assume additive noise, modeled by the random variable η . Altogether, we obtain the formulation of Equation (5.1) in the Bayesian framework as

$$S = A\Phi + \eta.$$

The random variables Φ and η are modeled by Gaussian variables with zero mean and covariance matrices C_Φ and C_η , respectively.

The layers are statistically independent, hence, the covariance matrix C_Φ has a block diagonal structure

$$C_\Phi = \text{diag}(C_1, \dots, C_L),$$

where C_ℓ is the covariance matrix at layer ℓ . Assuming the von Karman turbulence model, the covariance matrix at a certain layer is given by

$$C_\ell = \mathcal{F}^{-1}\Phi_\ell\mathcal{F};$$

see Section 2.3.2. Here, \mathcal{F} denotes the Fourier transform and Φ_ℓ is the spectral density of the layer given by

$$\Phi_\ell(\kappa) := \frac{0.023r_0^{-5/3}\lambda^2C_n^2(h_\ell)}{4\pi^2(|\kappa|^2 + \kappa_0^2)^{11/6}}. \quad (5.2)$$

We assume the noise to be independently distributed in every WFS, which implies a block-diagonal structure of

$$C_\eta = \text{diag}(\tilde{C}_1, \dots, \tilde{C}_{G_{LGS}}, \tilde{C}_{G_{LGS}+1}, \dots, \tilde{C}_G).$$

We denote by $G = G_{LGS} + G_{NGS}$ the number of guide stars. The definition of the covariance matrix for LGS is shown in Equation (2.6) and for NGS in (2.3).

For this setting it was shown in [8], that the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate provides an optimal point estimate for the solution given by

$$x_{MAP} = \operatorname{argmin}_{\phi \in \mathbb{R}^n} \{ \|\phi\|_{C_\phi^{-1}}^2 + \|s - A\phi\|_{C_\eta^{-1}}^2 \}.$$

The inner product here is given by Equation (4.16). The solution of this minimization problem is equivalent to the solution of the linear system of equations

$$(A^*C_\eta^{-1}A + C_\phi^{-1})\phi = A^*C_\eta^{-1}s, \quad (5.3)$$

where A^* denotes the adjoint tomography operator. Note, that the size of the operator A is, in general, larger for bigger telescopes. In the era of the new extremely large earthbound telescopes, solving the atmospheric tomography problem in real-time is a highly non-trivial task. That is the reason why efficient solvers are of great interest. In the following sections we show direct as well as iterative solvers that are currently used for the atmospheric tomography problem.

5.2 Direct solver

The standard procedure to solve Equation (5.3) is called Matrix Vector Multiplication (MVM) method; see [34]. In this approach the solution is computed by a matrix-vector multiplication with the matrix R , given by

$$R := (A^T C_\eta^{-1} A + C_\phi^{-1})^{-1} A^T C_\eta^{-1}.$$

A typical choice for discretization is the basis of Zernike polynomials; see, e.g, [8]. The MAP estimate is then obtained by simply multiplying the matrix R with the sensor measurements s . Commonly, a mirror fitting operator F , as defined in Section 2.4.2, is used in combination with the atmospheric reconstruction, allowing a direct mapping from sensor measurements to actuator commands

$$a = (FR)s.$$

The calculation of (FR) is often referred to as soft real-time, since the re-computation has to be done only when certain parameters change. In particular, the noise level, which changes the entries of C_η , and the turbulence parameters, that effect C_ϕ , cause changes in R . Telescope rotations or misalignment influences the matrix F . In contrast, the multiplication with the vector of sensor measurements s , which is done at approximately 500 – 1000 Hz, is called hard real-time. The matrix R is dense, thus, the MVM scales at $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$. However, the method is well parallelizable, and therefore still efficient. The dimension n is related to the size of the telescope, in particular, it depends on the number of subapertures of the WFSs and the number of actuators of the DMs. For ELTs n can get very large and the method becomes computationally expensive.

There exist different discretization strategies for Equation (5.3). Moreover, certain factorization techniques, such as Cholesky decomposition, are used to compute and store the inverse in a more efficient way. Altogether, there are different variations of the MVM available.

5.3 Iterative solvers

Because the MVM becomes very demanding for ELTs, recent research is more focused on iterative methods. Such kind of methods can outperform the MVM method if the number of iterations is small and the left hand side operator has an efficient representation. Since the left hand side operator of Equation (5.3) is symmetric and positive definite, the CG method can be used as an efficient solver. One way to reduce the number of iterations is preconditioning; see Section 4.3.4. Different PCG methods have been proposed in the literature for atmospheric tomography. The first methods in that direction utilize multigrid preconditioners (MG-PCG); see [11, 102, 103]. With those methods the computational complexity has been reduced to $\mathcal{O}(n^{3/2})$. Later on, the research in [12–14, 104] has been focused on Fourier domain preconditioning (FD-PCG), which leads to approaches that scale with $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. The Fourier basis turned out to be very efficient regarding a sparse representation of the underlying operators. Algorithms based on the Fourier transform have been proposed in [105, 106]. The forward as well as the inverse covariance of the noise are sparse, hence, efficient to apply. However, the inverse covariance of the layers is usually a dense matrix. This is why the research has shifted towards the development of a sparse approximation. Ellerbroek; see [107]; uses a modified turbulence power law in combination with biharmonics for the approximation. There exist two very promising other approaches that scale at $\mathcal{O}(n)$. The first one, called Fractal Iterative Method (FrIM), has been proposed by Tallon in [16, 17, 108, 109]. The second one is based on a dual domain discretization into a wavelet and finite element domain; see [23–25]; called Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm (FEWHA). Iterative methods in the context of AO are also studied beyond the Bayesian framework, e.g., an algorithm based on Kaczmarz iteration in [18, 19, 81]. In the upcoming subsections we give an overview on the FD-PCG, FrIM and FEWHA, because they are based on similar ideas. Later on we will focus on FEWHA and improve its convergence behavior by a Krylov subspace recycling technique.

5.3.1 Fourier Domain PCG

In the Fourier domain the bilinear interpolation, the SH operator and the covariance of turbulence layers in the MAP estimate (5.3) have a diagonal representation. Unfortunately, the mask itself not, because of its finite size. There are two possibilities on how to formulate the FD-PCG, both of them apply the Fourier transform and its inverse once per PCG iteration, and thus scale at $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. In the first approach the approximation by Ellerbroek in [107] is used together with a discretization in the bilinear domain. The problem is solved using the PCG with a Fourier domain preconditioner

$$\mathcal{F}^{-1}(\hat{A}^T \hat{C}_\eta^{-1} \hat{A} + \hat{C}_\phi^{-1}) \mathcal{F},$$

where the hat on the respective operators indicates the discretization in the bilinear domain and \mathcal{F} denotes the Fourier transform on each layer. On the other hand, the MAP estimate (5.3) can be directly discretized using the Fourier basis. There, all operators except the mask have a sparse representation. For applying the mask the inverse Fourier transform is applied. As for the first approach, the problem is solved using a PCG method with a Fourier domain preconditioner.

5.3.2 Fractal Iterative Method

Within the *Fractal Iterative Method* (FrIM) the covariance matrix of turbulence layers C_ϕ is approximated using matrices $K = K_1 \cdot \dots \cdot K_p$, where p denotes the number of scales, with hierarchical structure

$$C_\phi \approx KK^T. \quad (5.4)$$

The sparse matrices K_i for $1 \leq i \leq p$ are computed by a modified mid-point algorithm; see [110]. The decomposition in (5.4) into the sparse matrices K_i allows the application with a complexity $\mathcal{O}(n)$. The MAP estimate is formulated as

$$(K^T A^T C_\eta^{-1} A + I)x = K^T A^T C_\eta^{-1} s, \quad (5.5)$$

where the solution is given by the variable transformation $\phi = Kx$ and C_ϕ is approximated by the block diagonal matrix KK^T . Equation (5.5) is solved using the PCG method with a diagonal preconditioner.

5.3.3 Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm

The *Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm* (FEWHA) is an iterative method that uses compactly supported orthonormal wavelets for representing the turbulent layers. In the frequency domain, these wavelet representation allows a completely diagonal approximation of the penalty term in (5.3). To achieve a sparse representation for the atmospheric tomography operator, discretization is applied using a piecewise bilinear basis of finite elements. Since the dual domain discretization of FEWHA is used for the real-time implementation and algorithms developed throughout this thesis, we will describe it in greater detail. For more details we refer to [23–25].

Discretization of the turbulence layers

The most important feature of FEWHA is the ability to approximate the penalty term C_ϕ by a diagonal matrix. For that purpose, we discretize a turbulence layer $\phi : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

at height h in the wavelet domain by

$$\phi(x, y) = \sum_{j \in \mathbb{Z}} \sum_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \sum_{t \in \{1, 2, 3\}} \langle \phi, \psi_{jk}^t \rangle \psi_{jk}^t(x, y), \quad \text{for } (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2,$$

where ψ_{jk}^t denote the wavelet functions. For details on the discretization in the wavelet domain we refer to [23]. Further, we assume that the spectral density of the turbulent field fulfils the von Karman model; see Section 2.3.2. The covariance matrix of the turbulence layers is given by

$$C_\phi = c(h) \mathcal{F}^{-1} m \mathcal{F},$$

where \mathcal{F} is the Fourier transform, m is the spectral density defined by

$$m(\kappa) = (\|\kappa\|^2 + \kappa_0^2)^{-11/6}$$

and $c(h)$, see also (5.2), is given by

$$c(h) = \frac{0.023 r_0^{-5/3} \lambda^2 C_n^2(h)}{4\pi^2}.$$

For any $f \in C_0^\infty(\mathbb{R}^2)$ the penalty term in the MAP estimate (5.1) can be approximated by

$$\|C_\phi^{-1/2} f\|_{L^2}^2 \simeq \frac{1}{c(h)} (\kappa_0^{11/3} \|f\|_{L^2}^2 + \|(-\Delta)^{11/12} f\|_{L^2}^2). \quad (5.6)$$

We refer again to [23] for more details. Since we are only interested in reconstructing the turbulent domain on a bounded region, we consider the periodically extended wavelets on the domain

$$\Omega_\phi = [0, \delta(2^J - 1)^2] - \xi,$$

where J denotes the number of wavelet scales used for the discretization, $\delta > 0$ is a scaling factor and $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^2$ represents the shift from the origin. Within the discretized setting the function f in (5.6) is represented by a finite number of wavelet coefficients. Together with the Bernstein-Jackson inequalities; see [111]; this leads to the representation of Equation (5.6) by a diagonal matrix

$$D_{\lambda\lambda} = \frac{1}{c(h)} (\kappa_0^{11/3} + 2^{(11/3)j}),$$

where $\lambda = 0, \dots, 2^{2J-1}$ is the global wavelet index and $j = 0, \dots, J-1$ corresponds to the scale index. This concept is then extended to L turbulent layers $\phi = (\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L)$ at heights $0 \leq h_1 < \dots < h_L$ by introducing the square domain Ω_l and the diagonal matrix D_l . The full problem is defined via the block-diagonal matrix

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(D_1, \dots, D_L).$$

Finally, the penalty term is approximated by

$$\|C_\phi^{-1/2} \phi\|_{L^2}^2 = \sum_{l=1}^L \|C_l^{-1/2} \phi_l\|_{L^2}^2 \approx \sum_{l=1}^L (D_l c_l, c_l)_{L^2} = (\mathbf{D} \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{c}).$$

Discretization of the atmospheric tomography operator

A block representation of the atmospheric tomography operator A is given by

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_1 & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \Gamma_G \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} P_{11}^{LGS} & \dots & P_{1L}^{LGS} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ P_{G1}^{NGS} & \dots & P_{GL}^{NGS} \end{bmatrix},$$

where Γ_g denotes the SH operator at the aperture of the telescope and $P_{g\ell}^{NGS}$ and $P_{g\ell}^{LGS}$ are the projection operators into NGS or LGS direction which are given by Equation (2.2) and Equation (2.5), respectively. The domain observed by a WFS in the direction $\theta_g = (\theta_g^x, \theta_g^y)$ of the guide star g is given by

$$\Omega_{g\ell}^{LGS} := \left(1 - \frac{h_\ell}{H}\right) \Omega + (\theta_g^x, \theta_g^y) h_\ell \quad (5.7)$$

for an LGS and for an NGS by

$$\Omega_{g\ell}^{NGS} := \Omega + (\theta_g^x, \theta_g^y) h_\ell. \quad (5.8)$$

The two operators $\Gamma_{g\ell}^{NGS}$ and $\Gamma_{g\ell}^{LGS}$ are SH operators on the two projected domains $\Omega_{g\ell}^{NGS}$ and $\Omega_{g\ell}^{LGS}$, respectively.

The discretization of operator A in the wavelet domain is based on computing the interaction of the operator between a wavelet function on a single layer and the corresponding SH measurement. This leads to the following discretized version of the atmospheric tomography problem in (5.3)

$$(\tilde{A}^T C_\eta^{-1} \tilde{A} + \alpha D) \phi = \tilde{A}^T C_\eta^{-1} s, \quad (5.9)$$

where \tilde{A} is the atmospheric tomography operator discretized in the wavelet domain, D is the diagonal approximation of C_ϕ^{-1} and α is a regularization parameter.

The operator A has a more favorable structure in a finite element domain. There, continuous piecewise bilinear functions are utilized to represent layers and wavefronts. We utilize the domain of subapertures at the pupil of the telescope Ω defined by (2.7) to define the piecewise bilinear wavefront functions. The domain for the turbulence layers Ω_ℓ , as given in (5.8) and (5.7), is used to define the piecewise bilinear layer functions. This mesh consists of 2^{2J_ℓ} points, where J_ℓ denotes the number of wavelet scales. See Figure 5.1 for a graphical representation of Ω and Ω_ℓ .

The relation between the finite element discretization of the layers and the wavelet discretization is given by the DWT W ; see Section 4.2.1; via

$$c_\ell = \delta_\ell W \phi_\ell$$

Figure 5.1. Square grid of layers Ω_ℓ in black with $2^{2J_\ell} = 2^4$ points and equidistant spacing. Projected grid of subapertures Ω in red with $n_s^2 = 16$ subapertures.

and

$$\phi_\ell = \delta_\ell^{-1} W^{-1} c_\ell,$$

where δ_ℓ is a scaling constant at layer ℓ .

In general, the layer grid and the projected grid will not align, as shown in Figure 5.1. Thus, the incoming wavefront at a layer ℓ in direction g is given by a bilinear interpolation. In fact, the nodal values of layers ϕ_ℓ on Ω_ℓ are projected onto the domains $\Omega_{g\ell}^{NGS}$ and $\Omega_{g\ell}^{LGS}$ in the direction $\theta_g = (\theta_g^x, \theta_g^y, 1)$ of the guide start g . The bilinear interpolation can be defined via two linear interpolations, one into x - and one into y -direction. We denote by

$$I(x; a, b, f(a), f(b)) := \frac{f(b) - f(a)}{b - a}(x - a) + f(a)$$

the linear interpolation at a point $x \in [a, b]$. We fix now a layer ℓ , a direction g and a point $x = (x_i, x_j)$ with $1 \leq i, j \leq n_s$ on the grid of subapertures Ω . The projected point onto Ω_ℓ in a NGS direction is given by

$$(x, y) = (x_i, x_j) + (\theta_g^x, \theta_g^y) h_\ell$$

and for a LGS direction by

$$(x, y) = \left(1 - \frac{h_\ell}{H}\right) (x_i, x_j) + (\theta_g^x, \theta_g^y) h_\ell.$$

We define the bilinear interpolation of ϕ_ℓ onto the point (x, y) for either a LGS or NGS direction by

$$P_{g\ell} \phi_\ell := I(y; y_q, y_{q+1}, t_1, t_2),$$

where t_1 and t_2 are intermediate points given via a interpolation into the x -direction by

$$\begin{aligned} t_1 &= I(x; x_p, x_{p+1}, \phi_{\ell,p,q}, \phi_{\ell,p+1,q}), \\ t_2 &= I(x; x_p, x_{p+1}, \phi_{\ell,p,q+1}, \phi_{\ell,p+1,q+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, a incoming wavefront at a subaperture corner point (i, j) for $1 \leq i, j \leq n_s$ towards a LGS or NGS direction is given by the sum of all interpolation operations through all turbulence layers by

$$\varphi_{g,ij} := \sum_{\ell=1}^L (P_{gl}^{LGS} \phi_{\ell})_{ij}$$

$$\varphi_{g,ij} := \sum_{\ell=1}^L (P_{gl}^{NGS} \phi_{\ell})_{ij},$$

respectively.

Dual domain discretization

By combining those finite element and wavelet representations we obtain the *dual domain discretization* of the atmospheric tomography problem by

$$(\mathbf{W}^{-T} \hat{A}^T \hat{C}_{\eta}^{-1} \hat{A} \mathbf{W}^{-1} + \alpha D) c = \mathbf{W}^{-T} \hat{A}^T \hat{C}_{\eta}^{-1} s, \quad (5.10)$$

where \hat{A} is discretized in the bilinear domain and $\mathbf{W} = \text{diag}(\delta_1^{-1} W, \dots, \delta_L^{-1} W)$ is the DWT. Note that from now on we omit the bold notation and simply write W for the DWT. Since we are dealing with an approximation of C_{ϕ}^{-1} we utilize a scalar factor α for tuning the balance between the fitting and the regularizing term; see [112]. The vector c is composed into all wavelet coefficients of all turbulence layers and the vector s includes all SH sensor measurements from all guide star directions. Equation (5.10) is the discretization of (5.3), i.e., the operators are now matrices.

For the sake of simplicity, we define the left-hand side operator of Equation (5.11) by

$$M := (W^{-T} \hat{A}^T \tilde{C}_{\eta}^{-1} \hat{A} W^{-1} + \alpha D) \quad (5.11)$$

and the right-hand side as

$$b := W^{-T} \hat{A}^T \tilde{C}_{\eta}^{-1} s.$$

As proposed for FEWA in [25] we use Daubechies $N = 3$ wavelets for our numerical simulations. The wavelet family is orthogonal with compact support. Since the matrix M is symmetric and positive definite Equation (5.10) can be solved using the PCG Algorithm 2. To reduce the number of PCG iterations, we utilize a Jacobi preconditioner with a different weighting of the high and low frequency regimes; for details see [24]. The PCG is started with an initial guess obtained from the previous time step, which we refer to as warm restart.

The algorithm

The wavelet reconstructor is outlined in Algorithm 4. The main input of FEWHA is the measurement vector s and the output are the mirror commands $a^{(i+1)}$. We denote by the superscript indices $(i-1)$, (i) and $(i+1)$ the previous, the current and the next time step. The superscript indices $(i-1, i)$ and $(i, i+1)$ denote the measurements in between. Within FEWHA a two-step delay is used, i.e., the new mirror shapes $a^{(i)}$ are determined from the reconstruction based on the measurements $s^{(i-1, i)}$ and from the previous mirror shapes $a^{(i)}$. For simplicity we write s instead of $s^{(i-1, i)}$. The measurements $s^{(i, i+1)}$ are not available at time Step i . For details we refer to Section 2.6.

If the AO system is running in open loop, the measurements are obtained directly from the wavefronts. If closed loop control is applied, the DMs correct the wavefront before the measurements are obtained. In this case the so called pseudo open loop measurements, see Equation 2.16, are computed in a first step of Algorithm 4 in Line 4. These measurements are calculated as the sum of the actual residuals s (stemming from the WFSs) and the simulated SH measurements through the DMs $\Gamma a^{(i-1)}$. Hence, the measurements correspond to the residuals of the corrected wavefront after the DM correction. Due to the two-step delay, the DM shape from the previous step is used.

In Line 6 the right-hand side $b^{(i)}$ is computed with the new measurement vector s and, subsequently, the residual vector \bar{r} is updated in Line 7. The atmospheric tomography takes place in Line 8, i.e., the new wavelet coefficients are calculated using the PCG algorithm. In Line 9 the inverse DWT together with a fitting operator are applied to obtain the mirror commands \tilde{a} . In Lines 11 and 13 the closed or open loop control is performed. Here the new DM shapes are calculated as the linear combination of the current and the reconstructed DM shapes. A scalar weight, denoted gain, is used to balance between those terms. This factor has a value between zero and one. Such a gain control stabilizes the reconstruction. For a closed loop control, the artificially added DM shapes have to be removed. The term $(\tilde{a} - a^{(i-1)})$ corresponds to the reconstruction from the closed loop measurements.

5.4 Direct versus iterative methods

In the following we discuss the benefits and drawbacks of direct and iterative approaches for solving the atmospheric tomography problem. Direct methods have been, historically, the only approaches considered for a long time. Recently, research has been shifted more into the direction of iterative methods, mainly motivated by the computational load of ELTs.

Algorithm 4 FEWHA reconstructor

```

1: Input:     $s = (s_g)_{g=1}^G$  (measurement vector)
              gain (scalar weight)
               $J^{-1}$  (Jacobi preconditioner)
               $c^{(i)}$  (previous wavelet coefficients)
               $b^{(i)}$  (previous right-hand side)
               $r^{(i)}$  (previous residual vector)
               $a^{(i-1)}, a^{(i)}$  (previous two DM shapes)
              maxIter (number of PCG iterations)
2: Output:   $a^{(i+1)}$  (next DM shape)
3: if loop = closed then
4:    $s = s + \Gamma a^{(i-1)}$ 
5: end if

6:  $b^{(i+1)} = W^{-T} A^T C_\eta^{-1} s$ 
7:  $\bar{r} = b^{(i+1)} - M c^{(i)} = (b^{(i+1)} - b^{(i)}) + r^{(i)}$ 

8:  $(c^{(i+1)}, r^{(i+1)}) = \text{PCG}(M, J^{-1}, c^{(i)}, \bar{r}, \text{maxIter})$ 

9:  $\tilde{a} = F W^{-1} c^{(i+1)}$ 

10: if loop = closed then
11:    $a^{(i+1)} = a^{(i)} + \text{gain} \cdot (\tilde{a} - a^{(i-1)})$ 
12: else if loop = open then
13:    $a^{(i+1)} = (1 - \text{gain}) \cdot a^{(i)} + \text{gain} \cdot \tilde{a}$ 
14: end if

```

Direct solvers have been used in the context of atmospheric tomography since the beginning. They are convenient to use and the motivation in the community of AO to switch to other approaches is low. Moreover, they are easy to implement, its applications is well parallelizable and pipelineable. However, they have some non negligible drawbacks. First of all, the problem dimension for ELTs is extremely high, which leads to a very large matrix. Saving one big matrix is memory consuming and it is very demanding to compute the generalized inverse and to perform a matrix-vector multiplication. Fulfilling the real-time requirements of ELTs is only possible with very expensive hardware and a clever combination of parallelization and pipelining. Moreover, if certain parameters at the telescope or in the atmosphere change, the huge matrix has to be reassembled.

Iterative methods became of interest, because they can considerably reduce the computational load. Within atmospheric tomography they all rely on a discretization scheme that leads to sparse matrices. These sparse matrices can be efficiently implemented using matrix-free representations. This does not only reduce the computational load and memory consumption, but enables to easily update parameters on the fly. Because of their more complex structure, they have the drawback that parallelization and pipelining are more complicated.

With this work, we want to point out the benefits of iterative approaches for atmospheric tomography. In the community it is often criticized that iterative approaches are hard to implement on AO real-time systems. In this thesis, we show that an efficient implementation of FEWHA and an augmented version of the algorithm on real-time hardware architectures is possible. In particular, the upcoming chapters provide a detailed analysis of FEWHA regarding its computational performance using CPUs and GPUs. For details on the hardware architectures we refer to Section 3.1. Moreover, we provide an extension of FEWHA using an augmented Krylov subspace approach in order to decrease the number of PCG iterations.

Chapter 6

An augmented wavelet method for atmospheric tomography

In the following, we present our optimized, iterative method called augmented FEWHA for solving the atmospheric tomography problem in (4.15). Our algorithm is based on FEWHA, see Section 5.3.3 for details, but in addition reuses information from previous time steps. The warm restart, i.e., using the solution from the previous loop iteration as initial guess for the next one, is already a common procedure for iterative solvers in AO. We extend this concept by additionally reusing the search directions from the PCG method. The combination of the dual domain discretization of FEWHA, the frequency dependent preconditioner, proposed in [24], and the augmented Krylov subspace method described in Section 4.3.5 lead to a very fast solver for the atmospheric tomography problem. The sparse matrices obtained by the discretization in either the wavelet or finite element domain can be efficiently implemented by utilizing matrix-free representations. This decreases the number of floating point operations and the memory usage. For a detailed performance analysis of the algorithm as well as details regarding the implementation on real-time hardware architectures we refer to the upcoming chapters. The content of this chapter mainly follows our paper in [44] titled "An augmented wavelet reconstructor for atmospheric tomography".

6.1 General approach

FEWHA and its augmented version can be applied to various AO systems. We focus here on the three systems LTAO, MOAO and MCAO. All of them utilize information from various WFSs locked on multiple guide stars to tomographically estimate the atmospheric wavefront distortions. Classical AO systems, which utilize only one guide

star, achieve high imaging quality for scientific objects of interest located near this guide star. However, the turbulence within the atmosphere is time and space dependent. As the distance to this guide star increases, the image quality suffers. Often there are not enough bright guide stars available close to a scientific object of interest, hence, AO systems that achieve correction over a large field are required. In the following, we briefly point out the main differences between the three systems LTAO, MOAO and MCAO.

LTAO uses one ground DM in combination with several LGS and NGS for the tomographic reconstruction. This ground DM corrects into one direction of interest within the FoV, in which no guide star is available. The LTAO system is operating in closed loop, i.e., the residuals are obtained from the DM into all guide star directions. The MOAO system is very similar, but uses M mirrors to correct for different directions of interest within the FoV, simultaneously. In contrast, the MCAO system uses several DMs together with various LGS and NGS to obtain a uniform correction over the whole FoV. The DMs are conjugated to different altitudes. Before the WFS measures the wavefronts, the DMs corrections are applied, hence, the MCAO system is operating in closed loop.

FEWHA and its augmented version are so called two-step approaches. Such methods first perform the atmospheric reconstruction, and, subsequently fit the mirror shapes to the reconstructed atmosphere in order to obtain the actuator commands for deforming the adaptive mirror. Within augmented FEWHA we solve the atmospheric tomography problem on L turbulent layers utilizing the Jacobi preconditioned augmented PCG method and, subsequently, perform the mirror fitting depending on the AO system. For approaches that do not split the calculation, like the MVM method, the control matrix has to be recalculated constantly, e.g., for different guide stars or varying atmospheric conditions. Moreover, as the telescope size increases direct methods, which scale with $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$, become extremely demanding. Beside (augmented) FEWHA, many other approaches have been developed using the two-step scheme; see e.g. [8, 12, 14, 17, 102, 106, 108, 113]. Most of them still rely on the formulation of the forward problem as a matrix equation, which implies frequent reassembling of the matrix during the observation of a scientific object. FEWHA overcomes this limitation and allows to represent the atmospheric tomography problem without using a matrix formulation.

6.1.1 The algorithm

The general structure of the augmented wavelet reconstructor for one time step $(i + 1)$ is outlined in Algorithm 5. The difference to FEWHA, as proposed in [23], lies in the tomographic reconstruction, performed via an augmented conjugate gradient method preconditioned with a Jacobi preconditioner $J = J^{-1/2}J^{-1/2}$.

The input parameters of the algorithm are: the measurement vector $s^{(i+1)}$, corresponding

Algorithm 5 Augmented wavelet reconstructor

```

1: Input:    $s^{(i+1)} = (s_g)_{g=1}^G$  (measurement vector)
              gain (scalar weight)
               $c^{(i)}$  (previous wavelet coefficients)
               $b^{(i)}$  (previous right-hand side)
               $r^{(i)}$  (previous residual vector)
               $a^{(i-1)}, a^{(i)}$  (previous two DM shape)
               $maxIter$  (number of PCG iterations)
               $J^{-1/2}$  (Jacobi preconditioner)
               $P^{(i)}, Q^{(i)}$  (previous descent directions)
2: Output:  $a^{(i+1)}$  (next DM shape)
3: if loop = closed then
4:    $s^{(i+1)} = s^{(i+1)} + \Gamma a^{(i-1)}$ 
5: end if
6:  $b^{(i+1)} = W^{-T} \hat{A}^T \hat{C}_\eta^{-1} s^{(i+1)}$ 
7:  $r_0 = b^{(i+1)} - M c^{(i)} = (b^{(i+1)} - b^{(i)}) + r^{(i)}$ 
8:  $[c^{(i+1)}, r^{(i+1)}, P^{(i+1)}, Q^{(i+1)}] = augPCG(M, J^{-1/2}, P^{(i)}, Q^{(i)}, c^{(i)}, r_0, maxIter)$ 
9:  $\tilde{a} = FW^{-1} c^{(i+1)}$ 
10: if loop = closed then
11:    $a^{(i+1)} = a^{(i)} + gain \cdot (\tilde{a} - a^{(i-1)})$ 
12: else if loop = open then
13:    $a^{(i+1)} = (1 - gain) \cdot a^{(i)} + gain \cdot \tilde{a}$ 
14: end if

```

either to open or closed loop measurements, the solution from the previous time step $c^{(i)}$, which acts as initial guess for the augmented PCG algorithm, and the previous right-hand side and residual $b^{(i)}$ and $r^{(i)}$, respectively. Moreover, we use the current DM shape $a^{(i)}$ in combination with the previous DM shape $a^{(i-1)}$ for applying closed loop control. In order to be able to meet the real-time requirements of ELTs the number of PCG iterations is fixed to $maxIter$ iterations. This value is determined via a detailed analysis by numerical simulations; see Chapter 8. The augmented PCG method requires the descent directions of the previous time step $P^{(i)}$ as input. To avoid unnecessary recomputations we further save M applied to these search directions and denote this matrix by $Q^{(i)}$. The output is the new vector of actuator commands $a^{(i+1)}$, used by the control scheme to deform the adaptive mirror.

An AO system can operate either in closed or in open loop. If we apply open loop control, the measurements are directly obtained from the wavefronts. In contrast, if we use a closed loop control the pseudo open loop measurements have to be calculated as a first step of the algorithm in Line 3. Due to a two-step delay; see [82] for details; we use the DM shape $a^{(i-1)}$ from time step $(i-1)$ to compute the pseudo open loop measurements $s^{(i+1)}$. The right-hand side $b^{(i+1)}$ is computed in Line 6 with the new measurement vector

$s^{(i+1)}$, and subsequently the initial residual $r_0^{(i+1)}$ is updated in Line 7. The atmospheric reconstruction takes place in Line 8, where $P^{(i)}$ and $Q^{(i)}$ are used within the augmented PCG method to decrease the number of iterations by projection. In Line 9 the layers are first transformed back from the wavelet into the finite element domain by applying the inverse DWT and then the mirror shapes \tilde{a} are fitted to reconstructed atmosphere by applying the mirror fitting operator F . This operator is different for each AO system; see Section 6.5. Closed or open loop control is applied in Lines 10 - 14. The new DM shapes are calculated as a linear combination of the current and the reconstructed DM shapes, weighted by a scalar value called *gain* $\in [0, 1]$. This gain control improves the stability of the reconstruction. For closed loop control the artificially added DM shapes $a^{(i-1)}$ are subtracted from the computed mirror shapes \tilde{a} .

In the upcoming sections we focus on several parts of the algorithm in more detail. This includes the pseudo open loop data computation, the tip-tilt correction and the mirror fitting step for different AO systems. We provide a detailed description of the augmentation approach for performing the tomographic estimation of the 3D atmospheric wavefront distortion. Moreover, we show how our algorithm deals with the temporal delay introduced within an AO system, i.e., the time between the measurements are obtained and the correction is applied.

6.2 Pseudo open loop data

For each AO system the pseudo open loop data is generated in a different way, i.e., the operator Γ in Line 3 of Algorithm 5 has a different shape. Within an LTAO system G guide stars together with a single DM are used for correction. Hence, the operator Γ is of the form

$$\Gamma = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma_1 \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma_G \end{pmatrix}.$$

If all WFSs have the same geometry, i.e., $\bar{\Gamma} := \Gamma_1 = \dots = \Gamma_G$, the operator needs to be applied only once and is then copied for each direction

$$\Gamma = \begin{pmatrix} I \\ \vdots \\ I \end{pmatrix} \bar{\Gamma},$$

which is computationally beneficial. Here I denotes the identity matrix.

In case of an MCAO system, M mirrors are used that are conjugated to different altitudes $0 \leq h_1 < \dots < h_M$. The structure of the operator Γ , which creates SH WFS

measurements through the DMs, is similar to the atmospheric tomography operator in (5.3.3) and given by

$$\Gamma = \begin{pmatrix} \Gamma_1 & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \Gamma_G \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{P}_{11}^{LGS} & \cdots & \bar{P}_{1M}^{LGS} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \bar{P}_{G1}^{NGS} & \cdots & \bar{P}_{GM}^{NGS} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The first operator projects the wavefront through the M mirrors towards the direction of an LGS and NGS, respectively, whereas the second operator simulates the WFS. For the projection into an LGS direction, the cone effect is taken into account. Note that the MOAO system is running in open loop. Thus, the computation of pseudo open loop measurements is not necessary.

6.3 Tip-tilt correction

LGSs introduce a tip-tilt uncertainty, which has to be corrected in order to achieve a good correction; see Section 2.4.1. There are several ways on how to deal with this phenomenon, e.g., noise-weighted methods as proposed in [12, 107] or split tomography as shown in [14]. For the classical FEWHA the incorrect tip-tilt component is removed directly in Equation (5.10). Numerical simulations show that this procedure achieves the best reconstruction quality for augmented FEWHA as well.

Let us denote by \mathcal{M} the SH WFS mask associated to an LGS. We define the two tip-tilt measurement vectors of dimension $2|\mathcal{M}|$ by

$$t^x = (e \ \mathbf{0})^T \quad t^y = (\mathbf{0} \ e)^T,$$

where $e = (1, \dots, 1)^T$ denotes a vector of ones and $\mathbf{0}$ a vector of zeros, both of dimension $|\mathcal{M}|$. The tip-tilt projection operator T is then given by

$$T = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{M}|} (t^x \ t^y)(t^x \ t^y)^T.$$

In order to remove the incorrect tip-tilt we apply operator T to the inverse noise covariance matrix C_η . In fact, C_η is modified for each LGS direction $g = 1, \dots, G_{LGS}$ to

$$\hat{C}_g^{-1} = (I - T)\tilde{C}_g^{-1}(I - T),$$

where I is the identity matrix and the operator T applies an orthonormal projection into the measurement space of tilt and tilt. The noise covariance matrix is given by

$$\hat{C}_\eta = \text{diag}(\hat{C}_1, \dots, \hat{C}_{G_{LGS}}, \tilde{C}_{G_{LGS}+1}, \dots, \tilde{C}_{G_{NGS}}),$$

where \tilde{C}_g denotes the noise covariance matrix for an NGS direction g . Altogether, Equation (5.10) is modified to

$$(W^{-T}\hat{A}^T\hat{C}_\eta^{-1}\hat{A}W^{-1} + \alpha D)c = W^{-T}\hat{A}^T\hat{C}_\eta^{-1}s. \quad (6.1)$$

6.4 Atmospheric tomography

For the classical FEWHA the atmospheric tomography problem is solved using the PCG method; see [23]. Since the PCG method is an iterative solver, we need to reapply it for every single time step. This is costly in terms of computational speed compared to a direct solver, where the factorization can be reused independently of the right-hand side as long as the left-hand side matrix does not change. We extended the classical PCG method with an augmented Krylov subspace method, see Section 4.3.5, in order to decrease the number of PCG iterations. The basic idea here is to speed up the convergence of the current time step by reusing the search directions obtained when solving the system with the PCG method for the previous system.

Within the control of an AO system we are dealing with several right-hand sides, corresponding to different WFS measurements, available consecutively in every time step $i = 1, 2, \dots$ by

$$A\phi^{(i)} = s^{(i)}.$$

We use the dual domain discretization approach from Section 5.3.3 and obtain the following formulation of the atmospheric tomography problem for several time steps.

Problem 1. *The dual domain discretization of the atmospheric tomography problem for several time steps $i = 1, 2, \dots$ is defined by*

$$Mc^{(i)} = b^{(i)}, \quad (6.2)$$

where M is given by (5.11) and the right-hand is defined by

$$b^{(i)} := W^{-T}\hat{A}^T\hat{C}_\eta^{-1}s^{(i)}. \quad (6.3)$$

We use an augmented Krylov subspace method, as described in Section 4.3.5 to improve the convergence behavior of the algorithm. As a first step we improve the initial guess c_0 by a Galerkin projection technique. The corresponding initial residual r_0 is chosen orthogonally to the Krylov subspace $\mathcal{K}_m(M, r_0^{(i)})$, i.e., the condition

$$(P_m^{(i)})^T r_0^{(i+1)} = 0, \quad (6.4)$$

has to be fulfilled, where $P_m^{(i)} := (p_0^{(i)}, \dots, p_m^{(i)})$ denotes the matrix of conjugate search directions for time step (i) .

Theorem 9. Let c_0 denote the initial guess and $r_0 = b^{(i+1)} - Mc_0$ the corresponding initial residual. Further, assume that we have already solved the problem $Mc^{(i)} = b^{(i)}$ for the previous time step (i) with m PCG iterations. To enforce the orthogonality condition (6.4) we must choose

$$c_0^{(i+1)} = c_0 + P_m^{(i)} D_m^{-1} (P_m^{(i)})^T r_0. \quad (6.5)$$

and the initial residual as

$$r_0^{(i+1)} = b^{(i+1)} - Mc_0^{(i+1)} = H_m^T r_0, \quad (6.6)$$

with $H_m = I - P_m^{(i)} D_m^{-1} (MP_m^{(i)})^T$ and $D_m = (P_m^{(i)})^T MP_m^{(i)}$.

Proof. Using Theorem 6 for $Mc^{(i+1)} = b^{(i+1)}$ with $i = 1$ and $W_m := P_m^{(i)}$ immediately proves the desired result. \square

To further improve the convergence behavior we keep the orthogonality of the residual vectors with respect to the Krylov subspace throughout the iterations of the PCG method, see Section 4.3.5 for more details. This projection is defined by conditions (4.40)-(4.42). The augmented PCG method used within FEWHA is shown in Algorithm 6.

Theorem 10. Algorithm 6 is a realization of the augmented PCG method, i.e., the initial guess $c_0^{(i+1)}$ and the initial residual $r_0^{(i+1)}$ are chosen according to Theorem 9 and the conditions (4.40) - (4.42) are fulfilled.

Proof. Since Algorithm 6 is just a special form of Algorithm 3 the result follows with Theorem 7. \square

6.4.1 Preconditioning

We use here a modified Jacobi preconditioner in which the low and high frequencies are weighted differently; see [24]. The classical Jacobi preconditioner is a diagonal matrix given by $J = \text{diag}(M)$, hence, very easy to invert and efficient to apply. We use a slightly modified form, where J is given by

$$J = \text{diag}((W^{-T} \hat{A}^T \hat{C}_\eta^{-1} \hat{A} W^{-1}) + \alpha \max(D, \tau I)), \quad (6.7)$$

where I denotes the identity matrix, τ is a non-negative scalar factor and D is the approximation of the covariance matrix of layers C_ϕ . The maximum value of the two matrices is taken component wise. The benefit of a Jacobi preconditioner is the reduction of CG iterations and an increased stability and robustness of the method. However, a

Algorithm 6 Augmented PCG Algorithm for $Mc^{(i)} = b^{(i)}$

1: **Input:** c_0, r_0 (previous wavelet coefficients)
 $maxIter$ (number of PCG iterations)
 J^{-1} (preconditioner)
 M (left-hand side matrix given by Equation (5.11))
 $P_m^{(i)}$ (matrix of previous descent directions)
 $Q_m^{(i)}$ (M applied to the previous descent directions)

2: **Output:** $c^{(i+1)}, r^{(i+1)}$ (new wavelet coefficients and residual)
 $P^{(i+1)}$ (matrix of new descent directions after $maxIter$ iterations)
 $Q^{(i+1)}$ (M applied to the matrix of new descent directions)

3: **for** $j = 0, \dots, m$ **do**
4: $\sigma_j = (r_0, p_j^{(i)}) / (p_j^{(i)}, q_j^{(i)})$
5: $c_0 = c_0 + \sigma_j p_j^{(i)}, r_0 = r_0 - \sigma_j q_j^{(i)}$
6: **end for**

7: $z_0 = J^{-1} r_0$
8: **for** $j = 0, \dots, m$ **do**
9: $z_0 = z_0 - (z_0, q_j^{(i)}) / (p_j^{(i)}, q_j^{(i)})$
10: **end for**

11: $p_0^{(i+1)} = z_0$
12: **for** $k = 0, \dots, maxIter$ **do**
13: $q_k^{(i+1)} = M p_k^{(i+1)}$
14: $\alpha_k = (r_k^{(i)}, z_k) / (p_k^{(i+1)}, q_k^{(i+1)})$
15: $x_{k+1} = x_k + \alpha_k p_k^{(i+1)}, r_{k+1} = r_k - \alpha_k q_k^{(i+1)}$
16: $z_{k+1} = J^{-1} r_{k+1}$
17: $\mu_k = (z_{k+1}, q_m^{(i)}) / (p_m^{(i)}, p_m^{(i)})$
18: $z_{k+1} = z_{k+1} - \mu_k p_m^{(i)}$
19: $\beta_k = (r_{k+1}^{(i)}, z_{k+1}) / (r_k^{(i)}, z_k)$
20: $p_{k+1}^{(i+1)} = z_{k+1} + \beta_k p_k^{(i+1)}$
21: **end for**

22: $c^{(i+1)} = c_{k+1}, r^{(i+1)} = r_{k+1}$

standard Jacobi preconditioner dampens the high scales too much in comparison to the lower ones. The high and low wavelet scales are related to high and low frequency regimes of the atmospheric layers. The elements inside the matrix D are increasing very fast with these scales. Hence, we need a way to balance the level of damping for the classical Jacobi preconditioner. This is the reason for introducing the parameter τ . If we choose $\tau = 0$ we arrive at the standard Jacobi preconditioner, whereas for a very large τ the term τI dominates. In Chapter 8 we analyse the influence of the parameter τ on the quality of augmented FEWHA.

For the computation of J we need the diagonal entries of the left-hand side matrix M , given by Equation (5.11). Computing the explicit form of M is computationally very demanding, since it involves several matrix-matrix multiplications. However, for our test configuration; see Section 7; the update time for M is fixed to 6 minutes. Hence, we precompute J and reuse it for the forthcoming time steps, in which only the right-hand side $b^{(i)}$ changes. Note that the memory required to store J is quite low as it is a diagonal matrix. Inside the augmented PCG method the dense matrix M is never used explicitly. Instead, the sparse matrices are applied implemented a matrix-free way.

The tomographic reconstruction in Line 8 of Algorithm 5 is performed via an augmented PCG method with $maxIter$ iterations. The initial residual r_0 is calculated in Line 7 using the new and previous right-hand side $b^{(i+1)}$ and $b^{(i)}$, respectively, together with the previous residual $r^{(i)}$. We utilize the solution from the previous time step $c^{(i)}$ as initial guess for the augmented PCG method of the next one, often referred to as warm restart.

6.4.2 Convergence analysis

The aim of preconditioning and the augmentation approach is to improve the convergence behavior of the PCG method. Thus, we list in the following some quantities that influence the error in iteration k . These quantities are mainly based on the eigenvalue distribution and eigenvectors of the left-hand side matrix. In subsequent chapters we will utilize these quantities in order to determine if the augmented Krylov subspace method positively influences the convergence behavior for our specific test configuration.

We start with a theorem that connects the classical CG method with the augmented PCG method.

Theorem 11. *The augmented PCG method as shown in Algorithm 6 is a classical CG method preconditioned by the symmetric semidefinite preconditioner HH^T and J^{-1} , where H is given by (4.31) and J^{-1} by (6.7).*

Proof. We use a result from [27]. There it is shown that the augmented CG method

is a classical CG method applied to the matrix $H^T M H$. Hence, the augmented PCG method in Algorithm 6 is a classical CG method applied to $H^T J^{-1/2} M J^{-1/2} H$, which proofs the desired result. \square

We utilize this theorem to calculate an asymptotic error bound for the augmented PCG method at a certain iteration k by applying the well-known theory of convergence rates from the classical method.

Theorem 12. *Let κ be the condition number of $\bar{M} := H^T J^{-1/2} M J^{-1/2} H$. Then the error bound in time step $(i + 1)$ of Algorithm 6 for the augmented PCG at iteration k is given by*

$$\left\| c_k^{(i+1)} - c^{(i+1)} \right\|_{\bar{M}} \leq 2 \left\| c_0^{(i+1)} - c^{(i+1)} \right\|_{\bar{M}} \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa} + 1} \right)^k. \quad (6.8)$$

The asymptotic convergence rate of the augmented PCG method as shown in Algorithm 6 is less or equal to the asymptotic convergence rate of the classical PCG.

Proof. Since Theorem 11 implies that the augmented PCG method is a classical CG method we can use available error bounds, see e.g. [114], which immediately proves Equation (6.8). Let κ_1 denote the condition number of $J^{-1/2} M J^{-1/2}$ and κ_2 the condition number of $H^T J^{-1/2} M J^{-1/2} H$. It follows from [27] that $\kappa_1 \leq \kappa_2$, which concludes the proof. \square

The upper bound in Theorem 12 is far from sharp. The next theorem provides a tool for analyzing the convergence behavior in more detail.

Theorem 13. *The rate of convergence for the augmented PCG method in time step $(i + 1)$ of Algorithm 5 is influenced by the eigenvalue distribution of the left-hand side matrix $\bar{M} := H^T J^{-1/2} M J^{-1/2} H$ and the decomposition of the initial residual $r_0^{(i+1)}$, defined in Theorem 9, with respect to the eigenvectors.*

Proof. The approximate solution $c_k^{(i+1)}$ in iteration k has a non-linear relation to the initial value $c_0^{(i+1)}$; see [115]. Let P_k denote the space of polynomials with degree at most k . Then there exists a polynomial $q \in P_k$ with $q(0) = 1$ that fulfills

$$c_k^{(i+1)} - c^{(i+1)} = q(\bar{M})(c_0^{(i+1)} - c^{(i+1)}) \quad \text{and} \quad r_k^{(i+1)} = q(\bar{M})r_0^{(i+1)}.$$

It is shown, e.g., in [115], that

$$\left\| c_k^{(i+1)} - c^{(i+1)} \right\|_{\bar{M}}^2 = \min_{q \in P_k, q(0)=1} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{(u_j, r_0^{(i+1)})^2}{\lambda_j} q(\lambda_j)^2, \quad (6.9)$$

where u_j is the j -th eigenvector of \overline{M} and λ_j the corresponding eigenvalue. We assume $\lambda_j \geq \lambda_i$ for $j < i$. As a consequence, the rate of convergence of the CG method, and in that sense also for augmented PCG, is influenced by the eigenvalue distribution of the left-hand side matrix and the decomposition of the initial residual with respect to the eigenvectors. \square

We conclude that clustering of the eigenvalues is important. If the value of q in (6.9) is small for a specific λ_j , then by continuity of the polynomial we know that the value is small at all eigenvalues clustered around λ_j . Note that the Jacobi preconditioning improves the structure of the matrix in the sense that all diagonal elements become 1; see [116]; which implies that all Gerschgorin discs are centered around 1. By Gerschgorin's circle theorem [117] we know that all the eigenvalues are contained in at least one of these discs. However, we do not have any information about the radius of the discs. In Chapter 8.1.1 we analyze the eigenvalue distribution and the structure of the initial residual with respect to the eigenvectors of the left-hand side matrix in detail for the test configuration of MAORY.

6.5 Mirror fitting

Mirror fitting is the second step after atmospheric tomography in the so called two-step approaches, in which the shapes of the mirrors are fitted to the reconstructed atmosphere. For FEWHA and augmented FEWHA the mirror fitting step coincides. For each AO system mirror fitting is performed differently, however, the general form (see Line 9 of the algorithm) is the same. First the inverse DWT is applied to transform the layers into the bilinear domain and afterwards the actuator commands, which we model as continuous piecewise bilinear functions, are determined using the projection operator F . Altogether, we obtain

$$a^{(i+1)} = FW^{-1}c^{(i+1)},$$

where W^{-1} is the inverse wavelet transform, F is the fitting operator, $c^{(i+1)} = (c_\ell)_{\ell=1}^L$ is the vector of wavelet coefficients at time step $(i+1)$ and $a^{(i+1)} = (a_m)_{m=1}^M$ denotes the vector of new mirror shapes. In the following theorems we define the fitting operator F for the AO system LTAO, MOAO and MCAO. For more details we refer to [18, 80].

Theorem 14 (Mirror fitting LTAO). *For an LTAO system we obtain the actuator commands in time step $(i+1)$ of Algorithm 5 by*

$$a^{(i+1)} = (a_1) = (\bar{P}_{\theta_1,1}^{NGS} \cdots \bar{P}_{\theta_1,L}^{NGS}) \begin{pmatrix} \delta_1^{-1}W^{-1} & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \delta_L^{-1}W^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^{(i+1)} \\ \vdots \\ c_L^{(i+1)} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $\bar{P}_{\theta_1, \ell}^{NGS}$ is a bilinear interpolation on layer $\ell = 1, \dots, L$ towards the direction θ_1 . The mirror fitting operator is given by $F = (\bar{P}_{\theta_1, \ell}^{NGS})_{\ell=1}^L$.

Proof. For an LTAO system the mirror is optimized towards a certain direction of interest, which we denote by θ_1 . The fitting step is a projection through the reconstructed layers towards the direction θ_1 . Since we model the actuator commands by bilinear functions, the projection is given by a bilinear interpolation $\bar{P}_{\theta_m, \ell}^{NGS}$ on layer $\ell = 1, \dots, L$ towards the direction θ_1 , which proves the result. \square

Theorem 15 (Mirror fitting MOAO). *For an MOAO system with M mirrors we obtain the actuator commands in time step $(i + 1)$ of Algorithm 5 by*

$$a^{(i+1)} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_M \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{P}_{\theta_1, 1}^{NGS} & \cdots & \bar{P}_{\theta_1, L}^{NGS} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \bar{P}_{\theta_M, 1}^{NGS} & \cdots & \bar{P}_{\theta_M, L}^{NGS} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \delta_1^{-1} W^{-1} & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \delta_L^{-1} W^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^{(i+1)} \\ \vdots \\ c_L^{(i+1)} \end{pmatrix},$$

where $\bar{P}_{\theta_m, \ell}^{NGS}$ is a bilinear interpolation on layer $\ell = 1, \dots, L$ towards the direction θ_m with $m = 1, \dots, M$. The fitting operator is given by $F = (\bar{P}_{\theta_1, \ell}^{NGS})_{\ell=1}^L$.

Proof. For an MOAO system we optimize towards M directions of interest $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_M$. For each direction θ_m with $m = 1, \dots, M$ the fitting step is a projection through the reconstructed layers towards this direction. Using Theorem 14 for each direction we obtain the desired result. \square

Theorem 16 (Mirror fitting MCAO). *For an MCAO system the M mirrors are aligned at different heights $0 \leq h_1 \leq \dots \leq h_M$. In case of $L = M$ layers directly located at the altitudes of the DMs the fitting operator becomes the identity. The actuator commands in time step $(i + 1)$ of Algorithm 5 are then given by*

$$a^{(i+1)} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_M \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \delta_1^{-1} W^{-1} & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \delta_L^{-1} W^{-1} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_1^{(i+1)} \\ \vdots \\ c_L^{(i+1)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

If we reconstruct more layers than DMs, i.e., $L > M$, the actuator commands are given by the solution of the system

$$\bar{P}^T P W^{-1} c^{(i+1)} = \bar{P}^T \bar{P} a. \quad (6.10)$$

Here $P = ((P_{\bar{\theta}_n, \ell}^{NGS})_{n=1}^N)_{\ell=1}^L$ denotes the matrix of projections through layer ℓ in direction $\bar{\theta}_n$ and $\bar{P} = (\bar{P}_{\bar{\theta}_n, m}^{NGS})_{n=1}^N)_{m=1}^M$ is the matrix of projections through DM m in direction $\bar{\theta}_n$. The fitting operator is then given by $F = (\bar{P}^T \bar{P})^{-1} \bar{P}^T P$.

Proof. For the MCAO system we have to distinguish between two cases; see [8]. If the number of DMs M is equal to the number of layers L and the layer heights are at the altitude of the mirrors $h_1 = \bar{h}_1, \dots, h_L = \bar{h}_M$, the mirror shapes are determined directly from the layer shapes. Since an interpolation onto the mirrors is not necessary, no fitting is required and the fitting operator becomes the identity matrix. See Figure 6.1 for a graphical illustration.

If we reconstruct more layers than DMs, i.e., $L > M$, we have to solve another minimization problem, where the cost functional is given by

$$\int_{\text{FoV}} \int_{\Omega_{\mathcal{M}}} \left\| (P_{\theta}^{NGS} \phi)(x) - (\bar{P}_{\theta}^{NGS} a)(x) \right\|^2 dx d\theta.$$

We choose N discrete directions of interest $\bar{\theta}_1, \dots, \bar{\theta}_N$, such that these directions cover the whole FoV; see Figure 6.2. We assume that the mirror is represented by a bilinear function and the layers by wavelets. Then we obtain the following discretized minimization problem

$$\min_a \left\| \begin{pmatrix} P_{\bar{\theta}_1,1}^{NGS} & \dots & P_{\bar{\theta}_1,L}^{NGS} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ P_{\bar{\theta}_N,1}^{NGS} & \dots & P_{\bar{\theta}_N,L}^{NGS} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \delta_1^{-1} W^{-1} c_1 \\ \vdots \\ \delta_L^{-1} W^{-1} c_L \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \bar{P}_{\bar{\theta}_1,1}^{NGS} & \dots & \bar{P}_{\bar{\theta}_1,M}^{NGS} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ \bar{P}_{\bar{\theta}_N,1}^{NGS} & \dots & \bar{P}_{\bar{\theta}_N,M}^{NGS} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ \vdots \\ a_M \end{pmatrix} \right\|. \quad (6.11)$$

We write (6.11) in the following form

$$\min_a \left\| PW^{-1}c - \bar{P}a \right\|.$$

As for the atmospheric tomography problem, the solution of this minimization problem is equivalent to the solution of the normal equation

$$\bar{P}^T PW^{-1}c = \bar{P}^T \bar{P}a,$$

which concludes the proof. □

For solving Problem (6.10) we choose a similar approach as for solving the atmospheric tomography problem and keep the sparsity by using an iterative solver. To improve numerical stability we introduce a factor α and solve

$$\bar{P}^T PW^{-1}c = (\bar{P}^T \bar{P} + \alpha I)a,$$

with the CG algorithm. Again this CG approach is warm restarted by using the mirror shapes $a^{(i)}$ from the previous time step. We want to stress that this is just one way to deal with mirror fitting in MCAO. Other discretization approaches or other solution methods might provide better results. However, this is not taken into account in the framework of this thesis.

Figure 6.1. MCAO mirror fitting for the case $L = M$, where the mirror shapes are determined directly from reconstructed layers.

6.6 Integrator control

Within an AO system there is a certain time delay between the moment when measurements are acquired by the WFS and the time when the DM correction is applied. These delay is commonly measured in time steps. In this thesis, we utilize a two-step delay as illustrated in Figure 2.17. Hence, the measurements taken between time step $(i - 1)$ and (i) are used for the reconstruction in the interval $[i, i + 1)$. To indicate that we are in principle applying the wrong correction we use a so called output or loop gain in the last step of Algorithm 5 as proposed in [118]. This loop gain combines the actuator commands from the previous time step $a^{(i)}$ and the current time step \tilde{a} to get the new actuator command vector $a^{(i+1)}$. In Chapter 8 we study the sensitivity of our method against this parameter.

Figure 6.2. MCAO mirror fitting for the case $M > L$, where the mirror shapes are fitted to the reconstructed layers. The crosses denote the actuator positions of the DM, whereas the dots are located on the direction of interest $\bar{\theta}_n$.

Chapter 7

Numerics: Test configuration

To validate the performance of augmented FEWHA we test our method with numerical simulations. In this chapter we define the test configuration, including the simulation environment and system as well as method specific parameters. Further, we give details on the hardware. The test setting is motivated by the instrument MAORY, which is an AO module for the ELT operating in MCAO. Moreover, we define a test configuration for a wide field of view LTAO system as well, to validate the performance of augmented FEWHA for a broader set of parameters. We refer to Chapter 2 for details on the AO systems. The hardware configuration is based on the analysis of real-time systems in Chapter 3.

The ELT will become the largest optical/near-infrared telescope in the world and will consist of two so called Nasmyth platforms on each side of the telescope. Each of these platforms hosts several instruments, one of these is MAORY. Figure 7.1 shows a 3D model of the Nasmyth platform, including the MICADO and MAORY instrument. The high angular resolution camera MICADO is a client of MAORY. MAORY requires a high quality image correction in order to perform highly accurate astrometry and photometry.

7.1 AO system configuration

We simulate a telescope that gathers light through a primary mirror with 37 m diameter, where approximately 11 % of the mirror are obstructed. The turbulence is simulated according to median seeing conditions with a Fried parameter of $r_0 = 0.157$. For the MCAO system simulation we utilize a 35 layer atmosphere as defined in Table 7.3 and for the LTAO system a 9 layer atmosphere defined in Table 7.4. For details about the configuration we refer to [120]. Our algorithm reconstructs between 3 and 9 atmospheric

Figure 7.1. Model of the ELT's Nasmyth platform with the MICADO SCAO system and MAORY NGS WFSs (green), the MAORY post focal MCAO relay bench (red) and a possible second generation instrument (blue); see [119].

layers that follow the von Karman statistics; see [53]. The performance in terms of quality is evaluated using the Strehl ratio in the K band, i.e., at a wavelength of 2200 nm. The general parameters are summarized in Table 7.2.

MAORY is operating at 500 Hz. The quality requirements are 30% Strehl ratio in the K band as a baseline and 50% as a goal. Note, that the quality requirements were already fulfilled for the classical FEWHA, however, the run-time still is an issue.

7.1.1 Deformable mirrors

The ELT optical design consists of three mirrors denoted by M1, M2 and M3 on-axis with two DMs (M4, M5) for performing the AO. Figure 7.5 illustrates the optical configuration of the ELT. The incoming light is first reflected by the primary mirror M1 and afterwards bounces off to the two 4 m mirrors M2 and M3. The two deformable mirrors M4 and the TT mirror M5 then perform the wavefront correction. For MAORY up to two additional DMs (DM1, DM2) inside the instrument and conjugated to different altitudes are used for wavefront compensation. For the numerical simulations carried out in the framework of this thesis we assume the Fried geometry with equidistant actuator spacing for the DMs; see [64].

MAORY has to provide two AO modes to support the imaging camera MICADO, namely

Parameter	Value
Telescope diameter	37 m
Central obstruction	11%
Fried parameter r_0	0.157
Na-layer height	90 km
Na-layer FWHM	11.4 km
Outer scale L_0	25 m
FoV	1 arcmin
Simulated duration	1 s
Delay	2 frames
Evaluation criterion	LE Strehl
Evaluation wavelength	K band (2200 nm)

Table 7.2. General system parameters.

MCAO and SCAO. In this thesis we focus on the MAORY MCAO mode, which has to achieve a uniform AO correction over the full MICADO FoV of 1 arcmin. The details about the DM configuration utilized within our numerical simulation are listed in Table 7.6. We use all three DMs for the MCAO simulations and only the M4 for the LTAO systems configuration.

Wavefront sensors

We simulate 6 LGS for measuring the wavefront aberrations supplemented with 3 NGS for tip-tilt correction. The laser beams are launched at the four corner points of the square $[-21 \text{ m}, 21 \text{ m}]^2$ from the side of the telescope; see Figure 7.7 for a graphical illustration. We model the sodium layer at which the LGS beam is scattered via a Gaussian random variable with mean altitude $H = 90 \text{ km}$ and FWHM of the sodium density profile of 11.4 km. To each guide star a SH WFS is assigned.

For the MCAO configuration the 6 high order SH WFSs that measure the light incoming from the LGS, consist of 74×74 subapertures, each having 10×10 pixels. The 3 low order WFSs, which are used for measuring the NGS aberrations and correcting for the tip-tilt uncertainty, consist of only 2×2 subapertures with 125×125 pixels each. The LGS are positioned in a circle of 90 arcsec diameter and the NGS in a circle of 110 arcsec

Layer	Altitude	Wind	Strength	Layer	Altitude	Wind	Strength
1	30 m	5.5 m/s	0.242	19	10500 m	32 m/s	0.013
2	90 m	5.5 m/s	0.12	20	11500 m	27 m/s	0.007
3	150 m	5.1 m/s	0.0969	21	12500 m	22 m/s	0.016
4	200 m	5.5 m/s	0.059	22	13500 m	14.5 m/s	0.0259
5	245 m	5.6 m/s	0.0473	23	14500 m	9.5 m/s	0.0191
6	300 m	5.7 m/s	0.0473	24	15500 m	6.3 m/s	0.0099
7	390 m	5.8 m/s	0.0473	25	16500 m	5.5 m/s	0.0062
8	600 m	6 m/s	0.0473	26	17500 m	6 m/s	0.004
9	1130 m	6.5 m/s	0.0399	27	18500 m	6.5 m/s	0.0025
10	1880 m	7 m/s	0.0324	28	19500 m	7 m/s	0.0022
11	2630 m	7.5 m/s	0.0162	29	20500 m	7.5 m/s	0.0019
12	3500 m	8.5 m/s	0.0261	30	21500 m	8 m/s	0.0014
13	4500 m	9.5 m/s	0.0156	31	22500 m	8.5 m/s	0.0011
14	5500 m	11.5 m/s	0.0104	32	23500 m	9 m/s	0.0006
15	6500 m	17.5 m/s	0.01	33	24500 m	9.5 m/s	0.0009
16	7500 m	23 m/s	0.012	34	25500 m	10 m/s	0.0005
17	8500 m	26 m/s	0.004	35	26500 m	10 m/s	0.0004
18	9500 m	29 m/s	0.014				

Table 7.3. Simulated 35 layer atmosphere for the MCAO configuration.

Layer	Altitude	Wind	Strength
1	0 m	15 m/s	0.5224
2	140 m	13 m/s	0.026
3	281 m	13 m/s	0.0444
4	562 m	9 m/s	0.116
5	1125 m	9 m/s	0.0989
6	2250 m	15 m/s	0.0295
7	4500 m	25 m/s	0.0598
8	9000 m	40 m/s	0.043
9	18000 m	21 m/s	0.06

Table 7.4. Simulated 9 layer atmosphere for the LTAO configuration.

Figure 7.5. Illustration of the 5-mirror optical system of the ELT. Before reaching the science instrument the light is first reflected by the primary mirror (M1) with 38.5 m diameter and then bounces off to the two 4 m mirrors (M2 and M3). The final two mirrors (M4 and M5) are deformable and form the built-in AO system [45].

Parameter	M4	DM1	DM2
Number of active actuators	4457	1522	2576
DM altitude	0 km	4 km	12.7 km
DM actuator spacing	0.5 m	1 m	1 m

Table 7.6. For the MCAO configuration all three DMs are used, whereas for LTAO system only the M4 is utilized for wavefront correction.

Figure 7.7. The ELT uses laser beams to generate the LGS. These LGS are used by the SH WFSs to measure the distortion of light caused by turbulences in the Earth’s atmosphere; see [45].

diameter. The quality is measured using 25 probe stars positioned in a 5×5 grid over a 1 arcmin square. The MCAO star asterism is shown in Figure 7.8. Details about the parameters can be found in Table 7.9.

The LTAO simulations in this thesis are configured to simulate a wide field of view. The 6 LGS are positioned in a circle with a 7.5 arcmin diameter. The 3 NGS are positioned in a circle of 10 arcmin diameter. In contrast to the MCAO configuration, the 6 LGS and 3 NGS are equipped with 74×74 subapertures each consisting of 10×10 pixels. The star asterism is shown in Figure 7.10. In this configuration we use a single DM (M4) for the wavefront correction. The quality for this test setting is measured at the zenith. Details about the parameters can be found in Table 7.11.

The operating wavelength λ of the WFS influences the scaling factor between the phase and the wavefront aberrations; see Equation (2.1). For the LGS the wavelength is fixed to 589 nm. For the NGS we use a wavelength of 1650 nm for the MCAO system and a wavelength of 500 nm for the LTAO system. If not indicated otherwise, all simulations are performed with noise due to spot elongation; see Section 2.4.1. Moreover, we vary the photon flux level between a few hundred photons per subaperture (low flux) and up to 10000 photons (high flux). Note that the number of photons is directly related to the noise level of the WFS. A higher number of photons corresponds to less noise. In addition to photon noise, we simulate the WFS detector read-out noise (RON). This noise is related to reading errors on the CCD, which is given in number of electrons per pixel. In all our simulations this value is fixed to 3.0.

Figure 7.8. MCAO star asterism of NGS (red) in a circle of 110 arcsec diameter and LGS (teal) in a circle of 1.5 arcmin diameter. The 5×5 quality evaluation grid over a 1 arcmin FoV is marked in gray.

Parameter	LGS-WFS	NGS-WFS
Type	SH WFS	SH WFS
Number	6	3
Geometry	74×74 subap.	2×2 subap.
GS asterism	90 arcsec diameter	110 arcsec diameter
Wavelength	589 nm	1650 nm
WFS FoV	16.8 arcsec	1.3 arcsec
Subaperture size	10×10 pixels	125×125 pixels
Detector RON	$3.0 e^-/\text{pixel}/\text{frame}$	$3.0 e^-/\text{pixel}/\text{frame}$

Table 7.9. MCAO WFS configuration for MAORY.

Figure 7.10. LTAO asterism of NGS (red) in a circle of 10 arcmin diameter and LGS (teal) in a circle of 7.5 arcmin diameter. The quality evaluation is performed at the zenith (dark gray).

Parameter	LGS-WFS	NGS-WFS
Type	SH WFS	SH WFS
Number	6	3
Geometry	74 × 74 subap.	74 × 74 subap.
GS asterism	7.5 arcmin diameter	10 arcmin diameter
Wavelength	589 nm	500 nm
WFS FoV	16.8 arcsec	16.8 arcsec
Subaperture size	10 × 10 pixels	10 × 10 pixels
Detector RON	3.0 e^- /pixel/frame	3.0 e^- /pixel/frame

Table 7.11. LTAO WFS configuration.

7.1.2 Method parameters

In Table 7.12 we list the parameters that configure our augmented FEWHA algorithm. Besides a typical value we indicate if the parameter is an offline or online parameter. One benefit of (augmented) FEWHA is that most of the parameters can be updated on the fly. We call such quantities online parameters. The offline parameters are related to the recomputation of the Jacobi preconditioner, which is precomputed and depends on the left-hand side matrix M . We indicate if the parameter value has to be either tuned, is fixed for a certain test setting or if there is a trade-off between quality and speed. Moreover, we list the sensitivity of the method with respect to the parameter, i.e., if a small deviation from the optimal value heavily influences the performance. In the following, we describe the method specific parameters in more detail. In Chapter 8 we provide a sensitivity study of augmented FEWHA against these parameter values and list the optimal parameter values for the MCAO as well as the LTAO system.

For the discretization of the atmospheric layers in the wavelet domain we use J_ℓ wavelet scales. This value induces a grid of size $2^{J_\ell} \times 2^{J_\ell}$ with equidistant spacing given by δ_ℓ . If the number of wavelet scales increases, the quality improves at the expense of higher computational costs. Thus, for this parameter, together with the scaling, a trade-off between quality and speed has to be chosen. The same applies to the number of PCG iterations `maxIter`. A higher number improves the quality, however, increases the run-time. The regularization parameter α , the spot elongation α_η , the preconditioner threshold τ and the gain are variable parameters that have to be tuned for a certain test setting and noise level. Especially, to changes in the regularization parameter α the method reacts very sensitive. The last three parameters correspond to the mirror fitting for MCAO in the case where we reconstruct more DMs than layers, i.e., $M > L$. Again the number of PCG iterations for the fitting problem is a trade-off between speed and quality.

7.1.3 System dependent parameter values

In the following, we provide the AO system specific parameter values. The reconstructed layers are configured in a different way for each AO system. Moreover, some of the parameters vary with the noise level. In Table 7.13 we list the system specific method parameters for the 9 and 3 layer configuration. Since we focus here mainly on a speed oriented set up, i.e., fulfilling the run-time requirements of the ELT, the parameters are configured in order to obtain a fast reconstruction.

For the LTAO system simulations we reconstruct 9 atmospheric layers. We assume that their position and strength is known; see Table 7.13. We utilize a grid of 128×128 points for the ground layer in order to obtain an overlap of the DM grid. For higher altitudes

Parameter	Value	Update	Comment
Number of wavelet scales J_ℓ	1 – 10	offline	trade-off
Spacing δ_ℓ	(0, 1] m	offline	trade-off
Regularization α	[0, 64]	online	tuned, sensitive
Elongation α_η	[0, 1]	offline	tuned, sensitive
Gain	(0, 1]	online	tuned
Preconditioner threshold τ	$10^0, 10^1, \dots, 10^9$	online	tuned
Num. of aug. PCG iterations	1 – 10	online	trade-off
Num. of optimization directions N	25	online	trade-off
Optimization directions $\bar{\theta}_n$	angles over FoV	online	trade-off
Num. of CG iterations for fitting	4	online	trade-off

Table 7.12. Method parameter for FEWHA and its augmented version.

we keep this number, as it is beneficial for parallelization. However, this leads to a lower resolution for the two highest layers. For FEWHA it has been demonstrated in [23] that these lower resolution for the two upper-most layers has only a marginal influence on the overall quality.

For the MCAO system simulation we reconstruct 3 atmospheric layers, such that these layers are conjugated with the DMs. The grid points and spacing is chosen according to the DM specifications. We choose the layer strength heuristically. Most of the strength is contained in the ground layer, which is verified through empirical observations. For details about the layer configuration we refer to Table 7.13. Note that if all guide stars are NGS, i.e., there is no cone effect present, and the optimization directions are chosen as the guide star directions the 3 and 9 layer configurations coincide; see [19].

7.2 Simulation environment

For all simulations in this thesis we utilize the software package OCTOPUS, which is an AO simulation tool used by the ESO; see [121, 122]. The tool was defined as the benchmark standard for evaluating reconstruction methods developed within the Austrian AO (AAO) project "Mathematical Algorithms and Software for ELT Adaptive Optics". It is programmed in C and runs fully parallel on an appropriate CPU cluster. In order to simulate the reality, i.e., the complete telescope with its components, distorted

Layer	Altitude	Strength	Scales J_ℓ	Grid points	Spacing δ_ℓ
1	0 m	0.75	7	128×128	0.5 m
2	4000 m	0.15	6	64×64	1.0 m
3	12700 m	0.1	6	64×64	1.0 m
1	0 m	0.5224	7	128×128	0.5 m
2	140 m	0.026	7	128×128	0.5 m
3	281 m	0.0444	7	128×128	0.5 m
4	562 m	0.116	7	128×128	0.5 m
5	1125 m	0.0989	7	128×128	0.5 m
6	2250 m	0.0295	7	128×128	0.5 m
7	4500 m	0.0598	7	128×128	0.5 m
8	9000 m	0.043	7	128×128	1.0 m
9	18000 m	0.06	7	128×128	1.0 m

Table 7.13. Method specific configuration for 3 (top) and 9 (bottom) reconstructed layers.

light propagation through the turbulent atmosphere and image formation on the scientific camera, OCTOPUS is using complex models. This makes the tool trustworthy and precise, however, also time and memory consuming. With OCTOPUS it is possible to simulate SCAO, LTAO, MOAO, MCAO and GLAO systems. In the following, we briefly describe how components, which are relevant for the work in this thesis, are simulated within the tool.

OCTOPUS assumes a layered structure of the turbulent atmosphere. In reality, the phase delay is time dependent, which is commonly referred to as boiling. However, within OCTOPUS the simulations are restricted to a fixed phase delay at a fixed height. Only horizontal drifts are applied with constant speed. This simplification is well justified, as the perturbations caused by the wind speed have a much higher effect on the wavefronts than boiling. The benefit is that precomputed phase delays can be used, which considerably speeds up the simulation. The calculation is based on a random number generator and the von Karman turbulence model. The SH WFS model of OCTOPUS simulates the light propagation through the lenslets via a Fourier transform, which results in an optical energy distribution on the sensor plane. The trajectories of these distributions are generated via a Poisson process, which leads to a cloud of photon impacts of the image of the guide star in every subaperture. Utilizing these images, the output of the sensor is computed by a centroiding algorithm, commonly a Weighted Center of Gravity (WCoG). Photon and read-out noise are modeled statistically. To model the DM reaction on the actuator commands, OCTOPUS is using an influence function of the DM and models the actuator response. For each DM the conjugated height has to be specified. In every time step the PSF; see Section 2.2; of the AO system

Figure 7.14. Basic functionality of OCTOPUS working with an external reconstructor; [48]. The data exchange is handled via the file system.

is computed and stored. From this data, OCTOPUS calculates quality measures such as the Strehl ratio, see Section 2.7.2, which we use to evaluate the quality of our methods. OCTOPUS is considering several error sources arising within an AO system. This includes fitting errors, temporal errors, aliasing and quantum noise. Moreover, effects caused by the LGS are taken into account, e.g., the cone effect, spot elongation and tip/tilt indetermination.

Several reconstruction methods are included into OCTOPUS, such as the standard MVM (see Section 5.2), FrIM (see Section 5.3.2) and a Fourier transform based reconstructor. However, it is easy to add new reconstruction methods as no implementation in C or recompiling OCTOPUS is necessary. This procedure is used for the simulations carried out in the framework of this thesis. New methods can simply be started in a separate process and the data transfer is handled via the file system. In fact, in every time step OCTOPUS is updating the DM shape and the atmosphere and calculates the new sensor measurements using the internal WFS model. The external reconstructor starts its calculations once the necessary files have been written by OCTOPUS. Utilizing the sensor measurements from OCTOPUS the atmospheric reconstruction is performed, the actuator commands are calculated and written to a file. OCTOPUS begins with updating the DM shapes as soon as all necessary files have been written by the external reconstructor and the procedure is starting anew. This loop is running for a fixed number of time steps. Figure 7.14 shows a graphical illustration on how OCTOPUS is working with an external reconstructor.

7.3 Hardware configuration

In general, three basic technologies are used for the real-time control of large telescopes: CPUs (Central Processing Unit), GPUs (Graphics Processing Unit), and FPGAs (Field Programmable Gate Array). In this thesis, we address the performance of augmented FEWHA on a single CPU and on an NVIDIA GPU. For the implementation on the CPU we utilize C++ 17 together with the GCC 9.2 compiler. On the NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU we use CUDA 10.1. Due to high development costs, the FPGA implementation is marked as future task.

We run the parallel CPU implementation of augmented FEWHA on Radon1, the high performance cluster of the Radon Institute for Computational and Applied Mathematics in Linz. The cluster has 1168 computing cores and 10.7 TB of memory allocated and 66 compute nodes, 4 GPU nodes and one login node, all running on CentOS Linux. For our numerical simulations we use one of these compute nodes, which is equipped with two 8-core Intel Haswell processors (Xeon E5-2630v3, 2.4Ghz) and 128 GB of memory. For the performance tests of the GPU based implementation we use a Tesla V100 GPU with CUDA 10.1. The Tesla V100 is a high-end GPU from NVIDIA optimized for deep learning and high-performance computing. Listing 7.1 shows the output of the CUDA device query sample, provided by the CUDA toolkit. This example enumerates the properties of the available CUDA devices in the system. Important parameters for performance considerations are the clock rate, the maximal number of blocks per multiprocessor, the number of CUDA cores and the maximal number of threads per multiprocessor.

```

CUDA Device Query (Runtime API) version (CUDA static linking)

Detected 1 CUDA Capable device(s)

Device 0:"Tesla V100-PCIE-32GB"
CUDA Driver Version / Runtime Version      10.1 / 10.1
CUDA Capability Major/Minor version number: 7.0
Total amount of global memory:             32480 MBytes (34058272768 bytes)
(80) Multiprocessors, ( 64) CUDA Cores/MP: 5120 CUDA Cores
GPU Max Clock rate:                        1380 Mhz (1.38 GHz)
Memory Clock rate:                         877 Mhz
Memory Bus Width:                          4096-bit
L2 Cache Size:                             6291456 bytes
Maximum Texture Dimension Size (x,y,z)     1D=(131072), 2D=(131072, 65536), 3D=(16384, 16384, 16384)
Maximum Layered 1D Texture Size, (num) layers 1D=(32768), 2048 layers
Maximum Layered 2D Texture Size, (num) layers 2D=(32768, 32768), 2048 layers
Total amount of constant memory:           65536 bytes
Total amount of shared memory per block:   49152 bytes
Total number of registers available per block: 65536
Warp size:                                 32
Maximum number of threads per multiprocessor: 2048
Maximum number of threads per block:       1024
Max dimension size of a thread block (x,y,z): (1024, 1024, 64)
Max dimension size of a grid size (x,y,z): (2147483647, 65535, 65535)
Maximum memory pitch:                      2147483647 bytes
Texture alignment:                         512 bytes
Concurrent copy and kernel execution:      Yes with 7 copy engine(s)
Run time limit on kernels:                 No
Integrated GPU sharing Host Memory:        No
Support host page-locked memory mapping:   Yes
Alignment requirement for Surfaces:        Yes
Device has ECC support:                    Enabled
Device supports Unified Addressing (UVA):  Yes
Device supports Compute Preemption:        Yes
Supports Cooperative Kernel Launch:        Yes
Supports MultiDevice Co-op Kernel Launch:  Yes
Device PCI Domain ID / Bus ID / location ID: 0 / 0 / 9

```

Listing 7.1. CUDA device query output.

Chapter 8

Numerics: Quality evaluation

This chapter is devoted to the detailed quality analysis of augmented FEWHA for the MCAO and LTAO system defined in Chapter 7. We start with an analysis of convergence rates, which involves the condition number, eigenvalue distribution and the structure of the eigenvectors of the left-hand side matrix M . Moreover, we test our method utilizing numerical simulations in OCTOPUS. For each AO system we compare our method with the classical FEWHA. Furthermore, we examine the influence of system specific and method related parameters on the quality of augmented FEWHA.

8.1 Performance for the MCAO system

We start with the standard test configuration in this thesis related to MAORY. As a benchmark for the numerical simulations we use the classical FEWHA. In [23] a detailed study of FEWHA already showed the superb quality of the algorithm compared to other approaches, such as FrIM and the MVM algorithm. The main goal of augmented FEWHA is to keep the quality of FEWHA, but with a lower number of PCG iterations in order to considerably reduce the run-time.

8.1.1 Analysis of convergence rates

As mentioned in Section 6.4.2, the convergence rate of the augmented PCG is influenced by the eigenvalue distribution of the left-hand side matrix, and in relation to that also by the condition number κ , and the structure of the initial residual with respect to the corresponding eigenvectors.

$\kappa_0 := \text{cond}(M)$	$\approx 8,2913 \cdot 10^8$
$\kappa_1 := \text{cond}(J^{-1/2}MJ^{-1/2})$	$\approx 1,2975 \cdot 10^7$
$\kappa_2 := \text{cond}(J^{-1/2}H^T MHJ^{-1/2})$	$\approx 9,8381 \cdot 10^6$

Table 8.1. Condition numbers for the left hand side matrix of FEWHA (unpreconditioned and preconditioned) and augmented FEWHA.

In the following, we analyze the condition numbers of the left-hand side matrix for FEWHA and augmented FEWHA with a flux level of 500 photons per subaperture per frame. Note that the condition number of M is influenced by the regularization parameter α , which is 0.2 for this test configuration. During our analysis we observed that a good choice of α positively influences the condition number. The number of photons and in this regard the noise level has only a marginal impact. Table 8.1 shows the condition numbers κ_0 , κ_1 and κ_2 of the unpreconditioned matrix M , the preconditioned matrix for FEWHA $J^{-1/2}MJ^{-1/2}$, and the preconditioned and projected matrix for augmented FEWHA $J^{-1/2}H^T MHJ^{-1/2}$, respectively. We observe $\kappa_0 > \kappa_1 > \kappa_2$, which also follows from Theorem 12.

This result suggests that augmented FEWHA requires less PCG iterations than the classical algorithm. However, this upper bound is far from sharp and the difference between κ_1 and κ_2 is small. Therefore, we validate the convergence behavior in more detail using Theorem 13.

Figure 8.2 illustrates the eigenvalue distribution of the unpreconditioned matrix M (red), the preconditioned matrix for FEWHA $J^{-1/2}MJ^{-1/2}$ (teal) and the left-hand side for augmented FEWHA $J^{-1/2}H^T MHJ^{-1/2}$ (dashed orange). We observe that the eigenvalues of the Jacobi preconditioned matrix (teal) are clustered around 1, which is not surprising since Jacobi preconditioning improves the structure of the matrix in the sense that all diagonal elements become 1; see [116]. This implies that all Gerschgorin discs, in which the eigenvalues are contained, are centered around 1. The projection operator H has only a marginal influence on the eigenvalue distribution, which is not visible in the graph. In fact, the eigenvalue distribution of $J^{-1/2}MJ^{-1/2}$ (teal) almost completely overlaps with that of $J^{-1/2}H^T MHJ^{-1/2}$ (dashed orange). We observe the decay of eigenvalues towards 0, a characteristic property of an ill-posed problem.

Figure 8.3 illustrates the influence of the projection, used within augmented FEWHA, in the decomposition of the initial residual with respect to the eigenvectors. The initial residual, unprojected or projected, is taken after 100 time steps. Note that the structure of the initial residual for the original FEWHA is positively influenced by the warm restart technique, i.e., using the solution of the previous time step as initial guess for the next one. The upper left graph shows the energy of the initial residual with respect to the j -th eigenvector u_j of the preconditioned matrix $J^{-1/2}MJ^{-1/2}$, corresponding to FEWHA. The upper right graph illustrates the influence of the Galerkin projection of

Figure 8.2. Logarithmic plot of the eigenvalues λ_j of the left-hand side matrix M (red), the preconditioned matrix for FEWHA (teal) and the projected preconditioned matrix for augmented FEWHA (dashed orange) as a function of the index number j .

the initial residual r_0 , again with respect to the preconditioned matrix. In the last graph the projection by the matrix H is taken into account by considering the j -th eigenvector u_j of the projected and preconditioned matrix $J^{-1/2}H^T M H J^{-1/2}$, corresponding to augmented FEWHA. We observe how the augmentation procedure influences the value of (r_0, u_j) . The structure of the initial residual for the classical FEWHA with 4 PCG iterations is similar to the one in the upper right graph. The influence of the matrix H is shown in the last graph. In general, applying H decreases the value of (r_0, u_j) , which is beneficial for the error estimate shown in Equation (6.9).

Based on the analysis above we hypothesize that augmented FEWHA requires a lower number of iterations compared to the original algorithm to obtain a similar quality for the tomographic reconstruction. We verify this hypothesis by numerical simulations in the upcoming section.

8.1.2 Numerical simulations

In this section, we verify whether the augmentation procedure enables us to reduce the number of PCG iterations while keeping the quality of the classical FEWHA. We restrict ourselves to the 3 layer configuration, because we want to omit the time intensive mirror fitting step. Since augmented FEWHA is designed to be fast, we verify that the quality requirements for MAORY can be fulfilled for a speed oriented set-up. Note that the method is capable of handling a 9 layer configuration as well. Both methods use a Jacobi preconditioner with a different weighting of the high and low frequency regimes. For details about the preconditioner we refer to Section 4.3.4. The optical

Figure 8.3. Plot of the energy of the unprojected and projected initial residual with respect to the eigenvectors of the preconditioned matrix $J^{-1/2}MJ^{-1/2}$ and the projected preconditioned matrix $J^{-1/2}H^T MHJ^{-1/2}$ as a function of the index j .

strength, altitude and wind speed are listed in Table 7.3. The wavefront compensation is performed using the DMs defined in Table 7.6. To evaluate the quality we use the LE Strehl in K band, i.e., at 2200 nm, after 500 time steps. We use a photon flux of 10^4 for the high flux simulations and between 100 and 500 photons per subaperture per frame for the low flux tests. If not explicitly mentioned, we simulate LGS with spot elongation and a detector read-out noise of $3.0 e^-$ per pixel per frame for the LGS as well as the NGS WFSs. We study the sensitivity of our algorithm against the amount of noise and method specific parameters.

High flux simulations

First, we focus on a test setting which is not greatly influenced by noise. We fix the number of detected photons per subaperture to 10000. Moreover, we simulate LGS detectors that do not suffer from spot elongation. Hence, the noise for the LGSs is modeled as for the NGSs; see Section 2.4.1 and Section 2.4.1 for details.

In order to find the optimal parameter values for the high flux simulations, we start with a sensitivity study of augmented FEWHA against method specific parameters. We vary the regularization parameter α , the preconditioner threshold τ and the loop gain. Note that the spot elongation tuning parameter α_η is not used here, since we simulate LGSs without spot elongation. Moreover, we analyze the influence of the number of PCG iterations for FEWHA and its augmented version.

The left plot of Figure 8.4 illustrates the influence of the regularization parameter α on the center (orange) and average (teal) LE Strehl. The regularization parameter varies between 0.2 and 32, while all other parameters are kept constant. We observe that the optimal α for this simulation is 16. Note that α is an online parameter, i.e., it can be updated on the fly. In the right plot of Figure 8.4 the sensitivity of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA with respect to the number of PCG iterations is shown. We observe that augmented FEWHA provides already a good quality when using only 1 iteration. The quality slightly improves for a higher number of PCG iterations. The center (orange) and average (teal) LE Strehl of FEWHA with only 1 or 2 iterations suffers heavily.

In the left plot of Figure 8.5 we show the influence of the preconditioning parameter τ on the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl, while keeping all other parameters constant. We vary the parameter value between 10^0 and 10^9 . We observe that values between 10^5 and 10^7 provide a very similar LE Strehl, with the optimal value of 10^6 . Note that the influence of this parameter depends on the number of PCG iterations, which was 2 for this setting. In contrast to the other parameters, τ is an offline parameter and has to be fixed in advance.

Figure 8.4. The left plot shows the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl for augmented FEWHA as a function of the regularization parameter α . The right plot illustrates the influence of the number of PCG iterations for FEWHA and its augmented version.

The sensitivity of the method with respect to the gain is illustrated in the right plot of Figure 8.5. All other parameters are kept constant again. For a very high gain the method suffers heavily in terms of quality. For values between 0.2 and 0.8 the sensitivity of augmented FEWHA against the gain is not very high. The optimal value for this test configuration is 0.8. The gain is an online parameter and can be updated on the fly.

The left plot of Figure 8.6 shows a contour plot of the 1 arcmin FoV simulated with augmented FEWHA and 2 PCG iterations. We use the optimal parameter set determined above, i.e., $\alpha = 8$, $gain = 0.8$ and $\tau = 10^6$. In the right plot of Figure 8.6 we illustrate the LE Strehl versus the field off-axis position. Here the number of PCG iterations for FEWHA and its augmented version vary. We can confirm the hypothesis from the previous section that augmented FEWHA requires less PCG iterations to obtain a similar quality compared to the classical algorithm. In fact, augmented FEWHA with 2 PCG iterations provides almost the same quality as FEWHA with 4 iterations. Using augmented FEWHA with only 1 iteration yields already a good quality, which is superior to FEWHA with 2 iterations.

Figure 8.7 shows the SE Strehl (dashed) and the LE Strehl (solid) over 500 time steps for FEWHA (left) and augmented FEWHA (right). From this plot we can confirm the hypothesis that augmented FEWHA with 1 or 2 iterations provides a similar SE and LE Strehl than FEWHA with 4 iterations during the whole time frame. For FEWHA with 2 iterations we see fluctuations in the SE Strehl and a significant lower LE Strehl.

Note that the PCG method with only 1 iteration coincides with the steepest descent method, since the difference between those methods lies only in the computation of

Figure 8.5. Plot of the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl of augmented FEWHA as a function of the preconditioner parameter τ (left) and the loop gain (right).

Figure 8.6. Plot of the LE Strehl over the 1 arcmin FoV (left) and versus the field off-axis position in arcsec (right) after 500 time steps. High flux simulation with $n_{photons} = 10000$. The left plot is simulated with augmented FEWHA and 2 PCG iterations.

Figure 8.7. Plot of the on-axis LE Strehl over 500 time steps. High flux simulation with $n_{photons} = 10000$. For FEWHA (left) we use 2 and 4 iterations and for augmented FEWHA (right) 1 and 2 iterations.

the search directions. For the PCG method those are chosen M -conjugate to each other. When using the augmented PCG algorithm we choose the current search direction $p_k^{(i+1)}$ in addition M -conjugate to the search directions of the previous time step $p_k^{(i)}$ for $k = 1, \dots, maxIter$. Hence, if we use only 1 augmented PCG iteration the initial direction $p_0^{(i+1)}$ is chosen M -conjugate to the search direction of the previous time step $p_k^{(i)}$.

The flux level is directly related to the amount of noise. A higher number of photons per subaperture per frame corresponds to less noise. We increase now the noise level and study the performance of our method for lower flux levels. Moreover, we simulate LGSs with spot elongation and use the parameter α_η for fine tuning.

Low flux simulations

As before we start with optimizing the method specific parameters via numerical simulations. The study is performed for a flux level of $n_{photons} = 500$. In addition, we list the optimal method specific parameter values for all other photon flux levels used throughout the thesis. An automatic adjustment of, e.g., α , with the discrepancy principle is not possible, because of the strict real-time requirements.

The plot on the left side of Figure 8.8 illustrates the influence of the regularization parameter α on the center (orange) and average (teal) LE Strehl. The regularization parameter varies between 0.1 and 16, while all other parameters are kept constant as defined in Table 8.11. We observe that the method reacts very sensitive with respect

Figure 8.8. Plot of the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl for augmented FEWHA as a function of the regularization parameter α (left) and the spot elongation tuning parameter α_η (right).

to this parameter. A too large α has a significant negative influence on the LE Strehl. Hence, the relation between the fitting and the penalty term in Equation (4.15) has to be balanced in the right way. High values of α induce an over regularization of the problem, and thus degrade the reconstruction quality of the method. Note that the optimal value of $\alpha = 0.2$ for the low flux simulations is completely different than that for the high flux simulation with $\alpha = 16$. A similar behavior was observed for the classical FEWHA in [23]. In general, we would expect for an inverse problem that the regularization parameter is smaller for less noise. However, the number of photons in our simulations influences the covariance matrix of noise C_η , see Equation (2.3) and Equation (2.6). Hence, we are solving a different problem with a different left-hand side matrix.

From the right plot of Figure 8.8 we observe the influence of the spot elongation parameter α_η on the center (orange) and average (teal) LE Strehl. The parameter varies between 0 (full NGS model) and 1 (full LGS model) and determines the influence of the noise covariance matrix C_η for spot elongation. Again, all the other parameters are kept constant as defined in Table 8.11. We conclude that the spot elongation noise has to be taken into account to obtain a good LE Strehl. When using the full NGS model, which corresponds to $\alpha_\eta = 0$, the quality of the method suffers heavily. Numerical simulations show that for a lower photon flux level the optimal value of α_η is higher, independent from the AO system.

In the left plot of Figure 8.9 we illustrate the influence of the preconditioning parameter τ on the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl, while keeping all other parameters constant. We vary the parameter value between 10^0 and 10^9 . From the plot we conclude that the LE Strehl increases with a larger thresholding parameter until the optimal value

Figure 8.9. Plot of the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl of augmented FEWHA as a function of the preconditioner parameter τ (left) and the loop *gain* (right).

of 10^7 and then starts to decrease. Here we have a very similar behavior to the high flux simulations in Figure 8.5 (left), but the optimal value is slightly different.

In the right plot of Figure 8.9 we show the sensitivity of the method with respect to the gain. For a very low gain the method suffers heavily in terms of quality. For values between 0.4 and 0.8 the sensitivity of augmented FEWHA against the gain is not very high. The optimal value for this test configuration is 0.6. Comparing with the high flux simulation in Figure 8.5 (right) we have a similar behavior with a slightly different optimal value.

Figure 8.10 shows the sensitivity of augmented FEWHA and the classical FEWHA with respect to the number of PCG iterations. We observe that augmented FEWHA provides already a good quality when using only 1 iteration. In contrast, the classical FEWHA suffers heavily in terms of quality when performing only 1 iteration. More than 4 iterations do not yield quality improvements neither for FEWHA nor for its augmented version. Comparing with the high flux simulation in Figure 8.4 (right) we observe that the augmentation procedure is more effective there.

This parameter optimization has to be done for different flux levels separately. Especially the spot elongation parameter α_η is sensitive with respect to the photon flux. Table 8.11 shows the method parameters for all flux levels used for the simulations in this thesis. We observe that the optimal values for the regularization parameter α and the gain do not change. The parameter α_η varies slightly.

Before studying the behavior of our method against further flux levels, we provide a similar study as for the high flux case, but with 500 photons per subaperture. In the left plot of Figure 8.12 we show a contour plot of the 1 arcmin FoV for augmented FEWHA

Figure 8.10. Plot of the average (teal) and center (orange) LE Strehl of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA as a function of the number of iterations.

Parameter	Flux level				
	500	400	300	200	100
α	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
α_η	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8
τ	10^7	10^7	10^7	10^7	10^7
gain	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6

Table 8.11. MCAO method parameters for different flux levels given in photons per subaperture per frame.

Figure 8.12. Plot of the LE Strehl over the 1 arcmin FoV (left) and versus the field off-axis position in arcsec (right) after 500 time steps. Low flux simulation with $n_{photons} = 500$. The contour plot in (left) is obtained with augmented FEWHA and 2 PCG iterations.

with 2 PCG iterations. The plot on the right side of Figure 8.12 presents the LE Strehl versus the field off-axis position. We observe that augmented FEWHA enables us to decrease the number of iterations, while almost keeping the quality. However, in the low flux case the performance of augmented FEWHA seems to suffer more compared to the classical algorithm. We conclude that with a lower photon flux and in this regard a higher level of noise, reusing search directions from previous time steps becomes less effective.

Figure 8.13 shows the SE Strehl (dashed) and LE Strehl (solid) over 500 time steps for FEWHA (left) and augmented FEWHA (right). Again we observe that augmented FEWHA with 1 or 2 iterations provides a similar SE and LE Strehl than FEWHA with 4 iterations during the whole time frame. Although for the high flux cases the performance of augmented FEWHA was better compared to FEWHA.

Sensitivity with respect to noise

Figure 8.14 illustrates the sensitivity of our method with respect to the photon flux level on the center LE Strehl (left) and on the average LE Strehl (right). We use the optimal parameter values listed in Table 8.11. We observe that the noise has a crucial impact on the performance of augmented FEWHA. With increasing photon flux the method shows deficiencies in the reconstruction quality. Especially when comparing with the high flux simulation in Figure 8.7, where augmented FEWHA provides a significantly better quality.

Figure 8.13. Plot of the on-axis SE Strehl (dashed) and LE Strehl (solid) over 500 time steps. Low flux simulation with $n_{photons} = 500$. For FEWHA (left) we use 2 and 4 iterations and for augmented FEWHA (right) 1 and 2 iterations.

Figure 8.14. Plot of the on-axis (left) and average (right) LE Strehl after 500 time steps. Low flux simulation with photon flux between 100 and 500, spot elongation and a read-out noise of 3 electrons per subaperture per frame. For FEWHA we use 2 and 4 iterations and for augmented FEWHA 1 and 2 iterations.

8.1.3 Sensitivity with respect to the Fried parameter

In Figure 8.15 we illustrate the influence of the Fried parameter r_0 on the off-axis LE Strehl of FEWHA with 4 (upper left) and 2 (lower left) PCG iterations and augmented FEWHA with 2 (upper right) and 1 (lower right) iterations. Larger values of r_0 correspond to good seeing conditions, whereas smaller values refer to bad seeing and strong perturbations. Hence, a lower Fried parameter provides a lower LE Strehl.

The quality evaluation for the MCAO system configuration reveals that with augmented FEWHA we are able to reduce the number of PCG iterations. Especially for higher flux levels the method outperforms the classical FEWHA, even with a considerably lower number of PCG iterations. For low flux levels the augmentation procedure is less effective. We conclude that augmented FEWHA with 2 iterations provides a suitable quality for all simulations performed above. Moreover, the augmentation procedure enables us to decrease the number of iterations to 1 while still providing an acceptable quality. In contrast, the quality for FEWHA with only 1 iteration is far below the requirements. We continue with studying the performance of our method for a wide field of view LTAO system.

8.2 LTAO system for a wide field of view

In order to validate the performance of augmented FEWHA in greater detail we study an LTAO system with guide stars positioned in a wider field of view. The 6 LGS are positioned in a circle of 7.5 arcmin diameter and the 3 NGS in a circle of 10 arcmin diameter. The telescope configuration is the same as for the MCAO system and given in Table 7.2. The parameters for the WFSs are listed in Table 7.11. We use a single DM (M4) for the correction. The DM configuration is given in Table 7.6. Again we use the LE Strehl in K band after 500 time steps to evaluate the quality. The wavelet method is configured to reconstruct 9 atmospheric layers as given in Table 7.13. Here we use the mirror fitting step as defined in Chapter 6 to fit the mirror shape to the reconstructed atmosphere. We study the performance of FEWHA and its augmented version for different flux levels.

Influence of method parameters

In order to find the optimal parameter values for our simulations, we start again with analyzing the sensitivity of our algorithm against method specific parameters. We vary the regularization parameter α , the spot elongation tuning parameter α_η , the preconditioner threshold τ , the loop gain and the number of PCG iterations. The study is performed

Figure 8.15. Plot of the LE Strehl of FEWHA with 4 (upper left) and 2 (lower left) iterations and augmented FEWHA with 2 (upper right) and 1 (lower right) iterations versus the field off-axis position. The LE Strehl is taken after 500 time steps for different Fried parameters r_0 . Low flux simulation with 500 photons per subaperture per frame.

Figure 8.16. Plot of the center LE Strehl for augmented FEWHA as a function of the regularization parameter α (left) and the spot elongation tuning α_η (right).

for augmented FEWHA with 8 PCG iterations and a flux level of $n_{photons} = 500$. The higher number of iterations for the reconstruction here is again determined via numerical simulations; see Figure 8.18.

In the plot on the left side of Figure 8.16 we illustrate the influence of the regularization parameter α on the on-axis LE Strehl. We vary the regularization parameter between 8 and 256, while all other parameters are kept constant as defined in Table 8.19. We observe that the method reacts very sensitive with respect to this parameter. Choosing α too small or too large has a significant negative impact on the LE Strehl. In contrast to the MCAO system simulation, where the optimal value for α is 0.2, the optimal regularization parameter here has a significantly higher value of 40.

In the right plot of Figure 8.16 we observe the influence of the spot elongation parameter α_η on the center LE Strehl. The parameter varies between 0 (full NGS model) and 1 (full LGS model) and determines the influence of the noise covariance matrix C_η for spot elongation. Again, all the other parameters are kept constant as defined in Table 8.19. We examine that the spot elongation noise has to be taken into account to obtain a good LE Strehl. When using the full NGS model, which corresponds to $\alpha_\eta = 0$, the quality of the method suffers.

From the left plot of Figure 8.17 we observe the influence of the preconditioning parameter τ on the center LE Strehl. We vary the parameter value between 10^0 and 10^8 . The LE Strehl increases with a larger thresholding parameter until the optimal value of 10^5 and then starts to decrease. Note that the influence of this parameter depends on the number of PCG iterations, which was 8 for this setting. In contrast to the other parameters τ is an offline parameter and has to be fixed in advance.

Figure 8.17. Plot of the center LE Strehl of augmented FEWHA as a function of the preconditioner parameter τ (left) and the loop *gain* (right).

In the right plot of Figure 8.17 we show the sensitivity of the method with respect to the loop gain. For a very low gain the method suffers heavily in terms of quality. The optimal value for the LTAO test configuration is 0.9. Note that the gain is an online parameter and can be updated on the fly.

Figure 8.18 shows the sensitivity of augmented FEWHA and the classical FEWHA with respect to the number of PCG iterations. We observe that augmented FEWHA provides a better quality than the classical FEWHA when using the same number of PCG iterations. Hence, the augmentation procedure offers either the possibility to reduce the number of iterations and in this regard the run-time while keeping the quality or to increase the LE Strehl. For the upcoming sections we will use 6 and 8 PCG iterations for augmented FEWHA and 8 and 10 iterations for the classical method.

Table 8.19 summarizes the optimal method parameters for the LTAO system simulation for different flux levels. All parameter are determined via numerical simulations.

8.2.1 Low flux simulations

Figure 8.20 shows the SE Strehl (dashed) and the LE Strehl (solid) over 500 time steps. In the left plot we use the classical FEWHA and in the right plot the augmented version. We observe that augmented FEWHA with 6 or 8 iterations provides a similar quality as FEWHA with 10 iterations during the whole time frame.

Figure 8.21 illustrates the sensitivity of our method with respect to the photon flux level on the center LE Strehl. As for the MCAO system, we observe that noise has a

Figure 8.18. Plot of the center LE Strehl of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA as a function of the number of iterations.

Parameter	Flux level				
	500	400	300	200	100
α	40	40	32	32	32
α_η	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8
τ	10^5	10^5	10^5	10^5	10^5
<i>gain</i>	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9

Table 8.19. LTAO method parameters for different flux levels given in photons per subaperture per frame.

Figure 8.20. Plot of the on-axis SE Strehl (dashed) and LE Strehl (solid) over 500 time steps. Low flux simulation with $n_{photons} = 500$. For FEWHA (left) we use 8 and 10 iterations and for augmented FEWHA (right) 6 and 8 iterations.

crucial impact on the performance of augmented FEWHA. With decreasing photon flux the method shows deficiencies in the reconstruction quality compared to the classical method when using a smaller number of iterations. Note that if we would increase the number of iterations for augmented FEWHA to 8 or 10 the quality becomes at least as good as for the classical algorithm.

8.2.2 Sensitivity with respect to the Fried parameter

Figure 8.22 shows the on-axis LE Strehl versus the Fried parameter r_0 of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA with PCG iterations as indicated in the legend. Larger values correspond to good seeing conditions, hence, to weak turbulence, whereas smaller values refer to bad seeing and strong perturbations. We observe that the difference between augmented FEWHA with 8 iterations and FEWHA with 10 iterations is negligible. Augmented FEWHA with 6 iterations provides a better quality than FEWHA with 8 iterations.

Similar to the MCAO system simulations, the quality evaluation for the LTAO system reveals that with augmented FEWHA we are able to reduce the number of PCG iterations. We conclude that augmented FEWHA with 6 iterations provides a suitable quality for all simulation performed above. When using augmented FEWHA with 8 PCG iterations we can increase the reconstruction quality compared to the classical FEWHA. In the upcoming section we focus on the computational performance of augmented FEWHA on real-time hardware architectures.

Figure 8.21. Plot of the on-axis LE Strehl after 500 time steps. Low flux simulation with photon flux between 100 and 500, spot elongation and a read-out noise of 3 electrons per subaperture per frame. For FEWHA we use 8 and 10 PCG iterations and for augmented FEWHA 6 and 8 PCG iterations.

Figure 8.22. Plot of the on-axis LE Strehl of augmented FEWHA with 6 (teal) and 8 (orange) iterations versus the Fried parameter r_0 after 500 time steps. Low flux simulation with 500 photons per subaperture per frame.

Chapter 9

Numerics: Theoretical performance analysis

This section is dedicated to the complexity analysis of the real-time computing (RTC) algorithms. We provide details about the matrix-free representation of the operators involved and the parallelization possibilities for FEWHA and its augmented version. Moreover, we give a theoretical performance analysis of the MVM algorithm. An estimation of the system memory capabilities, necessary to implement the most demanding tasks, is also reported. The analysis treats the hard real-time as well as the soft real-time tasks. We apply the theoretical results to test configurations defined in Chapter 7. This enables us to estimate the computational throughput required to decide for a suitable real-time hardware. The results in this chapter are to a large extent taken from our paper about the feasibility of standard and novel solvers for atmospheric tomography in [43].

9.1 Block operators

FEWHA has the ability to represent its components in a matrix-free manner. Such a representation considerably reduces the required memory as well as the number of FLOPs. However, for modern real-time systems the number of FLOPs and memory usage is not the only performance indicator. Properties such as structured memory accesses or parallelization possibilities play a crucial role as well. In the following, we discuss the matrix-free representation of the block operators of (augmented) FEWHA, such as the SH operator, the bilinear interpolation and the wavelet transform. All of them play a significant role in the costs required for the algorithm, i.e., the application of M as defined in Equation (5.11). Moreover, these operators are involved in the

computation of the right-hand side b defined in Equation (5.3.3). In addition, we state the number of FLOPs and the required memory for the operators. Note that there is no difference in the discretization between FEWHA and its augmented version, and thus the matrices involved coincide. Hence, the descriptions below are valid for both algorithms. The computational estimates are mainly based on the number of subapertures n_s^2 of the WFSs in use and the number of layer discretization points $n_{lay} = 2^{2J_\ell}$, where J_ℓ denotes the number of wavelet scales on layer ℓ .

9.1.1 SH operator

For a specific SH WFS with n_s^2 subapertures the operator Γ maps wavefronts to the average x- and y-slopes of the subapertures of the WFSs. We discretize these wavefronts by continuous piecewise bilinear functions with $(n_s + 1)^2$ nodal values. Hence, the dimension of Γ is $2n_s^2 \times (n_s + 1)^2$. Storing a full matrix of this dimension requires $2n_s^2(n_s + 1)^2$ units of memory. The number of FLOPs for performing a matrix-vector multiplication with this matrix sum up to $4n_s^3(n_s + 2)$. The piecewise bilinear basis used for discretization has local support. In fact, it interacts with at most four subapertures. The measurement in a single subaperture is only influenced by the wavefront function at the corner points of the respective subaperture. Thus, one row of Γ , which corresponds to one subaperture, has only four non zero entries. This sparse matrix representation enables to considerably reduce the FLOPs to $14n_s^2$ and the memory requirements to $8n_s^2$.

The structure of Γ offers the possibility to implement the operator in matrix-free way, which further reduces the FLOPs and memory usage. We split the computation of x-slopes in Equation (2.11) into two parts. In a first step, we calculate and store the differences between the nodal values. In a second step, we calculate the averages. The same procedure is applied for the y-slopes in Equation (2.12). The total number of FLOPs for the matrix-free implementation decreases to $6n_s^2 + 2n_s$ and the memory usage to $n_s^2 + n_s$.

9.1.2 Bilinear interpolation

The bilinear interpolation operator $P_{g\ell}$ maps the reconstructed layers to wavefronts using piecewise bilinear basis functions. The layers are discretized using a grid with $2^{J_\ell} \times 2^{J_\ell}$ points and the wavefronts using a grid with $(n_s + 1) \times (n_s + 1)$ values projected onto layer ℓ and guide star direction g ; see Figure 9.1. The dimension of the full matrix $P_{g\ell}$ is $2^{2J_\ell+1} \times (n_s + 1)^2$. Hence, the operation in a full matrix representation requires $(2^{2J_\ell+1} - 1)(n_s + 1)^2$ FLOPs and $2^{2J_\ell}(n_s + 1)^2$ units of memory. However, these quantities can be optimized by a matrix-free representation.

Figure 9.1. Square grid of layers Ω_ℓ in black with $2^{2J_\ell} = 2^4$ points and equidistant spacing. Projected grid of subapertures Ω in red with $n_s^2 = 16$ subapertures obtained by a bilinear interpolation. The blue rectangles represent the result after a linear interpolation in x-direction.

A bilinear interpolation is the concatenation of two linear interpolations, one in x- and one in y-direction. We utilize this fact for an efficient matrix-free representation. We illustrate the procedure on the example of Figure 9.1. In a first step, we interpolate in x-direction and obtain as results the blue rectangles. Afterwards, we interpolate in y-direction and obtain the projected grid (red). A matrix-free linear interpolation requires $2(n_s + 1)$ units of memory and 3 operations per interpolation point. Altogether, this leads to $(n_s + 1)^2 + 4(n_s + 1)$ units of memory and at most $6(n_s + 1)^2$ FLOPs. The number of operations here depends on the guide star direction and the altitude of the respective layer, thus, we state an upper bound.

9.1.3 Wavelet transform

The discrete wavelet transform (DWT) W and its transposed operator W^T consist of the application of the direct transformation matrices W_j and W_j^T , respectively, at each wavelet scale $j = 0, \dots, J - 1$. These matrices can be represented by a set of convolution operations with the corresponding wavelet coefficients. In fact, the representation as a convolution is more efficient than using sparse matrices; see, e.g. [123].

The wavelet coefficients are stored within a matrix of dimension $2^{j+1} \times 2^{j+1}$. Hence, the overall costs for applying the direct or inverse DWT with a wavelet filter of length p are

$$\sum_{j=0}^{J-1} 2(2p-1)2^{2(j+1)} = \frac{8}{3}(2p-1)(2^{2J}-1),$$

where J is the overall number of wavelet coefficients. In all our simulations we use Daubechies 3 wavelets, i.e., $p = 6$, which leads to $(88/3)(2^{2J}-1)$ FLOPs. In terms of

memory we have to store the wavelet filter of length p , which is almost negligible, and a temporary variable for the intermediate results at scale j for the application of W_j and W_j^T . Summarizing, this leads to 2^{2J} units of memory in the matrix-free implementation.

9.1.4 Inverse covariance of noise

The inverse noise covariance operator C_η^{-1} in the direction of an LGS consists of the correlation information between the measurements x-x, y-y, x-y and y-x. Since the correlation between x-y and y-x coincides, the matrix is symmetric. Hence, we only need to store 3 vectors of size n_s^2 . These vectors only change when the WFS geometry or the laser launch position is changed. We apply this operator by multiplying the measurement vector by the 3 vectors. For an NGS direction we only have to store the scalar parameter σ^{-2} . To summarize, the operator requires for an LGS direction $6n_s^2$ FLOPs and for an NGS direction $2n_s^2$ FLOPs. The memory consumption sums up to $6n_s^2$ for LGSs and essentially 0 for NGSs.

9.1.5 Tip-tilt removal operator

The tip-tilt removal operator $(I - T)$ calculates the average slopes of the measurements in x- and y-direction, respectively. These average values correspond to the tip and tilt of the wavefront, and thus are subtracted from the measurements. In total, this leads to $4n_s^2$ FLOPs and no additional memory consumption.

9.1.6 Inverse covariance of turbulence

Finally, we discuss the operator D , which approximates the inverse covariance matrix of turbulence C_ϕ^{-1} , see Section 6.4.2, with a diagonal matrix. Here we only store the weights at each wavelet scale, which sum up to 2^{2J_ℓ} FLOPs and a memory consumption of J_ℓ .

9.1.7 Performance estimates

Table 9.2 and Table 9.3 summarize the performance estimates of the matrix-free operators described above in terms of FLOPs and memory usage. In addition to the theoretical results, we provide the values for the MAORY test configuration defined in Chapter 7. We observe that both quantities have significantly smaller values when using a matrix-free representation. Especially for the wavelet transform, which is the most demanding

operator, the difference is significant. The reduction in the number of FLOPs is of order $2 \cdot 10^3$ and for the memory usage of order $16 \cdot 10^3$. A performance optimization for the full matrix representation by using sparse matrices is possible, but not considered in this thesis.

Operator	Full matrix FLOPs	Matrix-free FLOPs
SH matrix	$2n_s^2(n_s + 1)^2 = 61.605\text{M}$	$6n_s^2 + 2n_s = 33.004\text{k}$
Bilin. interpolation	$(2^{2J_\ell+1} - 1)(n_s + 1)^2 = 184.314\text{M}$	$6(n_s + 1)^2 = 33.750\text{k}$
Wavelet transform	$(2^{2J_\ell+1} - 1)2^{2J_\ell+1} = 1.074\text{G}$	$\frac{88}{3}(2^{2J_\ell} - 1) = 480.570\text{k}$
Inv. cov. noise LGS	$(2n_s^2 - 1)n_s^2 = 59.968\text{M}$	$6n_s^2 = 32.856\text{k}$
Inv. cov. noise NGS	$(2n_s^2 - 1)n_s^2 = 59.968\text{M}$	$2n_s^2 = 10.952\text{k}$
TT removal	$(2n_s^2 - 1)n_s^2 = 59.968\text{M}$	$4n_s^2 = 21.904\text{k}$
Inv. cov. turbulence	$(2 \cdot 2^{2J_\ell} - 1)2^{2J_\ell} = 536.85\text{M}$	$2^{2J_\ell} = 16.384\text{k}$

Table 9.2. Theoretical FLOPs for the operators of (augmented) FEWHA for the matrix-based as well as the matrix-free version. The values correspond to the MAORY test configuration and indicate the significant benefit of the matrix-free representation.

9.2 Parallelization

Without parallelization it would not be possible to meet the real-time requirements of a large AO system as, e.g., required for the control of the ELT. The hard- and soft real-time costs for the MVM are mainly caused by computing the pseudo open loop slopes and the deformable mirror commands in hard real-time and the (FR) matrix update in soft real-time. All these operations consist of matrix-vector multiplications and can be efficiently parallelized using standard linear algebra libraries. For (augmented) FEWHA parallelization is more complicated, because of the more complex structure of the algorithm. In fact, the method allows two types of parallelization, which we refer to as global and local parallelization. By global parallelization we understand the decomposition of the operators involved into L or W blocks. Local parallelization refers to parallelization inside these blocks. The combination of these two strategies leads to a very efficient parallelization scheme. The parallelization strategy for augmented FEWHA is the same as for the original algorithm.

Operator	Full matrix mem. usage	Matrix-free mem. usage
SH matrix	$2n_s^2(n_s + 1)^2 = 61.61\text{MB}$	$n_s^2 + n_s = 5.55\text{kB}$
Bilin. interpolation	$2^{2J_\ell}(n_s + 1)^2 = 921.60\text{kB}$	$(n_s + 1)^2 + 4(n_s + 1) = 5.93\text{kB}$
Wavelet transform	$2^{4J_\ell} = 268.44\text{MB}$	$2^{2J_\ell} = 16.38\text{kB}$
Inv. cov. noise LGS	$n_s^4 = 29.987\text{MB}$	$6n_s^2 = 32.86\text{kB}$
Inv. cov. noise NGS	$n_s^4 = 29.987\text{MB}$	0
TT removal	$n_s^4 = 29.987\text{MB}$	0
Inv. cov. turbulence	$2^{4J_\ell} = 268.44\text{MB}$	$J_\ell = 7\text{B}$

Table 9.3. Memory usage in Byte for the operators of (augmented) FEWHA for full matrices as well as for the matrix-free version. The values correspond to the memory usage for the MAORY test configuration and demonstrate the significant benefit of the matrix-free representation.

9.2.1 Global parallelization

We illustrate the idea behind the global parallelization strategy of FEWHA on the matrix-free application of the left-hand side matrix M of Equation (5.10). This operator is applied once per PCG iteration and is the computationally most demanding part of the overall algorithm. Similar strategies are used for the right-hand side b of Equation (4.15). The matrix M consists of several sparse matrices, in particular, a discrete wavelet transform, a bilinear interpolation and a SH operator. These matrices have a block diagonal structure, where the number of blocks corresponds to either the number of atmospheric layers L or WFSs W . Since this block structure decouples the problem, we have the possibility to parallelize over either the number of layers L or WFSs W . However, parallelization can not be applied perfectly, because after a certain number of steps synchronization is necessary. Figure 9.4 shows a schematic representation of the global parallelization scheme. The kernels indicated on the right side of the figure refer to the parallel blocks of the algorithm. *Kernel1* performs an inverse wavelet transform, which is parallelizable over the number of layers L . *Kernel2* applies the atmospheric tomography operator A , decomposed into a SH-matrix Γ and a bilinear interpolation matrix P . Further, the inverse covariance matrix C_η^{-1} is applied together with Γ^T . This kernel is parallelized over the number of WFSs W . Finally, *Kernel3* applies the transposed bilinear interpolation matrix P^T , the transposed inverse wavelet transform and adds the regularization term αD in L parallel blocks. After each kernel, FEWHA requires a synchronization step (dashed lines). This is not optimal for certain hardware architectures, especially for GPUs, since they are optimized for computational throughput and latency can become a problem.

Figure 9.4. Parallelization of the application of the matrix M over W WFSs and L layers. The dashed lines indicate synchronization steps.

9.2.2 Local parallelization

Each block of the block diagonal matrices of FEWHA consists of operations that are applied to a grid of values and can be independently computed from each other. Local parallelization is performed inside each parallel kernel of Figure 9.4. The number of threads for local parallelization is related to the size of the block in the respective matrix. The dimensions of the matrices correspond to the number of layer discretization points $n_{lay} = 2^{2J_\ell}$ and the number of subapertures n_s^2 . These quantities have values up to a few hundred. For the implementation of these parallelization strategies on certain hardware architectures we refer to Chapter 10. In the following, we provide details on the parallelization of the matrix-free operators described in Section 9.1.

The SH operator Γ consists of two operations executed sequentially for the x- and y-directions. In particular, the operator computes differences followed by an averaging step; see Equation (2.11) and Equation (2.12). These operations are performed for a grid of $2(n_s + 1)n_s$ values. The computation for each grid point is independent from the other points, and thus can be fully parallelized.

The bilinear interpolation consists of two sequential operations. A linear interpolation into the x-direction and a linear interpolation into the y-direction. Again, the computation is performed on a grid of values, where the computation on each grid point is independent from the others. Hence, the interpolation into the x- and y-directions can be parallelized over $(n_s + 1)^2$ grid points.

The discrete wavelet transform consists also of two sequential operations at each wavelet scale $j = 0, \dots, J-1$. The direct transform sequentially applies the operator W_j twice to matrices of dimension $2^{j+1} \times 2^{j+1}$. The inverse transform applies the same operation, but with the matrix W_j^T ; see Equation (4.26). Each of the $(2^{j+1})^2$ entries of the resulting matrices can be calculated independently from the others. Hence, parallelization is applied over $(2^{j+1})^2$ entries.

Note that the parallelization over all grid points is just a theoretical outcome. In practice, one is limited by the amount of threads that are available on a certain hardware architecture. Moreover, depending on the hardware it can be more efficient to split the work to a smaller number of threads.

9.3 Overall hard and soft real-time FLOPs

In this section, we present the theoretical performance estimates of FEWHA, augmented FEWHA and the MVM algorithm in terms of FLOPs. We distinguish between FLOPs that are required to perform the hard real-time task and those required for soft real-time.

9.3.1 Wavelet reconstructor

The most time consuming steps for the hard real-time of (augmented) FEWHA are the application of M in the atmospheric tomography step and partially in computing the right-hand side and the fitting step. Below, we provide the number of FLOPs required for all the components within the augmented FEWHA algorithm.

Based on the estimates for the block operators in Section 9.1 we are able to analyze the computational cost for each component of our algorithm. For the sake of simplicity we make the following assumptions: The WFSs associated to all the guide stars use the same geometry with n_s^2 subapertures. Moreover, we assume that all layers are discretized using the same number of points. Note that there is a linear relation between the number of layer discretization points and the number of subapertures. The number of wavelet scales J is chosen in a way that the grid of layers overlaps the wavefront grid, i.e.,

$$2^{2(J_\ell-1)} < (n_s + 1)^2 \leq 2^{2J_\ell}.$$

Let us neglect the preconditioner and the left-hand side operator for a moment. Then the PCG method, as shown in Algorithm 2, consists of 8 vector operations. The diagonal Jacobi preconditioner is stored in a single vector of size $2^{2J}L$. Hence, the application of the preconditioner requires $2^{2J}L$ FLOPs. In total, one iteration of the PCG method requires $9 \cdot 2^{2J}L$ FLOPs plus the FLOPs for applying the left-hand side operator. The parameter J denotes the number of wavelet scales on all layers $\ell = 1, \dots, L$. We can apply parallelization within the PCG method in terms of vector operations. For the augmented PCG there are two additional parts: the projection of the initial guess c_0 and the initial residual r_0 onto the Krylov subspace of the previous system and the projection of the descent directions p_k onto the last vector of the descent directions of the previous system p_m in every time step. Our numerical simulations in Chapter 8 reveal that we are able to significantly reduce the number of PCG iterations with the augmentation procedure. Hence, the overhead induced for augmented FEWHA should be easily compensated by the reduction in the number of iterations.

In the mirror fitting step we apply two subsequent operations. First, the reconstructed layers are transformed back from the wavelet domain into the bilinear domain. Afterwards, the fitting operation is applied depending on the AO system; see Section 6.5. In this thesis we focus on a 3 layer MCAO and a 9 layer LTAO system. For the 3 layer MCAO system we do not need any fitting step, since the layers are directly reconstructed at the altitudes of the DMs. Hence, only the wavelet transform at every layer remains, which requires $\frac{88}{3}L(2^{2J} - 1)$ FLOPs. Note that this operation can be performed in parallel over the number of layers L . For the LTAO system we have an additional projection step, which requires $7(L - 1)n_a^2$ FLOPs.

Table 9.5 shows the overall FLOPs for FEWHA and its augmented version. The additional FLOPs for augmented FEWHA are marked in orange. The term $9n_{lay}^2L \cdot n_{augIter}$ is related to the projection of the initial residual, whereas the term $4n_{lay}^2L$ corresponds to the projection in each iteration. Instead of n_{iter} only $n_{augIter}$ iterations are performed.

Next, we determine the number of FLOPs of the direct MVM method.

9.3.2 MVM method

The main contribution in terms of computational costs for the soft real-time part of the MVM is the update of the (FR) matrix and there, in particular, the matrix inversion. The computational costs listed in Table 9.6 are estimated assuming that the matrix inversion is performed through a Cholesky decomposition. Note that one benefit of (augmented) FEWHA is that there are no additional soft real-time costs. Because it is an iterative approach, there is no need to precompute any inverse matrix and the whole computation is done in hard real-time. The hard real-time computational costs for the

Computation step	FLOPs
POL data computation	$(8n_s^2 + 2n_s)G$
Right hand side	$[14G_{LGS} + 2G_{NGS} + 6G]n_s^2 + 2Gn_s$ $+[(L - 1)(8.5G_{LGS} + 10G_{NGS}) + L(G - 1)](n_s + 1)^2$ $+(L + 1) + \frac{88}{3}(4n_{lay}^2 - 1) + n_{lay}^2 L$
Update residual	$2n_{lay}^2 L$
PCG method FEWHA	$\{[14G_{LGS} + 2G_{NGS} + 12G]n_s^2 + 4Gn_s$ $+[(L - 1)(15.6G_{LGS} + 18G_{NGS}) + L(G - 1)](n_s + 1)^2$ $+L\frac{176}{3}(4n_{lay}^2 - 1) + 13n_{lay}^2 L\}n_{iter}$
PCG method aug. FEWHA	$\{[14G_{LGS} + 2G_{NGS} + 12G]n_s^2 + 4Gn_s$ $+[(L - 1)(15.6G_{LGS} + 18G_{NGS} + L(G - 1)](n_s + 1)^2$ $+L\frac{176}{3}(4n_{lay}^2 - 1) + 13n_{lay}^2 L + (9n_{lay}^2 L + 4n_{lay}^2 L)\}n_{augIter}$
Fitting	$(L - 1)M(n_s + 1)^2 + L\frac{88}{3}(4n_{lay}^2 - 1) + Ln_{lay}^2$
Control	$3n_a^2$

Table 9.5. Hard real-time FLOPs for FEWHA and its augmented version. The additional FLOPs for augmented FEWHA and the different number of PCG iterations are marked in orange.

MVM are dominated by two contributions, which require about the same amount of operations: the pseudo open loop (POL) slopes computation, similar to (augmented) FEWHA, and the computation of the deformable mirror commands via a matrix-vector multiplication. The results are summarized in Table 9.7. The parameter n_{opt} denotes the number of optimization directions and n_{ml} is the number of modes used in the modal description of each layer.

9.3.3 Overall FLOPs for the MCAO configuration

In order to compare the computational throughput required for the MVM, FEWHA and augmented FEWHA, we apply the theoretical results from above to the MAORY test configuration defined in Chapter 7. The MCAO system is considerably complex and provides a suitable example to illustrate the advantages of (augmented) FEWHA.

The left plot of Figure 9.8 shows the hard and soft real-time FLOPs for the MVM (red),

Computation step	FLOPs
Computation of R	$n_s^6 + 4n_{ml}n_s^4L + (2n_{ml}^2L - n_{ml}L + 2)n_s^2$
Computation of F	$n_a^3 + (2n_{ml} + 2n_{ml}L + n_{opt} - 1)n_s^2$ $+ (2n_{ml}^2L + n_{opt}^2n_{ml}L - 3n_{ml}L)n_a$
Computation of FR	$(2n_{ml}L - 1)n_a^2n_s^2$

Table 9.6. Soft real-time FLOPs for the MVM algorithm.

Computation step	FLOPs
POL data computation	$2n_s^2Gn_a^2 - n_s^2G + 6n_sG$
Matrix vector mult. $(FR)s$	$2n_a^2n_s^2G - n_a^2$

Table 9.7. Hard real-time FLOPs for the MVM algorithms.

FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange). We observe the benefits of FEWHA and its augmented version compared to the MVM. Both wavelet reconstructors require only about 1/12 of the hard real-time FLOPs compared to the MVM. For the soft real-time part, since (augmented) FEWHA does not involve any significant computation, there is an evident advantage compared to the MVM algorithm.

Figure 9.8. Hard and soft real-time FLOPs for one time step for the MVM algorithm (red), FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange). In the left plot we simulate the MCAO system and in the right plot the LTAO system.

We assume $n_{augIter} = n_{iter}/2$, i.e., 4 iterations for FEWHA and 2 for augmented FEWHA. Then the classical PCG method used within FEWHA requires 63.5 MFLOPs and the augmented PCG 33.5 MFLOPs. This results in a reduction of about 20% of FLOPs

for the overall FEWHA algorithm. Note that utilizing augmented FEWHA with only 1 iteration, which still provides an acceptable quality as shown in Chapter 8, reduces the number of FLOPs even further.

9.3.4 Overall FLOPs for the LTAO configuration

The plot on the right side of Figure 9.8 shows the hard and soft real-time FLOPs for the MVM (red), FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) for the LTAO system defined in Chapter 7. Here we fix n_{iter} to 8 and $n_{augIter}$ to 6. As for the MCAO setting, the number of FLOPs for (augmented) FEWHA is significantly lower. Both wavelet reconstructors require only about 1/10 of the hard real-time FLOPs compared to the MVM. For the soft real-time part there is again a huge benefit with respect to the MVM algorithm. The higher number of FLOPs for the soft-real time part of the MVM for the LTAO system compared to the MCAO configuration is caused by a larger number of layers and a larger number of subapertures for the lower order WFSs (74×74 instead of 2×2).

The classical PCG method used within FEWHA requires about 357 MFLOPs and the augmented PCG 279 MFLOPs. We are able to save more than 20% of FLOPs when using the augmentation procedure. Note that the higher number of FLOPs here compared to the MCAO test configuration is caused by a larger number of layers and more PCG iterations.

9.4 Memory usage

The feature of (augmented) FEWHA of representing almost all of its components in a matrix-free way leads to a substantial reduction in storage. Table 9.9 shows in detail the memory usage for FEWHA and its augmented version. The additional memory requirements for the augmented PCG are marked in orange. For augmented FEWHA we have to save the descent directions p_k and $q_k = Mp_k$ for $k = 1, \dots, n_{augIter}$. Additionally, to decrease the number of FLOPs and avoid unnecessary recomputations we save the inner products (p_k, q_k) . Both vectors are of size $n_{lay}^2 L$, hence, in total we need $(2n_{lay}^2 L + 1)n_{augIter}$ units of additional memory.

In this work we only take into account the main contributions in terms of matrices required to perform the MVM method. This is, primarily, storing the huge (FR) matrix. The dimension of this matrix is $n_a^2 \times n_s^2$, which can become very large for ELTs. Hence, the memory requirements for the MVM are $n_a^2 n_s^2$. Note, that an optimization in terms of memory is possible, but usually involves a trade-off with respect to the computational

Computation step	Memory usage
POL data computation	$(2n_s^2 + n_s n_{phi})G$
Right hand side	$G + [0.7G_{LGS} + G_{NGS}](L - 1)(n_s + 1)^2 + Ln_{lay}^2$
Update residual	$L2^{2J_i}$
PCG method FEWHA	$2Gn_s^2 + G + [0.7G_{LGS} + G_{NGS}](L - 1)(n_s + 1)^2 + Gn_s n_{phi} + 4Ln_{lay}^2$
PCG method aug. FEWHA	$2Gn_s^2 + G + [0.7G_{LGS} + G_{NGS}](L - 1)(n_s + 1)^2 + Gn_s n_{phi} + 4Ln_{lay}^2 + (2n_{lay}^2 L + 1)n_{augIter}$
Fitting	$G(L - 1)(n_s + 1)^2 + 2Ln_{lay}^2$
Control	Mn_a^2

Table 9.9. Required memory for FEWHA and the additional memory consumption for augmented FEWHA (orange).

time. Here, we do not consider any optimization strategies.

9.4.1 Memory usage for the MCAO configuration

We illustrate the benefits of FEWHA and its augmented version in terms of memory usage on the test case of MAORY. The left plot of Figure 9.10 shows the units of memory in GB required for the MVM (red), FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange). Note that we assume here single precision (32 bit) floating point numbers. We observe the significant lower memory requirement of FEWHA (8 MB) and its augmented version (8.8 MB) compared to the MVM algorithm. The memory intensive MVM method requires 53 GB, mainly caused by storing the huge (FR) matrix.

The additional units of memory required for the augmentation procedure sum up to approximately 0.8 MB for this test configuration. Compared to the overall memory usage of FEWHA and especially compared to the memory intensive MVM method this additional units of memory are almost negligible.

Figure 9.10. Memory usage for the MVM (red), FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) for the MCAO (left) and LTAO (right) configuration.

9.4.2 Memory for the LTAO configuration

In the plot on the right side of Figure 9.10 we illustrate the amount of memory in GB required for the MVM (red), FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) for the LTAO system configuration. We observe a significant lower memory requirement for FEWHA (15 MB) and its augmented version (20.6 MB) compared to the MVM algorithm (60 GB).

The additional storage costs for the augmentation procedure sum up to 5.6 MB for this test configuration. Again we conclude that compared to the overall memory usage these contributions are almost negligible.

9.5 Real-time system

We determine a possible real-time hardware architecture, on the basis of the computational throughput requirements ascertained in the previous sections. We base the architectural design on the results accumulated within the GreenFlash research activity; see [38, 39]. The outcome of this study, in which CPU, FPGA and GPU technologies have been compared, has indicated that the most suitable technology for the computational engine of an ELT-class real-time hardware system is the GPU. Another important outcome of the study is that the FPGA technology is still superior for the smart-interfacing, i.e., at providing the interfaces between sensors and mirrors and the computational core. However, the Greenflash studied assumed the MVM as a reconstruction algorithm and did not consider (augmented) FEWHA.

Taking into account the computational load determined for the MVM, a single GPU would not achieve the computational throughput needed to meet the real-time requirements of MAORY. Thus, we suggest to use an off-the-shelf product, namely, the DGX-1 supercomputer by NVIDIA; see [124]. This workstation is equipped with 8 Tesla V100 GPUs connected by a dedicated ultra high speed bus (NVLINK). We suggest to use the DGX-1 for the hard as well as the soft real-time engine. Since the computational load of FEWHA is significantly lower, in theory, a single Tesla V100 or an off-the-shelf CPU should provide enough computational power to meet the real-time requirements. Moreover, for FEWHA no additional soft real-time engine is needed. Altogether, this leads to significant lower hardware requirements and likewise costs for (augmented) FEWHA compared to the MVM.

Chapter 10

Numerics: Performance on real-time hardware

This chapter is dedicated to a detailed study on the computational performance of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA on different real-time hardware architectures. The control of a large AO system, required for the new generation of ELTs, is a complex and crucial task. In order to meet the real-time requirements, an efficient reconstructor implemented on a high performance hardware architecture is inevitable. We focus here on the implementation of FEWHA and its augmented version on CPU and GPU, based on our analysis in Section 9.5. We provide an overview on several parallel programming models for CPUs and GPUs, which we utilize for performance optimization. We follow the work in [40] for CPUs and [41] for GPUs. The run-time analysis for FEWHA and its augmented version on CPU and GPU is performed for the test configurations defined in Chapter 7. The results presented in this chapter are mainly based on our work about the parallel implementation of an iterative solver for atmospheric tomography in [26].

10.1 Implementation on CPU

In the following, we describe two concepts for parallelization on a multi-core CPU, namely, threads and vectorization. We use both of them for the parallelization of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA. The first one is employed for the global parallelization scheme, whereas the second one is used for local parallelization of the individual operators; see Section 9.2. The global parallelization strategy on CPUs is implemented through the popular environment OpenMP¹, which is a portable standard for shared

¹<https://www.openmp.org/>

memory programming. OpenMP is supported by several compilers like, e.g., GCC or Clang. For local parallelization we apply the concept of vectorization using Intel AVX2² vector instructions.

10.1.1 Thread programming

We implemented the global parallelization scheme of (augmented) FEWHA on the CPU using OpenMP, which turned out to be very efficient for parallelizing simple loops in different applications as shown, e.g., in [125–127]. Each kernel in Figure 9.4 corresponds to a parallel OpenMP region. In addition to the *omp parallel for* directive, which indicates a parallelizable loop, we use the variable *OMP_NUM_THREADS* to restrict the regions to either *L* or *W* threads. For more details on OpenMP we refer to Chapter 3.

10.1.2 Single Instruction Multiple Data

For CPUs it has been shown, e.g. in [128], that for problems involving task and data parallelization techniques, Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) vectorization is a crucial concept for achieving reasonable performance. This is in agreement with what we observe for FEWHA and its augmented version. During our studies it turned out that the combination of OpenMP parallel regions for global parallelization and vector extensions for local parallelization provides best results. In contrast, using OpenMP nested parallelism induces too much overhead. This is reported for other applications as well, e.g., in [129]. Several loops inside the FEWHA algorithm are already auto-vectorized by the GCC compiler. However, when dealing with more complex constructs, compilers come to their limits; see, e.g., [130]. That is why we add explicit vectorization for the discrete wavelet transform, the SH operator and the bilinear interpolation to fully exploit the computational potential of the CPU. Since version 4.0 OpenMP supports SIMD instructions by using the directive *omp simd*. This statement indicates that the respective loop can be transformed into a SIMD loop. Beside OpenMP, there exist several other ways to include explicit SIMD vectorization. In fact, in all our simulations Intel intrinsics provide best results.

10.2 Implementation on GPU

On the NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU; see Section 7.3 for the hardware specifications; we utilize CUDA 10.1 to implement the parallelization scheme. CUDA offers special C++

²<https://software.intel.com/content/www/us/en/develop/documentation/cpp-compiler-developer-guide-and-reference/top/compiler-reference/intrinsics.html>

functions, called kernels, that are executed in parallel by a certain number of threads. For more details on CUDA we refer to Chapter 3.

In a first attempt, we utilized unified memory for the parallel version on the GPU. This concept handles the copy operations between CPU and GPU automatically, and thus provides an easy way to port an existing C++ code to CUDA. However, numerical simulations show that this approach is not satisfying and we decided to handle these copy operations by our own. In fact, for the final implementation of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA all computations are done by the GPU. This strategy minimizes host/device memory transfers, which are costly in terms of computational performance. We utilize CUDA kernels with L or W blocks for global parallelization. Although, L and W are usually low (below 10) the global parallelization strategy provides a significant speed up of the overall method, since the computations inside are very time intensive.

Figure 10.1. Concept of dynamic parallelism.

The local parallelization scheme on the GPU is implemented using CUDA dynamic parallelism with an optimized number of threads; see Figure 10.1. This concept makes it possible to launch kernels from threads, which run on the device, i.e., a thread can launch other threads. We implement the discrete wavelet transform similar to the one proposed in [131] and [132]. Moreover, we apply various optimization techniques that are common for NVIDIA GPUs. Global memory loads and stores of the 32 threads of a warp are merged by NVIDIA GPUs into the fewest possible number of transactions. This effect is known as memory coalescing. We utilize this feature and align the data for the operators to minimize the DRAM bandwidth usage. In addition, CUDA provides user defined vectorized memory load and store instructions, similar to the SIMD instructions we used for local parallelization on the CPU. Utilizing these vectorization strategy it was possible to improve the performance of the operators even further. These operations load and store data in 64- or 128-bit widths, and thus reduce the total number of instructions

and latency, and improve bandwidth utilization. The fact that global memory and shared memory have different speed in access by several orders of magnitude offers another possibility to improve performance. Because shared memory is on-chip, the latency is roughly 100 times lower than for uncached global memory on a NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU; see [124]. We utilize shared memory for the implementation of the matrix-free SH operator. This operator reuses data elements from memory, thus, moving these elements first to shared memory and being able to access them afterwards with lower latency is beneficial for the computational performance. Unfortunately, the other operators do not share this structure and shared memory does not yield comparable gains.

10.2.1 Optimized implementation of the PCG method

Based on the work in [133] we use an optimized version of the PCG for GPUs, which is shown in Algorithm 7. Our aim is to minimize the number of kernel calls, global memory loads and the communication overhead. By (\cdot, \cdot) we denote the standard ℓ_2 scalar product. These scalar products are grouped together and computed within a single kernel to reduce the number of synchronizing steps and kernels on GPU and CPU (steps 6-7). Within the main loop we load vectors at the same place and apply vector operations within a single kernel to allow multiple operations to reuse the data (steps 9-12). In the end, this approach has more floating point operations than the original one, however, shows a better performance on the GPU.

10.3 Computational performance for different AO systems

This section is dedicated to a detailed study of the computational performance of augmented FEWHA for different AO systems on a multi-core CPU and a GPU. We start with analyzing the local parallelization strategy, which is valid for both methods and all test configurations listed in Chapter 7. We continue with the overall run-time of the algorithms for the LTAO and MCAO system configuration defined in Chapter 7.

10.3.1 Performance of the local parallelization strategy

The performance verification for the local parallelization strategy of augmented FEWHA involves the run-time analysis of the matrix-free block operators, i.e., the bilinear interpolation, the SH operator and the discrete wavelet transform as described in Section 9.1. Figure 10.2 shows the block operators on the CPU (red) and on the GPU (green). Note that there is no difference between FEWHA and its augmented version in the local parallelization strategy. Hence, the graphs are valid for both algorithms. Although all

Algorithm 7 PCG on GPU for $Mc = b$

```

1: Input:       $r$  (residual vector)
                  $J$  (Jacobi preconditioner)
                  $M$  (FEWHA left-hand side operator)
                  $c$  (wavelet coefficient vector)
                  $maxIter$  (max. number of PCG iterations)
2: Output:    $c$  (new wavelet coefficient vector),  $r$  (new residual vector)
3: for  $iter = 0, 1, \dots, maxIter$  do
4:    $z = J^{-1}r$ 
5:    $s = Mz$ 
6:    $\rho = (r, z)$ 
7:    $\mu = (s, z)$ 
8:    $\beta = \rho / \rho_{old}$ 
9:    $\alpha = \rho / (\mu - \rho\beta / \alpha)$ 
10:   $\rho_{old} = \rho$ 
11:   $p = z + \beta p$ 
12:   $q = s + \beta q$ 
13:   $c = c + \alpha p$ 
14:   $r = r - \alpha q$ 
15: end for

```

these operators are applied in a matrix-free manner, the dimensions of the matrices still influence the computational speed. For all simulations we run 1000 loop iterations and take the average run-time.

In the upper left plot of Figure 10.2 we study the scalability of the discrete wavelet transform \mathbf{W} of dimension $n_{lay}^2 \times n_{lay}^2$ with respect to the number of layer discretization points n_{lay} . For our test configurations this parameter has a value of 128. We observe that for small matrix sizes the CPU clearly outperforms the GPU version. However, for bigger matrix dimensions the GPU shows its benefits. The time required for the execution on the GPU grows almost linearly with the matrix sizes. The reason is that parallelization on GPUs is very efficient. Note that for a higher value of n_{lay} the local parallelization strategy on the CPU, implemented through vectorization, might not be optimal. However, the optimization for large values of n_{lay} with, e.g., OpenMP nested parallelism, are beyond the scope of this thesis, since they are not relevant for the test configurations defined in Chapter 7.

The upper right plot of Figure 10.2 shows the scalability of the bilinear interpolation operator P of size $(n_s + 1)^2 \times n_{lay}^2$ with respect to the number of subapertures n_s . We fix n_{lay} to 128 for these test runs. Since the number of entries per row of P is constant; see Section 9.1; n_{lay} does not influence the overall performance. The number of subapertures

n_s for the test configurations used throughout this thesis is fixed to either 74 or 2. We observe a similar behavior as for the discrete wavelet transform. For small values of n_s the CPU version clearly outperforms the GPU. Again we want to point out that an optimization of the CPU implementation for higher values of n_s may be possible.

The plot on the bottom of Figure 10.2 shows the scalability of the SH operator Γ of dimension $2n_s^2 \times (n_s + 1)^2$ with respect to the number of subapertures n_s . Here we can clearly examine the benefit of shared memory. It is the only case where the GPU version is almost as fast as the CPU based implementation even for small dimensions.

Figure 10.2. Analysis of the local parallelization strategy for the discrete wavelet transform (upper left), the bilinear interpolation (upper right) and the SH operator (bottom). The simulations are performed with (augmented) FEWHA on the CPU (in red) and the GPU (in green).

For ELT-sized test configurations we are dealing with values of n_s and n_{lay} that are below the intersection point between the GPU (green) and CPU (red) curve. Hence,

for our test configurations the CPU based implementation clearly outperforms the GPU version for all the matrix-free block operators. Only for larger matrix sizes the GPU starts to show its benefits. However, these large values are far beyond the scope of the ELT specifications and just of academic interest. GPUs outperforming CPUs only for an increasing workload was observed for other applications as well; see, e.g., [134]. Note that this outcome does not contradict with the GreenFlash study in [38], since they analyzed feasible real-time architectures for the MVM method. The MVM approach involves considerably more FLOPs; see Section 9.3.3.

10.3.2 Overall performance for the MCAO system simulation

In the following, we provide the run-time results of FEWHA and its augmented version for the MAORY test configuration defined in Chapter 7. As hardware we use again one node of Radon1 for the CPU implementation and a Tesla V100 GPU; see Section 7.3. The main goal of this section is to verify that augmented FEWHA is able to fulfill the run-time requirements of MAORY. To prove this, we use a 3 layer MCAO configuration with 1 or 2 augmented PCG iterations. In Chapter 8 we verified that this configuration is able to provide a suitable reconstruction quality in terms of LE Strehl ratio. MAORY is operating at 500 Hz, hence, the real-time requirement is 2 ms.

From the left plot of Figure 10.3 we observe the computational performance of FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) on the multi-core CPU with a varying number of threads for global parallelization. For augmented FEWHA we use 1 and 2 iterations, whereas for FEWHA we utilize 4 PCG iterations. We observe that we already obtain a good performance with only 3 threads, related to the 3 layers. In fact, the best result is obtained when using 6 threads. The number 6 here corresponds to the number of high-order WFSs, which have a larger number of subapertures of 74×74 , and thus also significant more computations involved than the 3 low-order ones with 2×2 subapertures. For more than 6 threads the elapsed time stays the same or slightly increases. Comparing FEWHA and its augmented version we observe that augmented FEWHA is faster, caused by the lower number of PCG iterations.

Figure 10.4 shows the performance of FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) with a different number of PCG iterations on the GPU (left) and the CPU (right). We reconstruct 3 layers using 3 DMs for wavefront correction as defined in Chapter 7. We observe the linear increase in run-time with an increasing number of PCG iterations. This is what we expect as the PCG iterations are not parallelizable. Moreover, we see that the performance of augmented FEWHA is slightly worse compared to FEWHA when using the same number of PCG iterations. This behavior is caused by additional computations involved for the augmentation procedure, such as scalar products and vector updates. Comparing the GPU and the CPU performance we observe that the CPU implementation clearly outperforms the GPU one. On the multi-core CPU we are

Figure 10.3. Scalability of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA with different number of threads on the CPU for the MCAO configuration (left) and the LTAO system (right).

able to fulfill the real-time requirements of 2 ms with augmented FEWHA when using 2 or less PCG iterations. On the GPU the computational performance is far beyond the goal. When using 2 PCG iterations on the CPU the run-time limit is only barely undercut with about 1.8 ms. However, we have shown in Chapter 8 that the augmentation approach enables to decrease the number of iterations even to 1. Hence, it offers the possibility to perform the reconstruction in about 1.3 ms with acceptable sacrifices in terms of LE Strehl. If we consider the classical FEWHA with 4 PCG iterations, we are not able to run the MAORY configuration in real-time. Note that this outcome depends highly on the CPU in use. An optimization in terms of CPU hardware, e.g., a higher clock frequency, is possible and would improve the run-time.

Figure 10.5 illustrates the influence of the number of layers in the computational performance of (augmented) FEWHA. The different number of PCG iterations are indicated in the legend. The number of DMs is fixed here to the number of layers, in order to omit the mirror fitting step. The first three DMs are configured as listed in Chapter 7, whereas for the additional DMs we use the setting of DM2 in Table 7.6 with altitudes equal to the layer heights. We observe that both algorithms parallelize very well with respect to the number of layers on the GPU as well as on the CPU. For an increasing number of layers, the elapsed time only slightly increases. Moreover, we examine again that the CPU is considerably faster than the GPU.

We conclude that augmented FEWHA for the MAORY test configuration with 3 layers and 2 PCG iterations is able to meet the real-time requirements on an off-the-shelf CPU, as shown in Figure 10.4. The classical FEWHA with 4 PCG iterations is not able to fulfill this requirement. The poor performance of the GPU compared to the

Figure 10.4. Scalability of FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) with different number of PCG iterations on the GPU (left) and CPU (right) for the MCAO system configuration.

CPU of all our test runs is mainly caused by the following reasons: For the global parallelization scheme we are just parallelizing over up to 9 layers, or 9 WFSs, which is far too little to fully exploit GPU resources. This outcome is not new and was observed for other applications as well, e.g., in [134]. The GPU is designed to handle a big amount of simple tasks in parallel. On the other hand, CPUs are better for algorithms that are more difficult to run in parallel and require synchronization steps; see [135]. All these observations indicate that our implementation for the MAORY test configuration is memory bandwidth bounded, i.e., further parallelization or vectorization does not improve the run-time as memory accesses are the bottleneck. The term bandwidth here refers to the amount of data that is moved from or to a given destination. The problem of bandwidth bound occurs when the computational intensity is too low. Since for augmented FEWHA the number of FLOPs is drastically reduced by the matrix-free implementation, the memory bandwidth becomes the limiting factor. Moreover, some of the matrix-free operators involve random memory access, which is a common problem for, e.g., sparse matrix algebra or hash table lookups; see [136]. If memory is accessed sequentially it is very likely that the next requested data already resides in the cache, and thus can be accessed very fast. For random memory accesses, this becomes very much unlikely, resulting in a high percentage of calls to the slow main memory. This behavior is commonly referred to as cache misses.

For many recent and future scientific simulations off-chip memory bandwidth is a limiting factor for the computational performance. We hypothesize that this is the case for FEWHA and its augmented version as well. To validate this hypothesis we utilize the roofline model; see [137]; which offers an intuitive way to visualize the trade-off between computational intensity and data movement. In the context of this model we use the

Figure 10.5. Scalability of FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) with different number of layer on the GPU (left) and CPU (right) for the MCAO system configuration. For FEWHA we utilize 4 PCG iterations and for augmented FEWHA 1 or 2 iterations. The number of DMs is chosen equally to the number of layers.

term operational intensity, by which we understand the number of operations per byte of DRAM traffic. The total bytes accessed are those that go to main memory after being filtered by the cache hierarchy. The roofline model visualizes FLOPs, the operational intensity and the memory performance together in a two dimensional graph. The x-axis shows the operational intensity in FLOPs/Byte, whereas the y-axis indicates the floating point performance in GFLOPs/sec, both in logarithmic scale. The peak floating point performance is represented by a horizontal line. Obviously, the performance of any kernel cannot be better than that. Moreover, the DRAM bandwidth, i.e., how many bytes of data a given memory can deliver per second, is shown as a diagonal line. These two lines give the model its name, as they set an upper bound for the performance of kernels.

Figure 10.6 shows the roofline model for one node of the Radon1 cluster (left) and for the NVIDIA Tesla V100 (right); see Section 7.3 for the hardware specifications. The computationally most demanding kernels of the global parallelization scheme of augmented FEWHA for the MAORY test configuration are indicated by dots for a multi-core CPU of Radon1 (orange) and for the Telsa V100 GPU (red). These kernels are related to the application of the matrix M as shown in Figure 9.4. For a detailed description of the kernels we refer to Section 9.2. Since the kernels do not differ for FEWHA and its augmented version, the roofline models are valid for both algorithms. For the GPU we use NVIDIA Nsight Compute, which is part of the CUDA toolkit, to determine the measurements of the roofline model. For the CPU we utilize the Intel Advisor 2021. Both profiling tools offer an intuitive way to create roofline models either

for NVIDIA or Intel hardware. Kernels that lie on left side of the dashed, black line are memory bandwidth bounded, whereas kernels that lie on the right side are compute bounded. We can observe that all our kernels lie within the memory bandwidth bounded area. All these test runs are based on a matrix-free implementation. For a matrix-based version of FEWHA we would have to store a huge amount of data, which leads to time consuming copy operations for MAORY-sized test configurations. Moreover, a (sparse) matrix representation is even more memory bandwidth bounded.

Figure 10.6. Roofline model for one node of Radon1 (left) and a Tesla V100 GPU (right) of the computationally most demanding parts of (augmented) FEWHA.

Note that the number of FLOPs computed by the Intel Advisor or NVIDIA NSight Compute differ from the theoretically calculated FLOPs shown in Figure 9.8. It is known that the hardware performance counters which are used to count floating point arithmetic operations tend to over count on recent processors; see, e.g., [138]. The event counter increments every time the processor is dispatching the corresponding floating point instruction to the execution units. If the input data is not available due to a cache miss, the instruction will be rejected and retried a few cycles later. Especially for applications with a high cache miss rate this results in a significant over count. For our application the over count ratio is at about 2.

To analyze the computational performance of our method in greater detail, we study next the wide field of view LTAO system as defined in Chapter 7.

10.3.3 Results for the LTAO system simulation

In the following, we provide the run-time results of FEWHA and its augmented version for the LTAO test configuration defined in Chapter 7. We reconstruct 9 layers using a single DM. The PCG method within FEWHA is configured with 8 iterations, whereas for the augmented PCG we use 6 and 8 iterations. We run our numerical simulations again on one node of Radon1 for the CPU implementation and on a Tesla V100 GPU.

The plot on the right side of Figure 10.3 illustrates the performance of FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) on the multi-core CPU with a varying number of threads for global parallelization. In contrast to the MCAO configuration, we require 9 threads for a good performance. This is caused by the larger number of layers and the higher number of subapertures for the low-order WFSs (74×74 instead of 2×2) used within this test configuration. For more than 9 threads the elapsed time stays the same or slightly increases. Note that for some measurement points augmented FEWHA is even slightly faster than the classical algorithm. This is caused by side effects on the CPU, such as jitter, which influence the computational performance. We conclude that the additional steps for augmentation procedure are almost negligible for the run-time. Since augmented FEWHA with 6 PCG iterations provides a similar quality than FEWHA with 8 iterations, we can again considerably improve the run-time with the augmentation procedure.

Figure 10.7 shows the performance of FEWHA (dashed) and augmented FEWHA (solid) with a different number of PCG iterations on the GPU (left) and the CPU (right). We reconstruct 9 layers using a single DM for wavefront correction as defined in Chapter 7. As for the MCAO configuration we observe the linear increase in run-time with an increasing number of PCG iterations. Moreover, we notice that the additional computations for the augmentation procedure have a negligible performance impact. Comparing the GPU and the CPU performance we observe a similar behavior as for the MCAO system. The CPU implementation clearly outperforms the GPU one.

Figure 10.8 illustrates the influence of the number of layers on the computational performance of FEWHA and augmented FEWHA. The different number of PCG iterations are indicated in the legend. As for the MCAO system we observe that both algorithms parallelize very well with respect to the number of layers on the GPU as well as on the CPU. Note that in contrast to the MCAO system simulation the number of DMs is fixed to 1 here. For an increasing number of layers the elapsed time almost stays the same, because we apply here global parallelization using L threads. Moreover, we notice again that the CPU is considerably faster than the GPU.

Our performance study reveals that augmented FEWHA provides a significant speed-up of the algorithm, while still providing a similar reconstruction quality as FEWHA. Especially for the MAORY simulations the augmentation procedure is crucial to meet

Figure 10.7. Scalability of FEWHA (teal) and augmented FEWHA (orange) with different number of PCG iterations on the GPU (left) and the CPU (right) for the LTAO system configuration.

the real-time requirements. As expected, the choice of the computational architecture has a crucial impact on the performance of both methods. There are various applications in different scientific areas that can gain a significant speed-up from GPUs. However, we demonstrated by numerical simulations that for ELT-sized problems FEWHA and its augmented version perform better on CPUs. This is mainly caused by the low level of parallelization possibilities. The mathematical methodologies utilized within the wavelet based algorithms allow to solve the atmospheric tomography problem with a very low number of FLOPs; see Chapter 9. This is a huge benefit on CPUs. However, GPUs are made for computational throughput, and thus are not the optimal hardware for solving an ELT-sized problem with augmented FEWHA. Nonetheless, we show that for an increasing number of subapertures and actuators, the GPU tends to outperform the multi-core CPU.

Figure 10.8. Scalability of FEWHA with 8 PCG iterations (teal) and augmented FEWHA with 6 (orange) and 8 (blue) PCG iterations on the GPU (left) and the CPU (right) for the LTAO system configuration.

Chapter 11

Conclusion and outlook

In order to obtain good results with AO it is inevitable to implement an efficient real-time reconstructor on a high performance hardware architecture. Especially for the next generation of ELTs, e.g., the ELT of the ESO, the demands on the AO systems will get much higher. In real-time huge amounts of data from WFSs have to be processed and thousands of actuators of the DMs have to be controlled by elaborated algorithms. In this thesis, we present a novel iterative solver for wavefront reconstruction, called augmented FEWHA, which is based on the Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm proposed in [23]. Moreover, we provide a parallel implementation of FEWHA and its augmented version on the hardware solutions of the company Microgate based on GPUs and CPUs. Below, we summarize the outcome of our studies regarding quality and computational speed and state several ideas for future investigations.

11.1 Conclusion

The trade-off between optimal performance and computational complexity for the atmospheric tomography problem of ELTs has triggered the development of iterative real-time reconstructors with a complexity of $\mathcal{O}(n)$ operations. Most of them still rely on the formulation of the forward problem as a matrix equation, i.e., the matrix has to be assembled frequently during the observation of one scientific object. To overcome this limitation, the Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm (FEWHA) has been proposed in [23–25], which allows the inversion of the operator without using a matrix formulation. FEWHA utilizes a conjugate gradient based approach to compute the MAP estimate of the atmospheric tomography problem in the Bayesian framework. The algorithm is known to yield an excellent reconstruction quality for LTAO, MOAO, and MCAO systems. However, the real-time requirements of ELTs are hard to fulfill.

In this thesis, we extended FEWHA with an augmented Krylov subspace method, which enables us to reduce the number of PCG iterations, and thus the run-time of the algorithm. Within AO we are dealing with several right-hand sides b of Equation (5.3), available consecutively in every time step. Since the PCG method is an iterative solver we need to reapply it in each time step. This is costly in terms of computational speed compared to direct solvers, where the factorization can be reused independently of the right-hand side as long as the left-hand side matrix does not change. However, when solving the atmospheric tomography problem in (5.3) we can exploit the fact that the right-hand side only changes slightly from one time step to another. The basic idea is to speed up the convergence of the current time step by using the search directions obtained from the previous system.

In terms of quality, augmented FEWHA provides similar results as the classical FEWHA, since only the PCG method is changed. However, the number of PCG iterations can be considerably reduced. In fact, our analysis of convergence rates in Chapter 8 reveals that the PCG iterations can be reduced to almost 50%. We verified this hypothesis via numerical simulations for configurations similar to MAORY and a wide field of view LTAO system.

In Chapter 9 we provide a theoretical performance analysis of the MVM, FEWHA and augmented FEWHA in order to be able to decide on a suitable real-time hardware architecture for MAORY. The analysis of FLOPs and memory usage shows the significant advantage of the wavelet methods compared to the MVM. Based on these theoretical results we provide in Chapter 10 a parallel implementation of both wavelet algorithms on a multi-core CPU and a GPU. On the CPU we use C++ and a combination of OpenMP and Intel AVX instructions for parallelization. The GPU version is implemented in CUDA 10.1. In all our simulations the GPU shows a rather poor performance compared to the CPU. This is mainly caused by the low level of parallelization possibilities, which are far too little to fully utilize GPU resources. Since for augmented FEWHA the number of FLOPs is drastically reduced by the matrix-free implementation, the memory bandwidth becomes the limiting factor. Moreover, some of the matrix-free operators involve random memory access, which is a common problem for, e.g., sparse matrix algebra or hash table lookups.

In conclusion, we show that the reduction of PCG iterations is crucial for the computational performance. In fact, the augmentation procedure enables to fulfill the real-time requirements of MAORY.

11.2 Outlook

In this thesis, we provide a parallel implementation of augmented FEWHA on CPUs and GPUs, but omitted the FPGA technology due to high development costs. In future, we plan to go further into the direction of efficient real-time reconstruction for ELTs and investigate an implementation of the algorithm on FPGAs. The industrial partner Microgate has developed a very specific know-how in developing fully customized solutions based on large clusters of mixed DSP-FPGA boards and, more recently, on FPGAs only. This hardware has been employed to perform fundamental tasks in AO, like wavefront sensing and real-time wavefront reconstruction. Providing a package for the real-time control of AO systems, including their custom solutions based on FPGAs together with the efficient real-time reconstructor augmented FEWHA would make the company uniquely positioned in the marketplace. As programming language we use the Very High Speed Integrated Circuit Hardware Description Language (VHDL), which is a formal language intended for use in all phases of the creation of electronic systems. Because it is both, machine readable and human readable, it supports the development, verification, synthesis, and testing of hardware designs, the communication of hardware design data, and the maintenance, modification, and procurement of hardware.

In order to achieve a good correction with AO not only an efficient wavefront reconstruction algorithm implemented on high performance hardware is necessary, but also an accurate model of the deformable mirror. The company Microgate is engaged in the final design and construction of the adaptive mirrors for the next generation of ELTs, which requires accurate and demanding simulations of the mirror dynamics. In future, we aim to optimize the Digital Twin of the electromagnetically secondary mirror, which includes the structural dynamics, its interaction with the fluid film interposed between the mirror and its reference back plate and the disturbances due to local air turbulences.

Summarizing, we believe that the presented algorithm is a very promising tool for the wavefront reconstruction for the new generation of extremely large ground based telescopes. So far, the evaluation has only been performed via numerical simulations. In future, it would be amazing to have the opportunity to run the algorithm on a real telescope.

Notation

In this chapter we list abbreviations and variables, which are frequently used throughout this thesis. Table 11.1 shows a collection of abbreviations in alphabetical order and Table 11.2 a set of variables.

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Arithmetic Intensity
ALU	Arithmetic Logical Unit
AO	Adaptive Optics
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
AVX	Advanced Vector Extension
CCD	Charge Coupled Device
CG	Conjugate Gradient
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CUDA	Compute Unified Devices Architecture
CUDART	CUDA Runtime
DM	Deformable Mirror
DRAM	Dynamic Random Access Memory
DSP	Digital Signal Processor
DWT	Discrete Wavelet Transform
ELT	Extremely Large Telescope
ESA	European Space Agency
ESO	European Southern Observatory
FEM	Finite Element Method
FEWHA	Finite Element Wavelet Hybrid Algorithm
FLOP	Floating Point Operations
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array

FWHM	Full Width Half Maximum
GCC	GNU Compiler Collection
GLAO	Ground Layer Adaptive Optics
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GS	Guide Star
HARMONI	High Angular Resolution Monolithic Optical and Near-infrared Integral field spectograph
HO	High Order
HRT	Hard Real Time
LE	Long Exposure
LGS	Laser Guide Star
LL	Laser Launch position
LO	Low Order
LTAO	Laser Tomography Adaptive Optics
MAORY	Multi conjugate Adaptive Optics RelaY
MAP	Maximum A Posteriori
MB	Mega Byte
MCAO	Multi Conjugate Adaptive Optics
METIS	Mid-infrared ELT Imager and Spectograph
MICADO	Multi-AO Imaging CAmera for Deep Observations
MOAO	Multi Object Adaptive Optics
MVM	Matrix Vector Multiplication
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NGS	Natural Guide Star
NVLINK	NVIDIA Link
OS	Operating System
OTF	Optical Transfer Function
PCG	Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient
PCI	Peripheral Component Interconnect
POL	Pseudo Open Loop
POSIX	Portable Operating System Interface
PSD	Power Spectral Density
PSF	Point Spread Function

PWFS	Pyramid Wavefront Sensor
RHS	Right Hand Side
ROMSOC	Reduced Order Modelling Simulation and Optimization of Coupled systems
RON	Read Out Noise
RTC	Real Time Computing
SCAO	Single Conjugate Adaptive Optics
SE	Short Exposure
SH	Shack Hartmann
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
SIMT	Single Instruction Multiple Threads
SPD	Symmetric and Positive Definite
SRT	Soft Real Time
SSE	Streaming SIMD Extensions
TBB	Thread Building Blocks

Table 11.1. List of abbreviations in alphabetical order.

Variable	Description
D	Telescope diameter
$m = 1, \dots, M$	Number of mirrors
$\ell = 1, \dots, L$	Number of layers
$w = 1, \dots, W$	Number of wavefront sensors
$g = 1, \dots, G$	Number of guide stars
G_{NGS}	Number of natural guide stars
G_{LGS}	Number of laser guide stars
n_s	Number of subapertures
n_a	Number of actuators
n_{ml}	Number of modes
n_{opt}	Number of optimization directions
$n_{photons}$	Number of photons
n_{iter}	Number of PCG iterations
$n_{augIter}$	Number of augmented PCG iterations
n_{lay}	Number of layer discretization points

λ	Wavelength
r_0	Fried parameter
θ	Direction
l_0, L_0	Inner and outer scale in Kolomogorov turbulence model
h_ℓ	Height of layer ℓ
J_ℓ	Number of wavelet scales on layer ℓ
δ_ℓ	Spacing on layer ℓ
α	Regularization parameter
α_η	Spot elongation tuning parameter
τ	Preconditioner threshold parameter
$P_{g\ell}$	Projection operator
Γ	Shack Hartmann operator
W	Discrete wavelet transform
F	Mirror fitting operator
C_η	Covariance matrix of noise
C_ϕ	Covariance matrix of turbulence layer
T	Tip-tilt operator
J	Jacobi preconditioner
A	Atmospheric tomography operator
P	Matrix of search directions for augmented PCG
c	Wavelet coefficients
s	Vector of sensor measurements
a	Vector of mirror commands
κ	Condition number

Table 11.2. List of frequently used variables.

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Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Ich, Dipl. Ing. Bernadett Stadler, BSc, geboren am 16. Februar 1992, erkläre an Eides statt, dass ich die vorliegende Dissertation selbstständig und ohne fremde Hilfe verfasst, andere als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel nicht benutzt bzw. die wörtlich oder sinngemäß entnommenen Stellen als solche kenntlich gemacht habe. Die vorliegende Dissertation ist mit dem elektronisch übermittelten Textdokument identisch.

Linz, Oktober 2021

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Curriculum Vitae

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- 07/2008, 08/2009 **System Administrator**, soft technics Engelmaier, Erlauf, Austria

Journal Publications and Proceedings

- [1] A. Rivero Jimenez, P. Solano Lopez, A. Gomez Tato, D. Garcia-Selfa, M. Diaz Mendez, F. Pena, M. Martinolli, B. Stadler, N. Auer and U. Morelli. *Order Reduction on Dynamic Systems using Machine Learning*. In Proc. ESGI139, 2018.
- [2] B. Stadler, R. Biasi, and R. Ramlau. *Feasibility of standard and novel solvers in atmospheric tomography for the ELT*. In Proc. AO4ELT6, 2019.
- [3] R. Ramlau and B. Stadler. *An augmented wavelet reconstructor for atmospheric tomography*. In Electron. Trans. Numer. Anal, 2021.
- [4] B. Stadler, R. Biasi, M. Manetti and R. Ramlau. *Parallel implementation of an iterative solver for atmospheric tomography*. Accepted for Publication.
- [5] R. Ramlau and B. Stadler. *Performance of an iterative solver for MAORY*. In Preparation.

Conferences and Workshops

- 10/2021 ROMSOC Workshop. Talk: *Real-Time Computing Methods for Astronomical Adaptive Optics*, Catania, Italy.
- 10/2021 KLAIM 2021 Conference. Talk: *An Efficient Real-Time Reconstructor for Extremely Large Telescopes*, Kaiserslautern, Germany.
- 05/2021 LIT Lecture JKU. Invited talk: *ROMSOC - An European Graduate School for Applied Mathematics with Industry*, online.
- 01/2021 ECCOMAS 2020 Conference. Talk: *Performance of an iterative solver for atmospheric tomography on real-time hardware*, online.
- 12/2020 SPIE 2020 Conference. Talk: *Performance of an iterative solver for atmospheric tomography on real-time hardware*, online.
- 11/2020 ROMSOC Seminar. Talk: *Real time computing methods for Adaptive Optics*, online.
- 10/2020 WFS Workshop. Talk: *Real-time implementation of an iterative solver for atmospheric tomography*, online.
- 09/2020 ROMSOC Workshop. Talk: *RTC implementation of high-performance algorithms for adaptive optics control*, online.
- 02/2020 AHPC Conference. Talk: *Performance optimizations for the atmospheric tomography problem of extremely large telescopes on real-time hardware*, Klosterneuburg, Austria.

- 10/2019 WIM 2019 Workshop. Talk: *Efficient solvers for atmospheric tomography*, Strobl, Austria.
- 07/2019 ICIAM 2019 Conference. Talk: *Efficient solvers for atmospheric tomography*, Valencia, Spain.
- 06/2019 AO4ELT6 Conference. Poster: *Feasibility of Standard and Novel Solvers in Atmospheric Tomography*, Quebec, Canada.
- 11/2018 L2 Meeting. Talk: *Feasibility of standard and novel solvers for atmospheric tomography*, JKU Linz, Austria.
- 10/2018 ROMSOC Midterm Check. Talk: *Real-time computing methods for astronomical adaptive optics*. Bremen, Germany.

Technical Reports

- ROMSOC Deliverable D5.1 N. Auer, P. Barral, J. Benamou, D. Comesana Fernandez, M. Girfoglio, L. Hauberg-Lotte, M. Hintermüller, W. Ijzerman, K. Knall, P. Maass, G. Marconi, M. Martinolli, P. Monticone, U. Morelli, A. Nayak, L. Polverelli, A. Prieto, P. Quintela, R. Ramlau, R. Conte, G. Rozza, G. Rukhaia, N. Shah, B. Stadler, C. Vergara. *Reports about 8 selected benchmark cases of model hierarchies*. 2018.
- ROMSOC Deliverable D5.2 N. Auer, P. Barral, J. Benamou, D. Comesana Fernandez, M. Girfoglio, L. Hauberg-Lotte, M. Hintermüller, W. Ijzerman, K. Knall, P. Maass, G. Marconi, M. Martinolli, P. Monticone, U. Morelli, A. Nayak, L. Polverelli, A. Prieto, P. Quintela, R. Ramlau, R. Conte, G. Rozza, G. Rukhaia, N. Shah, B. Stadler, C. Vergara. *Software-based representation of selected benchmark hierarchies equipped with publically available data*. 2019.
- ROMSOC Deliverable D3.1 G. Rozza, B. Stadler, R. Ramlau, O. Jadhav, U. Morelli and N. Shah. *Reports on specific reduced order modelling techniques for different applications*. 2019.
- ROMSOC Deliverable D3.2 R. Ramlau and B. Stadler. *Model Reduction and Inverse Problems. In Reports about new model order reduction techniques, error estimators and algorithms*. 2020.
- ROMSOC Deliverable D4.1 R. Ramlau and B. Stadler. *Inverse problems in atmospheric tomography. In Reports about error estimators and data-driven adaptations for modelling and optimization errors*. 2020.
- ROMSOC Deliverable D4.3 R. Ramlau and B. Stadler. *Optimization of an iterative solver for atmospheric tomography on real-time hardware architectures*. 2021.
- ROMSOC Deliverable D5.4 P. Barral, J. Benamou, D. Comesana Fernandez, M. Girfoglio, L. Hauberg-Lotte, M. Hintermüller, W. Ijzerman, K. Knall, P. Maass, G. Marconi, M. Martinolli, P. Monticone, U. Morelli, A. Nayak, L. Polverelli, A. Prieto, P. Quintela, R. Ramlau, R. Conte, G. Rozza, G. Rukhaia, N. Shah, B. Stadler, C. Vergara. *Description of the selected benchmark cases*. 2021.

Teaching Activities

- 02/2021 Seminar in mathematics for high-school students
A cooperation of JKU Linz and the society "Talents Upper Austria"
- 07/2020 Supervision of a student intern
A cooperation of JKU Linz and the society "Talents Upper Austria"

Schools and Training Courses

- 09/2020 3rd Ethics Workshop, online.
- 07/2019 2nd Ethics Workshop, Nuremberg, Germany.
- 07/2019 Optimization methods, FAU Erlangen, Germany.
- 04/2019 Reduced order methods for comp. mechanics, SISSA Trieste, Italy.
- 03/2019 Communicating scientific research, MOX Milano, Italy.
- 11/2018 Introduction to information-based complexity, JKU Linz, Austria.
- 10/2018 1st Ethics Workshop, Nuremberg, Germany.
- 10/2018 Advanced programming for scientific computing, MOX Milano, Italy.
- 08/2018 Hierarchical energy based modeling, TU Berlin, Germany.
- 07/2018 ESGI 139, ITMATI Santiago de Compostela, Spain.
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Language Skills

- German Native
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- Programming Languages C, C++, Java, C#, Python, R, CUDA, VHDL
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- Mathematical Programs Mathematica, Matlab
- Databases MySQL and Oracle

Linz, October, 2021

Bernadett Stadler

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